

The Serbian Society for Ceramic Materials
Institute for Multidisciplinary Research (IMSI), University of Belgrade
Institute of Physics, University of Belgrade
Center of Excellence for the Synthesis, Processing and Characterization of
Materials for use in Extreme Conditions "CEXTREME LAB" - Institute of
Nuclear Sciences "Vinča", University of Belgrade
Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Belgrade
Center of Excellence for Green Technologies, Institute for Multidisciplinary
Research, University of Belgrade
Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade

Edited by:
Branko Matović
Jelena Maletaškić
Vladimir V. Srdić

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Editors-in-Chief

Dr Branko Matović
Dr. Jelena Maletaškić
Prof. Vladimir V. Srdić

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Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade

PROGRAMME AND THE BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

**7th Conference of The Serbian Society for
Ceramic Materials**

June 14-16, 2023
Belgrade, Serbia
7CSCS-2023

Edited by:
Branko Matović
Jelena Maletaškić
Vladimir V. Srdić

SPECIAL THANKS TO

**Република Србија
МИНИСТАРСТВО НАУКЕ,
ТЕХНОЛОШКОГ РАЗВОЈА И ИНОВАЦИЈА**

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ORGANISATION of
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- The Serbian Society for Ceramic Materials
- Institute for Multidisciplinary Research (IMSI), University of Belgrade
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WELCOME MESSAGE

On behalf of the organizers and organizing committee of the 7th Conference of the Serbian Society for Ceramic Materials (7CSCS-2023), I would like to extend my warmest welcome to all of you for attending the 7CSCS-2023. The conference is hosted and organized by the Serbian Society for Ceramic Materials, and co-organized by Institute for Multidisciplinary Research - University of Belgrade, Institute of Physics - University of Belgrade, Center of excellence for the synthesis, processing and characterization of materials for use in extreme conditions “CEXTREME LAB”, Institute of Nuclear Sciences “Vinča” - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering - University of Belgrade, Center of excellence for green technologies, Institute for Multidisciplinary Research - University of Belgrade, and Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy - University of Belgrade.

The goal of the Conference is to provide a platform for academic exchange among participants from universities, institutes, companies around the region in the field of ceramics research as well as to explore new direction for future development. 7CSCS-2023 aims to bring together leading academic scientists, researchers and research scholars to exchange and share their experiences and research results about all aspects of ceramic materials. It also provides the premier inter-multi-trans-disciplinary forum for researchers, practitioners and educators to present and discuss the most recent innovations, trends, and concerns, practical challenges encountered and the solutions adopted in the field of ceramic materials. We have received 102 abstracts with researchers from 15 countries.

The Conference will feature three plenary lectures, 30 invited talks and 64 oral and poster presentations as well as exhibitions of some new ceramic materials and devices. 7CSCS-2023 includes Ceramic Powders, Characterization and Processing, High Temperature Phenomena, Sintering, Microstructure Design and Mechanical Properties, Advanced Materials For Energy-Related Applications, Traditional Ceramics and Engineering Materials, Computing In Materials Science, Materials for Environmental Technology, Catalytic Materials, Materials for Sensing Devices, Ceramic Composites, Membranes And Multimaterials and Electro And Magnetic Ceramics. Exhibitions from company sponsors will be held at the Conference as well.

We are grateful for the support from the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Inovation of the Republic of Serbia. We would also like to express our sincere thanks to the symposia organizers, session chairs, presenters, exhibitors and all the Conference attendees for their efforts and enthusiastic support in this exciting time in Belgrade. I look forward to meeting you and interacting with you at Conference.

7CSCS-2023 President

Branko Matović

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7th Conference of the Serbian Society for Ceramic Materials
June 14-16, 2023, Belgrade, Serbia

PROGRAM of 7CSCS–2023

Day 1. Wednesday - June 14, 2023

08.00 – 09.00 h, Registration

09.00 – 09.15 h, Opening ceremony and welcome addresses

09.15 – 09.30 h, Cocktail

Plenary lecture

Chair: Brank Matović, Jelena Maletaškić

09.30 – 10.00 h, Plenary lecture, PL-1

Neven Barišić, *OPTICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF CUPRATES IN A NEW LIGHT*

Session 1: Ceramic powders, characterization and processing

Chair: Aleksandar Radojković, Zoltán Lenčéš

10.00 – 10.20 h, Invited lecture, I-1

Zoltán Lenčéš, *TRANSLUCENT/TRANSPARENT SPINEL PHOSPHORS FOR SOLID STATE LIGHTING AND PHOTOCATALYTIC APPLICATIONS*

10.20 – 10.35 h, Oral presentation, O-1

Sanita Ahmetović, *SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF PURE AND SM-, ZR-DOPED TiO₂ NANOFIBERS AND ITS PHOTOCATALYTIC ACTIVITY*

10.35 – 10.50 h, Invited lecture, O-2

Jovana Acković, *CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC INVESTIGATION OF THE IRON PHOSPHATE TUNGSTEN BRONZE (FE-PWB)*

10.50 – 11.05 h, Coffee break

Session 2: High temperature phenomena, sintering, microstructure design and mechanical properties

Chair: Peter Tatrko, Ravi Kumar

11.05 – 11.25 h, Invited lecture, I-2

Ravi Kumar, *COOLING RATE DEPENDENT MECHANICAL AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF ENTROPY STABILIZED OXIDES*

11.25 – 11.45 h, Invited lecture, I-3

Ankit Srivastava, *IN-SITU ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE TOLERANCE MECHANISMS IN LAYERED CRYSTALS*

11.45 – 12.05 h, Invited lecture, I-4

Peter Tatarko, *NEW HIGH-ENTROPY CERAMICS FOR EXTREME ENVIRONMENT APPLICATIONS*

12.05 – 12.25 h, Invited lecture, I-5

Jelena Mitrović, *CORRELATION BETWEEN THE MICROSTRUCTURE AND ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF Sb-DOPED BaSnO₃ CERAMICS*

12.25 – 12.40 h, Oral presentation, O-3

Manuel Gruber, *EXPLORING THE USE OF ADVANCED CERAMICS FOR SPARK PLUG ELECTRODES OF LARGE GAS ENGINES*

12.40 – 12.55 h, Oral presentation, O-4

Inga Zhukova, *DESIGN, SYNTHESIS, AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF DIBORIDE STRUCTURES WITH DIFFERENT MOLAR RATIOS OF TRANSITION METALS (Ti-Zr-Hf-Nb-Ta)*

12.55 – 13.10 h, Oral presentation, O-5

Miloš Dujović, *DEFORMATION AND FRACTURE RESPONSE OF SINGLE CRYSTAL MAX PHASES*

13.10 – 14.20 h, Lunch break

13.10 – 14.20 h, Poster Session 1 (Posters P1 – P25)

Session 3: Advanced materials for energy-related applications

Chair: Jelena Bobić, Ivana Cvijović Alagić

14.20 – 14.40 h, Invited lecture, I-6

Jelena Bobić, *TWO-PHASE AND THREE-PHASE FLEXIBLE THICK FILMS: POTENTIAL USE AS ENERGY STORAGE AND ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEMS*

14.40 – 14.55 h, Oral presentation, O-6

Mirjana Vijatović Petrović, *ENHANCED PROPERTIES OF PVDF COMPOSITES BY ACTIVE PHASE SILANIZATION* Priyanka Reddy, *NOVEL ELECTRONIC MATERIALS ON THE VERGE OF METALLICITY AND IONICITY*

14.55 – 15.10 h, Oral presentation, O-7

Priyanka Reddy, *NOVEL ELECTRONIC MATERIALS ON THE VERGE OF METALLICITY AND IONICITY*

Session 4: Traditional ceramics and engineering materials

Chair: Tatjana Volkov-Husović, Zvezdana Baščarević

15.10 – 15.30 h, Invited lecture, I-7

Nataša Džunuzović, *ENHANCING THE REACTIVITY OF THE INDUSTRIAL FLY ASH IN THE PROCESS OF ALKALI ACTIVATION*

15.30 – 15.50 h, Invited lecture, I-8

Tatjana Volkov-Husović, *CAVITATION EROSION RESISTANCE OF REFRACTORY CERAMICS FOR FOUNDRY COATINGS APPLICATION*

15.50 – 16.10 h, Invited lecture, I-9

Snežana Vučetić, *ECO-LOGICAL: DESIGN OF CERAMIC MATERIALS BASED ON THE INDUSTRIAL WASTES*

16.10 – 16.25 h, Oral presentation, O-8

Damjan Vengust, *OVERCOMING SYNTHESIS AND DENSIFICATION CHALLENGES TO IMPROVE THE PROPERTIES OF PMN-33PT PIEZOELECTRIC CERAMICS*

16.25 – 16.40 h, Oral presentation, O-9

Zvezdana Baščarević, *DURABILITY OF HIGH VOLUME FLY ASH BINDERS*

16.40 – 16.55 h, Oral presentation, O-10

Jelena Rakić, *CHEMICAL ACTIVATION OF HIGH VOLUME FLY ASH BINDERS BY SELECTED SODIUM SALTS*

Day 2. Thursday - June 15, 2023

Plenary lecture

Chair: Jelena Zagorac, K.C. Hari Kumar

09.00 – 09.30 h, Plenary lecture, PL-2

Johann Christian Schön, *THIN FILMS AND MONOLAYERS - PREDICTION, MODELING, AND EXPERIMENTS*

Session 5: Computing in materials science

Chair: Dasari L.V. Prasad, Dejan Zagorac

09.30 – 09.50 h, Invited lecture, I-10

Dasari L.V.K. Prasad, *DATA-MINING FOR NOVEL CERAMIC MATERIALS*

09.50 – 10.10 h, Invited lecture, I-11

K.C. Hari Kumar, *THERMODYNAMIC MODELLING OF CaO-MgO SYSTEM*

10.10 – 10.30 h, Invited lecture, I-12

Yuri Rostovtsev, *QUANTUM SENSORS FOR GAS MIXTURE DETECTION*

10.30 – 10.50 h, Invited lecture, I-13

Dejan Zagorac, *SCANDIUM OXYCHLORIDE (SCOCL): STRUCTURE PREDICTION USING A MULTI-METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH*

10.50 – 11.05 h, Oral presentation, O-11

Jelena Zagorac, *COMPUTATIONAL DISCOVERY OF NEW FEASIBLE CRYSTAL STRUCTURES IN Ce_3O_3N*

11.05 – 11.20 h, Oral presentation, O-12

Iva Toković, *EXPERIMENTAL STUDY AND DFT CALCULATION OF $LaMnO_3$ BASED THIN FILMS*

11.20 – 11.35 h, Oral presentation, O-13

Milan Pejić, *STRUCTURAL PROPERTIES OF MULTICOMPONENT SOLID SOLUTIONS WITH PYROCHLORE STRUCTURE ON DFT LEVEL*

11.35 – 11.50 h, Coffee break

Session 6: Catalytic materials

Chair: Matejka Podlogar, Uroš Čakar

11.50 – 12.10 h, Invited lecture, I-14

Jovana Ćirković, *PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF MORDANT BLUE 9 BY SINGLE-PHASE $BiFeO_3$ NANOPARTICLES*

12.10 – 12.30 h, Invited lecture, I-15

Matejka Podlogar, *BIO AND PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF TEXTILE FIBER-BASED MICROPLASTICS*

12.30 – 12.45 h, Oral presentation, O-14

Uroš Lačnjevac, *TiO₂ NANOTUBE ARRAYS DECORATED WITH IR NANOPARTICLES FOR ENHANCED HYDROGEN EVOLUTION ELECTROCATALYSIS* Stefan T. Jelić, *SYNTHESIS OF BISMUTH VANADATE PHOTOCATALYST WITH ENHANCED ADSORPTION PROPERTIES*

12.45 – 13.00 h, Oral presentation, O-15

Stefan T. Jelić, *SYNTHESIS OF BISMUTH VANADATE PHOTOCATALYST WITH ENHANCED ADSORPTION PROPERTIES*

13.00 – 14.10 h, Lunch break

13.00 – 14.10 h, Poster Session 2 (Posters P26 – P47)

Session 7: Materials for environmental technology

Chair: Zorica Branković, Slavica Lazarević

14.10 – 14.30 h, Invited lecture, I-16

Uroš Čakar, *THE INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS ON THE CONTENT OF NATURAL ACTIVE PRINCIPLES FROM FRUIT WINES AND ITS BENEFICIAL HEALTH EFFECTS*

14.30 – 14.50 h, Invited lecture, I-17

Malcolm Watson, *ADSORBENT MATERIALS: RECENT ADVANCES IN WATER TREATMENT*

14.50 – 15.10 h, Invited lecture, I-18

Slavica Lazarević, *SEPIOLITE-BASED NANOMATERIALS: STRUCTURE, PROPERTIES, AND APPLICATIONS FOR THE REMOVAL OF POLLUTANTS FROM WATER SOLUTIONS*

Session 8: Materials for sensing devices

Chair: Nikola Tasić, Samo B. Hočevar

15.10 – 15.30 h, Invited lecture, I-19

Samo B. Hočevar, *DEVELOPMENT OF DISPOSABLE TRACE METAL SENSORS, BIOSENSORS, AND GAS SENSORS USING VARIOUS MODIFICATION MATERIALS AND SCREEN-PRINTED ELECTRODES*

15.30 – 15.50 h, Invited lecture, I-20

Nikola Tasić, *POINT-OF-INTEREST ELECTROCHEMICAL DETECTION OF SARS-COV-2 VIRUS*

15.50 – 16.10 h, Invited lecture, I-21

Jelena Isailović, *INCORPORATION AND STABILIZATION OF Ti₃C₂TX MXENE INTO THE SENSITIVE H₂O₂ GAS SENSING PLATFORM*

16.10 – 16.25 h, Oral presentation, O-16

Sara Joksović, *THE DEVELOPMENT OF COST-EFFECTIVE CARBON-BASED TRANSPARENT ELECTRODES IN THE MID-INFRARED REGION*

16.25 – 16.40 h, Oral presentation, O-17

Aleksandar Malešević, *HIGH-TEMPERATURE HUMIDITY SENSING ABILITY OF INDIUM-DOPED BARIUM CERATE*

20.00 h, Conference dinner

Day 3. Friday - June 16, 2023

Plenary lecture

Chair: Nikola Kanas, Konstantina Lambrinou

09.00 – 09.30 h, Plenary lecture, PL-3

Miladin Radović, *TOWARDS SAFER AND SCALABLE SYNTHESIS OF MXene*

Session 9: Ceramic composites, membranes and multimaterials

Chair: Miladin Radović, Žaklina Burghard

09.30 – 09.50 h, Invited lecture, I-22

Waltraud M. Kriven, *MULTIFUNCTIONAL, REFRACTORY, GEOPOLYMER COMPOSITES*

09.50 – 10.10 h, Invited lecture, I-23

Konstantina Lambrinou, *DEGRADATION OF CVD SIC DURING SYNERGISTIC PROTON IRRADIATION/CORROSION TESTS*

10.10 – 10.25 h, Invited lecture, I-24

Dorota Chudoba, *NANOMATERIALS IN APPLICATION IN BIOMEDICINE*

10.25 – 10.40 h, Oral presentation, O-18

Zaklina Burghard, *A STRAIGHTFORWARD METHOD FOR SCROLLING PLANAR MATERIALS INTO FREE-STANDING 3D STRUCTURES WITH A SIGNIFICANT REDUCTION IN AREA FOOTPRINT*

10.40 – 11.00 h, Coffee break

Session 10: Electro and magnetic ceramics

Chair: Slavko Bernik, Goran Branković

11.00 – 11.20 h, Invited lecture, I-25

Kamila Komędera, *MOSSBAUER SPECTROSCOPY OF BIFEO₃-BASED COMPOUND*

11.20 – 11.40 h, Invited lecture, I-26

Slavko Bernik, *INFLUENCE OF PARTICULAR DOPANTS ON THE CHARACTERISTICS OF A NOVEL ZnO-Cr₂O₃-BASED VARISTOR CERAMIC*

11.40 – 12.00 h, Invited lecture, I-27

Tomislav Ivek, *COLOSSAL MAGNETORESISTANCE AND METASTABILITY IN La_{1-x}Ca_xMnO₃ (0.5 ≤ X ≤ 0.75) THIN FILMS*

12.00 – 12.20 h, Invited lecture, I-28

Zoran Jovanovic, *PLD GROWTH OF FUNCTIONAL OXIDES ON RGO-BUFFERED SILICON SUBSTRATE*

12.20 – 12.40 h, Invited lecture, I-29

Nikola Kanas, *RECENT PROGRESS ON OXIDE THERMOELECTRIC MATERIALS AND DEVICES*

12.40 – 13.00 h, Invited lecture, I-30

Sanja Perać, *THERMOELECTRIC CU DOPED SODIUM COBALTITE – STRUCTURAL, MAGNETIC AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES*

13.00 – 13.15 h, Oral presentation, O-19

Aleksandar Radojković, *TUNING OF FERROELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF BiFeO₃ CERAMICS BY CATION SUBSTITUTIONS AT Bi-SITE AND Fe-SITE*

13.15 – 13.30 h, Closing ceremony

13.30 – 14.30 h, Lunch

Day 1. Wednesday - June 14, 2023

Poster session 1: Ceramic powders, characterization and processing

P-1. Bratislav Todorović, *ELECTRON SPIN RESONANCE OF VANADYL IONS IN THE KAOLINITE STRUCTURE: KGA-1 KAOLINITE (GEORGIA, USA)*

P-2. Milena Rosić, *SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND PHOTOCATALYTIC EXAMINATION OF $C_{0.9}Ho_{0.1}MoO_4$ NANOPOWDERS*

P-3. Tijana B. Vlašković, *SYNTHESIS AND CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF $Ca_{0.9}Er_{0.1}MnO_3$*

P-4. Božana Petrović, *Mg SUBSTITUTED HYDROXYAPATITE FOR APPLICATION IN BONE TISSUE ENGINEERING*

P-5. Aleksa Luković, *CHARACTERIZATION OF HIGH-ENTROPY $A_2B_2O_7$ PYROCHLORE OBTAINED VIA COMBUSTION SYNTHESIS AND POST-CALCINATION*

P-6. Marija Prekajski Đorđević, *ENTROPY-STABILIZED OXIDES OWNING FLUORITE STRUCTURE: PREPARATION AND SINTERING*

Poster session 2: High temperature phenomena, sintering, microstructure design and mechanical properties

P-7. Jelena Mitrović, *THE INFLUENCE OF SPARK PLASMA SINTERING TEMPERATURE ON THE PROPERTIES OF Sb-DOPED BARIUM STANNATE CERAMICS*

P-8. Vladimir Pavkov, *ANDESITE BASALT AS A NATURAL RAW MATERIAL FOR OBTAINING GLASS-CERAMICS*

Poster session 3: Advanced materials for energy-related applications

P-9. Jana Mužević, *METAL-ORGANIC PEROVSKITES $[C(NH_2)_3][MII(HCOO)_3]$ ($M = Cu, Mn$ AND Co)*

P-10. Aleksandar Maslarevic, *THERMAL SPRAYING OF Ti_2AlC COATINGS*

P-11. Željko Mravik, *STRUCTURAL MODIFICATION OF GRAPHENE OXIDE/12 TUNGSTOPHOSPHORIC ACID COMPOSITES VIA ION BEAM IRRADIATION FOR IMPROVED ELECTROCHEMICAL CHARGE STORAGE*

Poster session 4: Computing in materials science

P-12. Tamara Škundrić, *AB INITIO INVESTIGATION OF THE NOVEL CR_2SIN_4 COMPOUND UNDER EXTREME PRESSURE CONDITIONS*

P-13. Dejan Zagorac, *THEORETICAL STUDY OF AlN/BN MIXED CHEMICAL SYSTEMS AND THEIR MECHANICAL PROPERTIES*

P-14. Tamara Škundrić, *ENERGY LANDSCAPE EXPLORATION AND CRYSTAL STRUCTURE PREDICTION OF TWO NOVEL COMPOUNDS IN THE Cr-Si-N SYSTEM*

P-15. Jelena Zagorac, *ZnO/ZnS CORE/SHELL NANOSTRUCTURES: EXPERIMENTS COMBINED WITH AB INITIO CALCULATIONS*

P-16. Milan Pejić, *ENERGY LANDSCAPE AND CRYSTAL STRUCTURE INVESTIGATIONS OF LANTHANUM FLUORO SULFIDE LAFS*

P-17. Dragana Jordanov, *ELECTRONIC PROPERTIES OF PREDICTED Y₂O₂S USING AB INITIO CALCULATIONS*

P-18. Dušica Jovanović, *DFT STUDY OF GLUTAMINE (L) MOLECULE INTERACTION WITH THE 001 AND 101 ANATASE SLAB SURFACES IN A VACUUM*

P-19. Dušica Jovanović, *DFT STUDY OF NEW HYBRID ORGANIC-INORGANIC PEROVSKITES: GUANIDINIUM-BX₃ SUBSTITUTED BY B = (Sn²⁺, Ge²⁺, Ba²⁺, Zn²⁺) AND X = (I⁻, Br⁻)*

Poster session 5: Materials for environmental technology

P-20. Vladimir Dodevski, *EXAMINATION OF IQOS RESIDUE, ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT AND POTENTIAL APPLICATION*

P-21. Vladimir Dodevski, *EXAMINATION OF DIFFERENT RAW MATERIALS, AS PRECURSORS FOR OBTAINING CARBON MATERIALS*

P-22. Sanja Krstić, *SUPERCAPACITIVE PROPERTIES OF CARBON MATERIALS ACTIVATED BY ALKALI METAL HYDROXIDES OBTAINED FROM SUCROSE*

P-23. Nenad Nikolić, *ZnMn₂O₄ AS A CATHODE MATERIAL IN AN AQUEOUS SOLUTION OF ZnCl₂ AND Mn(NO₃)₂ FOR ZN-ION BATTERIES*

P-24. Miroslav Hnatko, *ELECTROCHEMICAL FABRICATION OF TiO₂ NANOTUBE ARRAYS IN FLUORIDE-FREE SYSTEM*

P-25. Željka Milovanović, *PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF SEPIOLITE/ZrO₂ COMPOSITES FOR PHOSPHATE REMOVAL FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS*

Day 2. Thursday - June 15, 2023

Poster session 6: Catalytic materials

P-26. Bojana Simović, *Ag/ZnO NANOCOMPOSITES FOR PHOTOCATALYTIC APPLICATION*

P-27. Tijana Stamenković, *CHARACTERIZATION AND PHOTOCATALYTIC ACTIVITY OF NEWLY SYNTHESIZED Er AND Yb DOPED SrGd₂O₄ NANOPHOSPHORUS*

P-28. Marija Egerić, *METAL ORGANIC FRAMEWORK/POLYAMIDE ELECTROSPUN NANOFIBERAS MEAN FOR CONGO RED DYE PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION*

P-29. Marko Jelić, *INFLUENCE OF SWIFT HEAVY ION IRRADIATION ON PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BISMUTH-VANADATE*

P-30. Bojan Miljević, *PHOTOCATALYTIC EFFICIENCY ASSESSED IN SOLID STATE PHASE APPLICATION*

P-31. Milinko Perić, *DEVELOPMENT OF Ti₃C₂TX FOR PHOTOCATALYTIC WATER PURIFICATION*

P-32. Dragana Milošević, *THE INFLUENCE OF THERMAL ANNEALING OF Pt-BASED THIN FILMS ON ELECTRO-OXIDATION OF FORMIC ACID*

Poster session 7: Materials for sensing devices

P-33. Mihael Brezak, *SYNTHESIS OF Eu AND Yb BASED DIRAC SEMIMETALS*

P-34. Tijana Stamenković, *ENHANCEMENT OF UP-CONVERSION LUMINESCENT CHARACTERISTICS OF Yb³⁺/Ho³⁺ CO-DOPED Bi³⁺ BASED SrGd₂O₄ NANOPARTICLES*

Poster session 8: Ceramic composites, membranes and multimaterials

P-35. Svetlana Butulija, *BACTERIAL CELLULOSE (BC)-CeO₂ NANOCOMPOSITE FILM FOR CHRONIC WOUND TREATMENT*

P-36. Jelena Maletaškić, *SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF REINFORCED ALUMINA COMPOSITES*

P-37. Danica Maksimović, *ALUMINUM-BASED COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH CERAMIC FIBERS*

P-38. Branko Matović, *SPS DENSIFICATION OF B₄C-SiC COMPOSITES*

Poster session 9: Electro and magnetic ceramics

P-39. Milena P. Dojčinović, *INVESTIGATING NTC THERMISTOR, FERROELECTRIC AND ELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF Fe_2TiO_5*

P-40. Milena Rosić, *INFLUENCE OF Gd-DOPING ON ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES IN $Ca_{1-x}Gd_xMnO_3$ ($x=0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2$) PEROVSKITES*

P-41. Milena Rosić, *EFFECT OF $CoMoO_4$ NANOPOWDERS SYNTHESIZED BY GLYCINE NITRATE PROCEDURE AND CALCINATED AT 450 °C ON BRIGGS-RAUSCHER OSCILLATORY DYNAMICS*

P-42. Milica Vujković, *WHAT HAPPENS WHEN $BiFeO_3$ UNDERGOES POTENTIODYNAMIC POLARIZATION?*

P-43. Maria Čebela, *INFLUENCE OF Ag DOPING ON THE MORPHOLOGICAL AND MAGNETIC PROPERTIES IN CuO NANOPOWDERS*

P-44. Karolina Siedliska, *HYPERFINE INTERACTIONS IN THE HEXAGONAL STRUCTURE OF $CuFeO_2$ DELAFOSSITE*

P-45. Maria Čebela, *SYNTHESIS, STRUCTURE AND MAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF Fe_2TiO_5*

PL-1

OPTICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF CUPRATES IN A NEW LIGHT

Neven Barišić^{1,2}

¹*Institute of Solid State Physics, TU Wien, Wiedner Hauptstraße 8,
1040 Wien Austria,*

²*Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb, Bijenička
cesta 32, HR-10000, Zagreb, Croatia*

Understanding physical properties of unconventional superconductors and other correlated materials presents a formidable challenge. Their evolution with doping, frequency, and temperature, has frequently led to non-Fermi-liquid (non-FL) interpretations. Despite this prevailing opinion, it was recently established unambiguously by transport measurements that the itinerant charges do behave as a FL [1–5]. This result gave rise to the proposition that the non-FL behaviour of cuprates was due to a localized (non-conducting) component, thus that cuprates consist of two electronic subsystems [6,7]. The whole FL vs. non-FL discussion reduces to disentangling the two subsystems, naturally to be approached by optical measurements, which can see both.

In the light of the transport results, we conduct a novel analysis of optical responses [8]. We first demonstrate that the low-energy (conductive) part of the optical response is fully accounted for by transport measurements, proving, in particular, that the optical scattering rate exhibits precisely the scaling behavior predicted by FL theory. Second, a simple subtraction of the Fermi-liquid contribution from the overall optical response reveals that there is nothing left to explain in the low-energy sector. Third, this subtraction yields a clear identification of a second charge sector at the mid-infrared (MIR) energy range, which is thus determined experimentally for the first time without any fitting ambiguity. Temperature, frequency and doping evolution of the MIR feature identifies a gapped rather than dissipative response. Notably, in contrast to cuprates, the dissipative response is found to be relevant for pnictides and ruthenates. These results are of general importance for understanding the physics of cuprates. Not only do they identify the conducting sector as a FL, but also imply that the localized sector provides the glue for superconducting pairing without necessarily requiring the abandonment of the BCS framework for superconductivity [7,8].

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7. N. Barišić, D.K. Sunko, *J. Supercond. Nov. Magn.*, **35** (2022) 1781.
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PL-2

THIN FILMS AND MONOLAYERS - PREDICTION, MODELING, AND EXPERIMENTS

J. Christian Schön

MPI for Solid State Research, D-70569 Stuttgart, Germany

New chemical materials and compounds serve as the foundation for the modern technology of our civilization, where these materials should be environmentally friendly, with stable and controllable properties for a multitude of applications, and at the same time energy efficient in their synthesis. Traditionally, such materials are generated in bulk and then machined down to whatever size is needed. But such materials are also often grown in a bottom-up approach on a substrate, and in the extreme we are dealing with and aiming for low-dimensional systems with bespoke properties, where details of their structure and the stability of such materials often becomes an issue of concern.

The ability to predict such (meta)stable nanomaterials via the investigation of their energy landscapes, followed by a computation of their properties and stability, is of great value in their design and synthesis. Further insights come from modeling and simulating the synthesis process, and the detailed experimental study of their structure and properties. For the past three decades, the structure prediction of 3D bulk crystalline compounds, atom clusters, and (bio)molecules has shown great progress [1–3], and the computational approaches used are expected to be also applicable to low-dimensional systems [4,5]. In this presentation, we will discuss some of the methodological features specific to the prediction of such systems [6,7], together with examples of structure prediction and modeling for crystalline and amorphous atom- and molecule-based monolayers and thin films [4,6,8–12]. This is complemented by direct comparisons with experiments [9,10,13,14], and the discussion of additional thin film experiments that focus on new structural insights in seemingly completely understood systems like gallium [15] and ZnO films [16].

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2. D.J. Wales, H. Scheraga, *Science*, **285** (1999) 1368.
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PL-3

TOWARDS SAFER AND SCALABLE SYNTHESIS OF MXene

Miladin Radović¹, Vrushali Kothastane¹, Jodie Lutkenhaus^{1,2},
Micah Green^{1,2}

¹*Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Texas A&M University,
College Station, TX, USA*

²*Artie McFerrin Department of Chemical Engineering Texas A&M University,
College Station, TX, USA*

MXenes are two-dimensional (2D) nanomaterials that have garnered immense attention since their discovery in 2011. These transition metal 2D carbides and nitrides are typically synthesized by selectively etching the “A” element from their precursor MAX phases using top-down chemical etching commonly in concentrated HF or mixture of fluoride salts and HCl. MXene properties such as high electrical conductivity, hydrophilicity, etc., make them suitable for a wide range of applications in areas including energy storage, electromagnetic interference shielding, catalysis, sensing, and many more. Therefore, the large-scale synthesis of MXenes is required to foster their industrial applications. However, their large-scale is currently hindered due to a lack of (i) understanding of the etching mechanism of precursor MAX phases to MXenes; (ii) safer (non-toxic) and scalable etching routes for MXene synthesis at room temperature; and (iii) synthesis routes that produce MXene with reduced extent of degradation in colloidal dispersion over time, therefore having longer shelf-life.

Our current studies addresses the above bottlenecks by improving the mechanistic understanding of the MXene synthesis process, fine-tuning experimental process parameters and developing new synthesis routes and MXene compositions to enable large-scale production of MXenes. In this presentation, we will discuss results of our systemic study of etching V₂AlC MAX phases to V₂CT_z MXenes as a model system to develop a core-shell mechanism of etching MAX phases to MXenes in hydrofluoric acid. According to this mechanism, etching is not just limited to the removal of the A layer from the parent MAX phase, but also involves subsequent over-etching and degradation of MX layers to carbon and vanadium oxide. We have also demonstrated that core-shell etching of MAX phases to MXenes also takes place during electrochemical etching process is diluted HCl.

In addition, our team developed a novel and non-toxic etching route consisting of simultaneous etching and intercalation is developed for scalable MXene synthesis at room temperature using quaternary ammonium fluorides, this decreasing the numbers of processing steps in MXenes synthesis and reducing amount of hazardous chemicals used for their synthesis. This new method is also demonstrated to improve the oxidation-induced degradation and chemical stability of $Ti_3C_2T_z$ MXene dispersions. Alternative methods for safer etching of MAX phases to corresponding MXenes developed in our group also include etching in molten fluoride salts (SnF_2).

Last but not least, methods for scalable etching of MAX phases to corresponding MXenes using lower concentration mixtures of HF and HCl will be discussed on the example of series of novel compositions of MAX phases developed in our group to obtain $(V_x, Ti_{1-x})_3C_2T_z$ solid solution MXenes with enhanced and tunable electric conductivities.

I-1

TRANSLUCENT/TRANSPARENT SPINEL PHOSPHORS FOR SOLID STATE LIGHTING AND PHOTOCATALYTIC APPLICATIONS

Zoltán Lenčes¹, Patrícia Petrisková¹, Olivier Monfort², Robert Klement³

¹*Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Slovak Academy of Sciences, 84536 Bratislava, Slovakia*

²*Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Comenius University, 84215 Bratislava, Slovakia*

³*Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia*

Translucent $MgAlON$ and transparent $MgAl_2O_4$ spinel ceramics doped with rare-earth metals have been prepared. A systematic study was performed to develop a processing methodology for elimination of microstructural defects in sintered samples and improving optical transparency. The green pellets were prepared from freeze granulated and dried powder mixtures by uniaxial and cold isostatic pressing using 400 MPa pressure. The oxide $MgAl_2O_4$ spinels were sintered in air at 1550 °C and subsequently HIP-ed at 1550 °C for 5 h in 200 MPa Ar gas. A similar process, but at 1800 °C was used for the preparation of $MgAlON$ ceramics. The optical real in-line transmittance (RIT) of polished $MgAl_2O_4$ specimens was 95% of the theoretical value.

A series of translucent $MgAlON$ phosphors doped with different cations were prepared and emitted a blue (Eu^{2+}), yellowish (Ce^{3+}) red (Yb^{3+}), and dark red (Er^{3+})

light. Some of the phosphors excited by green light emitted dark-red light (715–720 nm).

Titania nanotubes (TNTs) were prepared on spinel substrates by anodization of Ti layer, previously deposited on their surface by magnetron sputtering. The photocatalytic properties of TNTs on spinel substrates were studied by following the degradation of bisphenol A and rhodamine B under UVA irradiation. Promising results have been obtained for the photocatalytic applications of TNTs on transparent/translucent spinel substrate.

Acknowledgement: This work was supported by APVV-14-0385 and VEGA2/0167/22 projects.

I-2

COOLING RATE DEPENDENT MECHANICAL AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF ENTROPY STABILIZED OXIDES

Ravi Kumar

Laboratory for High Performance Ceramics, Department of Metallurgical & Materials Engineering, Center of Excellence on Ceramics for Futuristic Mobility, Indian Institute of Technology-Madras (IIT Madras), Chennai, India

*Co-founder & Director, Ceratattva Innotech Pvt Ltd, Chennai, India
Founder & Director, InsituMicron, Chennai, India*

The possibility of altering the phase equilibria of multicomponent oxide systems through precise control of configurational entropy has opened avenues with unlimited possibilities to fine-tune material properties at several length scales. We have been working to tailor the mechanical and thermal properties of (MgNiCoCuZn)O by an intelligent design of microstructure resulting from controlled cooling from the stabilization temperature. Based on the cooling rates, in these systems the amount of copper oxide (CuO) nucleation was found to vary between 5.4 and 12.3 wt.%, along with a corresponding decrease in Cu²⁺ content in the matrix. It was observed that with the decrease in Cu²⁺ ion concentration in the matrix, the Young's modulus and hardness increased by 33% and 26%, respectively, along with a corresponding decrease in the coefficient of thermal expansion by 15%. Similarly, an increased nucleation of CuO precipitates led to the improvement of fracture toughness of the material by 15%, while its thermal conductivity remained unaltered. We have tried to understand and rationalize the variation in the observed properties by using neutron diffraction, EELS spectroscopy, multivariate statistical analysis (MSA) on a STEM-EDX mapping and molecular dynamics simulation.

I-3

IN-SITU ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE TOLERANCE MECHANISMS IN LAYERED CRYSTALS

Ankit Srivastava¹, Hemant J. Rathod¹, Andreas K. Kronenberg²,
Thierry Ouisse³, Miladin Radovic¹

¹*Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Texas A&M University,
College Station, TX, 77843, USA*

²*Department of Geology and Geophysics, Texas A&M University,
College Station, TX 77843, USA*

³*Université Grenoble Alpes, CNRS, Grenoble INP, LMGP, F-38000 Grenoble,
France*

Ceramic materials provide outstanding chemical and structural stability at high temperatures and in hostile environments but are susceptible to catastrophic fracture that severely limits their applicability. However, there are layered ceramics, such as MAX phases, with strongly bonded intra-layers and weakly bonded inter-layers that exhibit unconventional damage tolerance. In this work, we have carried out in-situ SEM experiments using an in-house design and built fixture that allows us to load single crystal specimens of these layered ceramics with a punch along predetermined directions, with and without deformation constraints. The deformation constrain in these tests mimics the presence of neighboring grains in a polycrystalline aggregate. Our results show that although layered crystals of this class of ceramic materials are prone to fracture along weakly bonded layers, the onset of an abstruse mode of deformation, referred to as kink-banding, can induce large crystallographic rotations and plastic deformation that physically heal the cracks (Fig. 1). Furthermore, kink-bands are not unique to MAX phases and have been observed in a variety of other layered ceramics. Thus, in addition to MAX phases, we also analyzed single crystals of a true and brittle mica to determine the effects of intra-layer and inter-layer properties on the formation of kink-bands. The complete results of this work will be discussed in this presentation.

Figure 1. In-situ SEM observation of onset and growth of a kink-band leading to physical healing of cracks in a single crystal Cr_2AlC MAX phase sample

I-4

NEW HIGH-ENTROPY CERAMICS FOR EXTREME ENVIRONMENT APPLICATIONS

P. Tatarko¹, I. Zhukova¹, N. Hosseini¹, H. Ünsal¹, Z. Chlup², M. Tatarková¹, A. Kovalčíková³, J. Dusza³, I. Dlouhý²

¹*Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Slovak Academy of Sciences,
Dúbravská cesta 9, 845 36, Bratislava, Slovakia*

²*Institute of Physics of Materials, Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic,
Žižkova 22, 616 62, Brno, Czech Republic*
*Institute of Materials Research, Slovak Academy of Sciences,
Watsonová 47, 040 01 Košice, Slovakia*

In this work, the synthesis, densification and mechanical properties of the main representative of two groups of High Entropy Ceramics (HEC), i.e. (Hf-Zr-Ta-Nb-Ti)C carbide (HECC) and (Hf-Zr-Ta-Nb-Ti)B₂ diboride (HEB), were investigated. While the carbide was synthesized using a solid-state synthesis of a powder mixture of binary carbides, the diboride was synthesized using boro/carbothermal reduction of oxide mixtures. Both the carbide and the diboride showed single solid solutions after Spark Plasma Sintering at 1600 °C and 2050 °C, respectively. The hardness, Young's modulus and wear resistance of the materials were investigated.

Moreover, the effect of various amounts of SiC additives on the densification and mechanical properties of (Hf-Zr-Ta-Nb-Ti)B₂ diboride was studied. It was shown that the addition of SiC significantly improved densification of HEB materials. The room temperature mechanical properties, such as hardness, flexural strength and fracture toughness continuously increased with the increasing amount of SiC up to 20 vol.%. A significant drop in the mechanical properties observed for the composite with 25 vol.% was caused by the significant coarsening of the microstructure. On the other hand, the dynamic oxidation rate of the materials significantly, almost linearly decreased with the addition of SiC up to 25 vol.%. It was concluded that the composite sintered with 20 vol.% SiC showed the best combination of room and high temperature mechanical properties.

In addition, fine grained (Hf-Zr-Ta-Nb-Ti)C/(Hf-Zr-Ta-Nb-Ti)B₂ dual-phase 60vol.%HECC/40vol.%HEB was prepared by boro/carbothermal reduction of oxide mixtures, and the properties were compared to the individual single phase materials.

Acknowledgement: This work was supported by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under the contract no. APVV-21-0402, APVV-SK-CZ-RD-21-0089, and APVV-19-0497. The support of VEGA 2/0161/22 and JRP SAV TUBITAK project No. 546676 is also acknowledged.

I-5

CORRELATION BETWEEN THE MICROSTRUCTURE AND ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF Sb-DOPED BaSnO₃ CERAMICS

Jelena Mitrović¹, Milica Počuča-Nešić¹, Aleksandar Malešević¹, Zorica Branković¹, Katarina Vojisavljević¹, Slavica Savić², Vesna Ribić³, Sandra Drev³, Matejka Podlogar³, Slavko Bernik³, Željko Rapljenović⁴, Tomislav Ivek⁴, Goran Branković¹

¹*Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia*

³*Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia*

⁴*Institute of Physics, Zagreb, Croatia*

The non-magnetic, non-inductive electroconductive materials with linear current-voltage characteristic and low and almost constant electrical resistivity in the wide temperature range could be used in conditions unfavorable for metals and alloys. Particular emphasis is placed on the performance and endurance of these materials in conditions at constant high voltage, current, and energy, as well as operating in acidic and humid environmental conditions.

The aim of this work was to investigate the influence of antimony concentration and sintering parameters on the structure, microstructure, and electrical properties of antimony-doped barium stannate, BaSn_{1-x}Sb_xO₃ (BSSO, $x = 0,00; 0,04; 0,06; 0,08$ and $0,10$) to obtain conductive electroceramic samples with linear current-voltage ($I-U$) characteristics and low electrical resistivity. For this purpose three different sintering techniques were used: conventional, spark plasma and cold sintering.

According to the X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis, single-phase ceramic materials with cubic BaSnO₃ structure were obtained by conventional sintering at 1600 °C for 3 h and spark plasma sintering at 1100 °C for 5 min. Raising the spark plasma sintering temperature to 1200 °C induced the formation of Ba-rich secondary phase, Ba₂SnO₄. XRD analysis confirmed the presence of unreacted SnO₂ and BaCO₃ in cold sintered BaSn_{0,92}Sb_{0,08}O₃ sample (310 °C for 5 min, 20 wt.% 1 M acetic acid). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) indicates a significant decrease in grain size upon doping, regardless of the sintering technique. High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) revealed the presence of low angle grain boundaries (LAGBs) in conventionally and spark plasma sintered (1200 °C for 5 min) samples with $x = 0,08$. The results of electrical measurements confirmed the semiconducting properties of all BSSO, except the spark plasma sintered BaSn_{0,92}Sb_{0,08}O₃ (1200 °C for 5 min) sample. This sample showed linear current-voltage characteristic, the lowest and almost constant electrical resistivity in the temperature range of 25–150 °C resulting from the loss of potential barriers at grain boundaries due to the large fraction of LAGBs present in BaSn_{0,92}Sb_{0,08}O₃ ceramic sample.

I-6

TWO-PHASE AND THREE-PHASE FLEXIBLE THICK FILMS: POTENTIAL USE AS ENERGY STORAGE AND ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEMS

Jelena Bobić¹, Nikola Ilić², Zeljko Despotovic³, Adis Dzunuzović¹,
Robertas Grigalaitis⁴, Ivan Stijepović⁵, Mirjana Vijatović Petrović¹

¹*University of Belgrade, Institute for Multidisciplinary Research,
University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Department of Atomic Physics, Vinca Institute of Nuclear Sciences, National
Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Mihajlo Pupin Institute, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

⁴*Faculty of Physics, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania*

⁵*Department of Materials Engineering, Faculty of Technology, University of
Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia*

For the last decades, energy harvesters based on piezoelectricity from mechanical vibration (wind, human activities, vibrations of machines and traffic, ocean waves, and acoustic waves) are explored extensively for its functionality in energy technologies. Typical applications that could benefit from mechanical energy harvesting are that many sensors, alarms, LED lights, and other low-power and ultra-low-power devices can be driven energetically completely independently [1]. To fabricate a flexible piezoelectric energy harvester (FPEHs) that operates under various conditions, ceramic particles were blended with a polymer to form composite films.

Two-phase lead-free BaZr_{0.2}Ti_{0.8}/PVDF and lead-based PbZr_{0.52}Ti_{0.48}/PVDF piezocomposites, as well as three-phase PbZr_{0.52}Ti_{0.48}/Ni_{0.7}Zn_{0.3}Fe₂O₄/PVDF composites films with variable filler content (up to 50 vol.%) have been prepared by hot pressing method. Structure and morphology of piezo-active phase powders as well as distribution of filler in obtained flexible films were characterized by XRD and SEM analysis. Total amount of electroactive phase (% F_{EA}) of PVDF in all films were investigated by FTIR analysis. In all composites dielectric permittivities was increased in contrast to their polymer PVDF host matrix, but also displayed decreased breakdown strength and raised energy loss. In addition, the remnant polarization (Pr) and leakage current were also investigated to evaluate the breakdown strength in all types of flexible films. Also, ferromagnetic response was established in PZT/ferrite/PVDF films under magnetic field of 10 kOe.

Calculations of storage energies and output voltage obtained for the investigated materials revealed an increasing trend with increasing amount of active phase. The maximum storage energy of 0.42 J/cm³ at 390 kV/cm³ was obtained for PZT-PVDF (40-60) films while the maximum output voltage of about 10 V was obtained for PZT-PVDF (50-50) flexible film. In addition, comparisons between properties of

lead based and lead free flexible films as well as potential use of those films as energy storage and energy harvesting systems were considered.

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I-7

ENHANCING THE REACTIVITY OF THE INDUSTRIAL FLY ASH IN THE PROCESS OF ALKALI ACTIVATION

Nataša Džunuzović, Miroslav Komljenović, Violeta Nikolić,
Zvezdana Baščarević

*Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, University of Belgrade,
Belgrade, Serbia*

Over the past few decades a new group of binding materials, geopolymers, have emerged as an alternative to traditional binding materials such as Portland cement. Geopolymers are obtained by the process of alkali activation of various aluminosilicate materials, both natural and synthetic. Of particular importance is the possibility of alkali activation of the industrial waste material such as fly ash. Fly ash (FA) is generated in the process of coal combustion in thermal power plants. In Serbia a small part of fly ash is recycled while the rest is landfilled, causing a serious environmental pollution. Alkali activation represents a process by which fly ash can safely be converted into a useful binding material, suitable for the construction purposes. Geopolymers (or alkali-activated materials) based on fly ash are known for their good compressive strength and good durability in aggressive environments, when properly designed. However, the limiting factor for wider use of fly ash in the process of alkali activation and geopolymers synthesis is its low reactivity and consequent low compressive strength of binding elements. Our research has shown that the reactivity of fly ash in the process of alkali activation can be enhanced by the appropriate choice of the reaction conditions – by mechanical activation of fly ash and by blending with more reactive material such as blast furnace slag (BFS). Both options were explored in this paper and comparison was performed. Mechanical activation of fly ash was conducted in a planetary ball mill, while blends of fly ash and blast furnace slag were prepared with different ratios (FA/(FA+BFS) = 1; 0,75; 0,50; 0,25; 0). Alkali activation was carried out at 95°C by use of sodium silicate solution as an activator. In both cases significant increase of geopolymer compressive strength was observed in respect to the geopolymer based on the initial fly ash. Optimal geopolymer strength was correlated with the chemical composition of the binding gel. Empirical values of optimal gel composition could serve as a basis for tailoring properties of alkali-activated binders based on different precursors. Both alkali-activated systems represent promising routes for geopolymer technology development.

I-8

CAVITATION EROSION RESISTANCE OF REFRACTORY CERAMICS FOR FOUNDRY COATINGS APPLICATION

Tatjana Volkov-Husovic¹, Ana Alil², Sanja Martinović²,
Milica Vlahović²

¹*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy,
Belgrade, Serbia*

²*University of Belgrade, Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy-
National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia*

Cavitation erosion causes serious failures, as well as potential injury for workers and others; loss of revenue, due to equipment downtime and the extra costs of failure analysis, repair, and replacement. Erosion behavior of engineering materials caused by cavitation can be observed in various equipments, such are pump impellers, high-speed propellers, and turbine blades, or equipment in conditions that include fluid flow.

In this paper cavitation erosion of refractory ceramic materials commonly used as coatings for foundry application, will be investigated. Selected materials are ceramics based on a talk with the addition of zeolite from two domestic localities (Igros and Zlatokop), and cordierite ceramics.

Samples were formed, pressed, and sintered at 1200 °C. Prepared samples were subjected to the cavitation erosion test by using the ultrasonic vibration method with a stationary sample.

The cavitation erosion behavior of selected samples will be analyzed using mass loss results and image analysis applied to formed pits.

Keywords: cavitation erosion, ceramics, zeolite, talc, cordierite, image analysis

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I-9

ECO-LOGICAL: DESIGN OF CERAMIC MATERIALS BASED ON THE INDUSTRIAL WASTES

Snežana Vučetić¹, Bojan Miljević¹, Mirjana Blagojev²,
Aleksandar Bunčić², Ranko Dragić²

¹*University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Novi Sad, Serbia*

²*University of Novi Sad, Academy of Arts, Department of Fine Arts, Sculpture Chair, Djure Jakšića 7, Novi Sad, Serbia*

Waste generation has expanded quickly in the 21st century due to the expanding population, consumerism, and linear approach to industrialization. The use of industrial wastes in ceramic production has increased globally. One of these wastes is “red mud”, an insoluble byproduct created by the Bayer process and with a pH between 10 and 13. The estimated annual global production of this byproduct is 90 million tons. Disposal of red mud is also very expensive and companies must spend 5% or more of the aluminium's manufacturing value on the proper disposal.

Bearing in mind all mentioned above the aim of our work was to obtain ceramic materials using red mud, low grade clays and fly ash, with the development of optimal technological parameters (composition, shaping, drying and sintering). Characterisation of the raw materials was performed by: XRD, SEM/EDS, DTA/TG and the optimal proportion of red mud to clay was found to be up to 50 mas.%. The open porosities of the final products were evaluated by water absorption and mercury intrusion porosimetry, while XRD and SEM/EDS were used in order to determine the crystalline phases and microstructure. The observed products were comparable to the pavement ceramic materials. Moreover, designed technological protocols were also used for the production of the ceramic materials which are part of the art exhibition – ECO-logical sculptures.

Keywords: industrial wastes, red mud, low grade clays, production technology

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I-10

DATA-MINING FOR NOVEL CERAMIC MATERIALS

Dasari L.V.K. Prasad

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur 208016, India

One of the most difficult problems in materials science is predicting the relationship between structure and functionality, especially when the structures of ceramics have complex correlations – order-disorder and compositional variations. In this talk, I will present our recent progress on predicting novel ceramic materials using a hybrid materials genome initiative approach – a combined global minimum search by first principles evolutionary and knowledge based crystal structure prediction approaches – in searching for the likelihoods of function specific structures. The methods and results of our investigation on specific important materials will be discussed.

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I-11

THERMODYNAMIC MODELLING OF CAO-MGO SYSTEM

K.C. Hari Kumar

Indian Institute of Technology Madras, Department of Metallurgical and Materials Engineering, Chennai – 600 036, India

CaO and MgO are extensively used in steelmaking processes for reducing the acidic nature of the slag. They are also used as furnace linings owing to their excellent refractory properties. Recently, dolomite (mixture of CaO and MgO) is being used as a catalyst for biodiesel synthesis. Hence, it is imperative to understand the phase equilibria and thermochemistry of the CaO-MgO system.

There is an ambiguity in the thermochemical information pertaining to this system. Enthalpies of formation for CaO and MgO reported by Berman *et al.* [1] significantly differ from the values reported by Gourishankar *et al.* [2]. The melting point of CaO reported in the literature is in the range of 3178 to 3222 K. Similarly, the melting point of MgO recommended by SGTE significantly differs from the value reported by Ronchi *et al.* [3]. To resolve these uncertainties, a critical analysis of the experimental data was performed in this work.

Since, the thermochemical information pertaining to the CaO-MgO system is rather limited, ab initio calculations were performed. Enthalpies of formation for CaO, MgO were computed using density function theory (DFT). Quasi harmonic approximation (QHA) was used to compute the finite temperature thermodynamic

Figure 1. Calculated phase diagram of the CaO-MgO system

properties for the same. Enthalpy of mixing of CaO and MgO was obtained by randomizing the Ca and Mg atoms in the solid solution using special quasirandom structures (SQS). Finally, thermodynamic optimization was performed using the thermochemical and constitutional data from literature along with the ab initio data generated from the present work as input. The calculated phase boundaries shown in Fig. 1 are in good agreement with the experimental data.

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I-12

QUANTUM SENSORS FOR GAS MIXTURE DETECTION

Goran Branković¹, Zorica Branković¹, Katarina Vojisavljević¹,
Alexandar Malešević¹, Zorica Marinković Stanojević¹, Milica Počuča-
Nešić¹, Jelena Mitrović¹, Yuri Rostovtsev²

¹*Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, University of Belgrade,
Kneza Vieslava 1a, 11030 Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Department of Physics and the Center for Nonlinear Sciences, University of
North Texas, Denton, TX 76203 USA*

Numerous methods have been utilized for molecular detection, including optical, calorimetric, acoustic, and techniques based on changes in electrical properties, such as metal oxide semiconductor sensors [1,2]. Recent research endeavors have led to a significant rise in sensitivity, detecting parts per billion (ppb) [3], but the challenges of selectivity and cross-sensing remain crucial areas of investigation. Developing a gas sensor with high selectivity to efficiently analyze multi-gas mixtures would be of great significance, with potential applications in various fields such as technology, environmental control, biology, and medicine.

Quantum sensors are a promising new technology for the detection of gas mixtures. They offer a number of advantages over traditional methods, including high sensitivity, selectivity, and response time. In the presentation, we propose a new method based on the resonant interaction of dipole molecules with ac fields, in the presence of a dc electric and magnetic field that creates Zeeman and Stark splitting of molecular levels specific to certain molecules, ensuring selectivity [4].

In this talk, we present some preliminary experimental results obtained for the molecule NO on the use of quantum sensors for the detection of gas mixtures. Our results demonstrate the potential of quantum sensors for a variety of applications in gas sensing. We believe that quantum sensors have the potential to revolutionize the field of gas sensing.

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I-13

SCANDIUM OXYCHLORIDE (SCOCl): STRUCTURE PREDICTION USING A MULTI-METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

Dejan Zagorac^{1,2}, Jelena Zagorac^{1,2}, Tamara Škundrić^{1,2}, Milan Pejić^{1,2}, Dušica Jovanović^{1,2}, Matej Fonović³, J. Christian Schön⁴

¹*Institute of Nuclear Sciences “Vinča”, Materials Science Laboratory, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Center of excellence “CextremeLab”, Center for synthesis, processing, and characterization of materials for application in the extreme conditions, Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Faculty of Engineering, University of Rijeka-RiTeh, Rijeka, Croatia*

⁴*Max Planck Institute for Solid State Research, Nanoscale Science Department, Stuttgart, Germany*

Rare-earth ternary compounds and especially scandium oxychloride (ScOCl) have recently become of interest as an advanced material with various possible applications e.g. in solid oxide fuel cells, photocatalysis, and electronic devices, as are oxyhalides of various transition metals. In the case of ScOCl, a multi-methodological approach has been used for structure prediction and energy landscape exploration, while final structure optimization has been accomplished using DFT-LDA and hybrid PBE0 functionals. The experimentally observed α -ScOCl phase has been found as well as several additional structure candidates at high pressures and/or temperatures [1]. A successful synthesis of these novel ScOCl modifications would have the potential for extending the scientific, technological and industrial applications of ScOCl.

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I-14

PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF MORDANT BLUE 9 BY SINGLE-PHASE BiFeO₃ NANOPARTICLES

Jovana Ćirković¹, Aleksandar Radojković¹, Danijela Luković Golić¹,
Nikola Tasić², Mirta Čizmić³, Goran Branković¹, Zorica Branković¹

¹*University of Belgrade, Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, Kneza
Višeslava 1, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Department of Analytical Chemistry, National Institute of Chemistry,
Ljubljana, Slovenia*

³*Fidelta Ltd Croatia, Prilaz baruna Filipovića 29, 10000 Zagreb, Croatia*

We present a systematic study on the photocatalytic activity of single-phase BiFeO₃ powder, (BFO) nanopowder, under the simulated solar irradiation in the presence of highly polluting textile dye (Mordant Blue 9). BFO nanopowder was synthesized by the means of the ultrasound-assisted sol-gel route. UV-Vis spectroscopy measurements have revealed favorably high absorbance of the visible light with the calculated band-gap value of 2.21 eV. Study of the photocatalytic process related to the pH value of the dye aqueous solution (pH = 1; 6.7 and 12) and the irradiation time, and the complete degradation mechanism of the occurring photodegradation process is presented. Time dependent decolorization and decomposition processes were characterized by the decay of the pollutant's absorbance signal, while the related photodegradation products were detected by high-performance liquid chromatography equipped with mass spectrometer (HPLC/MS-MS). HPLC/MS-MS analysis of solutions at pH = 1 and pH = 6.7 showed only decolorization process, with no detectable degradation products, while the samples collected after degradation at pH = 12 revealed the presence of three different degradation products, whose concentration slightly decreased with time. Reusability test, showed that BFO nanoparticles can be used in a four successive photodegradation cycles, with no significant activity losses.

I-15

BIO AND PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF TEXTILE FIBER-BASED MICROPLASTICS

Matejka Podlogar¹, Tina Radošević¹, Anja Černoša², Lara Einfalt¹,
Martina Kocijan³, Damjan Vengust¹, Cene Gostinčar²,
Nina Gunde Cimerman²

¹*Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia*

²*University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia*

³*University of Zagreb, Zagreb, Croatia*

Plastic pollution has been identified as a global problem that endangers the entire ecosystem. Numerous studies have shown that water systems are full of plastic particles degraded into microplastics (MP) and nanoplastics (NP). This has prompted investigations to assess the impact of MPs on global ecologies and human health. MP released into the environment is degraded very slowly by biotic or abiotic processes. Biodegradation is a promising method that slowly converts plastic into harmless residues, while photodegradation breaks down plastics through the process of photocatalysis.

In this work we present two naturally occurring processes. The photocatalytic degradation was carried out in cylindrical reactor with quartz cover, where 5 mg of photocatalyst was added to 5 mL of ultra-pure water and different types of plastic microfibers (PET, PP, PA). Reactor systems were irradiated under stirring using a UV-vis simulated sun spectrum (Ultra Vitalux, 300 W, Osram). Biodegradation was performed by 2 selected species of fungi, *Pleurostoma richardsiae* and *Coniochaeta hoffmannii*. Sterilized plastic fibres were transferred to tubes with sterile M9 liquid medium. Cell suspension of each selected strain was added to the tube and incubated at 24°C for 6 months.

SEM analysis after the treatments showed that the surface of individual fiber became rough with clear signs of partial degradation, which could not be observed on pristine fibers. In addition, we observed that fungi were successfully growing on fibers, which indicates that fibers became the food source for this fungi type. And Raman analysis showed changes in chemical structures of plastic material. The kinetics of both degradation processes are relatively slow, however combination should increase the dynamics of microplastics degradation.

I-16

THE INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS ON THE CONTENT OF NATURAL ACTIVE PRINCIPLES FROM FRUIT WINES AND ITS BENEFICIAL HEALTH EFFECTS

Uroš Čakar¹, Mirjana Čolović², Maria Čebela³, Aleksandar Petrović⁴,
Danijela Krstić⁵, Ivan Stanković¹, Brižita Đorđević¹

¹*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Pharmacy, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*University of Belgrade, Vinča Institute of Nuclear sciences - National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Department of Physical Chemistry*

³*University of Belgrade, Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences - National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia*

⁴*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture, Serbia*

⁵*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Medicine, Institute of Medical Chemistry, Belgrade, Serbia*

Natural active principles are present in the fruit and during its processing pass into the final products. Among many natural active principles it is important to emphasize those which exhibit beneficial health effect on human organism. Beneficial health effect of those compounds is result of antioxidant properties. Wine is fruit derived product which is rich source of those compounds. The aim of this study was to investigate the influence of technological process on the phenolic profile, antioxidant properties and activity of antioxidant protection enzymes *in vitro*. Fruit wines were produced in controlled conditions during microvinifications. Phenolic profile of fruit wines were obtained by UPLC MS/MS, while antioxidant properties and enzymatic activity determined by spectrophotometric methods. The content of phenolic compounds in fruit wines was significant. It is important to highlight that different applied technology during the production, influenced on the content of above mentioned compounds. Flavonoids and phenolic acids were the most important. Also fruit wines showed ability to activate enzymes of antioxidant protection, which could be used in the protection against free radicals and prevention of oxidative stress.

I-17

ADSORBENT MATERIALS: RECENT ADVANCES IN WATER TREATMENT

Malcolm Watson, Jasmina Nikić, Jasmina Agbaba

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Novi Sad, Serbia

This work presents some recent advances in the development of adsorbent materials for water treatment. Water resources are under immense pressure: climate change is affecting regional water balances, threatening many countries with water scarcity; and the global population and levels of industrialisation are increasing, leading to more polluted water bodies and a greater demand for water than ever before. Adsorption technologies are often viewed as the most appropriate solution, as in comparison to other technologies, they are easy to operate, scalable and generate low volumes of waste.

The application of nanomaterials as adsorbents is of particular interest, as their small particle size and large surface areas often result in excellent adsorption capacities. Inorganic nanoparticles such as iron and manganese oxides can be simply produced and often show strong affinities for heavy metals [1], as can carbon-based nanoparticles such as carbon nanotubes [2] or modified graphene oxides. However, although the adsorption performance of such nanoparticles under controlled laboratory conditions is often exceptional, several hurdles remain before nanomaterials are broadly applied for water treatment in the real world, such as finding economically and environmentally sustainable means for their mass production and ways to improve their stability and hydro-permeability. Their very small nature also makes nanoparticles difficult to separate from water, resulting in loss of adsorbent material during continuous flow operations. For these reasons attention is turning to the development of nanocomposite materials, which look to combine the unique characteristics of nanomaterials with the handling simplicity of larger carrier materials, such as sands, ceramics, resins, bio- and synthetic polymers and activated carbons.

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I-18

SEPIOLITE-BASED NANOMATERIALS: STRUCTURE, PROPERTIES AND APPLICATIONS FOR THE REMOVAL OF POLLUTANTS FROM WATER SOLUTIONS

Slavica Lazarević, Ivona Janković-Častvan, Đorđe Janačković,
Rada Petrović

*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Karnegijeva 4,
11000 Belgrade, Serbia*

Sepiolite [Si₁₂O₃₀Mg₈(OH)₄(OH₂)₄·8H₂O] is an abundant and widespread natural fibrous clay mineral with a high specific surface area and nano-sized channels running parallel to the length of the fibers [1]. As a result of this specific structure and high density of surface functional groups, sepiolite shows excellent adsorption and reinforcing properties. The main adsorption/modification sites in the sepiolite structure are a) oxygen ions on tetrahedral sheets; b) Si–OH groups along the fiber axis, and c) a small number of cation-exchange sites [2]. Through surface modification and by the formation of composites, the properties of sepiolite can be tailored for specific applications.

This study highlighted the application of natural sepiolite from the deposit Andrići in Serbia as an adsorbent in environmental protection, approaches to modification, the investigation of the structure and properties of sepiolite-based materials, as well as its applications for the adsorption of pollutants from water. Our previous studies have shown that sepiolite from deposit Andrići has high adsorption capacity for Pb²⁺, Sr²⁺, Cd²⁺ [3], Cu²⁺, Co²⁺ and Ni²⁺ ions, cationic dye and the antibiotic ciprofloxacin from water solutions.

In order to improve the adsorption performance, the sepiolite was modified by: (i) grafting of silane reagents to surface silanols by covalent bonding using: 3-mercaptopropyltrimethoxysilane, [3-(2-aminoethylamino)propyl]trimethoxy-silane and N-[3-(trimethoxysilyl)propyl] ethylenediaminetriacetic acid trisodium salt and (ii) deposition of iron(oxy)hydroxide, and zirconium oxide nanoparticles onto the sepiolite surface.

The obtained sepiolite-based nanomaterials were fully characterized and investigated as potential adsorbents. Modification of natural sepiolite resulted in the formation of adsorbents with higher adsorption capacities (sepiolite/iron (oxy)hydroxide composite for adsorption of Cu²⁺, Co²⁺ and Ni²⁺; sepiolite modified with ethylenediaminetriacetic acid trisodium salt for sorption of Ni²⁺ ions) and adsorbents with new applications (mercapto and amino functionalized sepiolites for anionic dye adsorption; sepiolite/ZrO₂ for phosphate adsorption).

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I-19

**DEVELOPMENT OF DISPOSABLE TRACE METAL SENSORS,
BIOSENSORS, AND GAS SENSORS USING VARIOUS
MODIFICATION MATERIALS AND SCREEN-PRINTED
ELECTRODES**

Samo B. Hočevar¹, Jelena Isailović^{1,2}, Nikola Tasić¹, Tea Romih¹,
Alnilan Lobato^{1,2}, Ivan Konjević¹, Kristijan Vidović¹

¹*Department of Analytical Chemistry, National Institute of Chemistry,
Hajdrihova 19, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia*

²*Jožef Stefan International Postgraduate School, Jamova cesta 39,
1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia*

In the fields of environmental monitoring, biology, clinical diagnostics, occupational health and food safety, cultural heritage preservation, homeland security, etc., there is an increasing need for cost-effective, sensitive, and selective disposable sensors for various inorganic and organic analytes. In this context, electrochemistry offers unparalleled opportunities for the development of numerous sensing strategies in conjunction with advanced electrochemical techniques and myriad modification (nano)materials that can be used as thin catalytic deposits, (bio)recognition elements, immobilization and anti-interference membranes, electrolytes, and accumulation and/or derivatization media for analytes. In addition, electrochemistry provides an excellent platform for the development of simple and point-of-need sensing devices, along with numerous miniaturization options [1]. A proper selection, pretreatment, and modification of a supporting electrode are crucial steps for successfully fabricating an electrochemical (bio)sensor. From this perspective, screen-printed electrodes (SPEs) have proven to be attractive substrates suitable for the deposition of different building blocks of electrochemical sensors.

In the following, we will summarize our recent research on the development of SPE-based sensors for detecting several important analytes in liquid and gaseous samples [2–4]. In addition, in fabricating electrochemical sensors, a reproducible response of the supporting electrode is of immense importance [5]. Therefore, strategies to improve the electrochemical properties of SPEs will be discussed, along with a brief study of the effects of electrode surface pretreatment on protein binding kinetics and electrode surface stability. We will demonstrate the operation and performance of selected SPE-based sensors developed in our laboratory for the detection of trace metal ions, gaseous phenol and hydrogen peroxide, antibodies, antigens, and DNA/RNA.

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I-20

POINT-OF-INTEREST ELECTROCHEMICAL DETECTION OF SARS-COV-2 VIRUS

Nikola Tasić¹, Ivan Konjević¹, Alnilan Lobato^{1,2}, Jelena Isailović^{1,2},
Tea Romih¹, Samo B. Hočevar¹

¹*Department of Analytical Chemistry, National Institute of Chemistry,
Ljubljana, Slovenia*

²*International Postgraduate School Jožef Štefan, Ljubljana, Slovenia*

In this work, we present simple and sensitive one-shot impedimetric sensors for the human anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG antibodies and the SARS-CoV-2 spike S1 protein. We demonstrate various strategies for modifying the disposable screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs) with emphasis on the use of polyaniline (PANI) and gelatin as surface modifiers and optimized chemical protocols for binding the biological recognition elements within the sensor architectures. Analytical performance studies for antibody detection were performed using the anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG antibody solution in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and diluted human serum samples from infected patients and showed a very low detection limit of 0.93 fM. In addition, we present an operation mode that includes a dual working electrode system, with an integrated negative control unit [1]. On the other hand, the spike S1 protein immunosensor showed an excellent linear response in the clinically relevant range of 0.001-10 µg m/l, along with very low detection limits of 2.15 pM in PBS and 1.15 pM in artificial nasopharyngeal fluid (ANF). The sensors exhibited good stability, repeatability, and selectivity, making them ideal for point-of-need applications.

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I-21

INCORPORATION AND STABILIZATION OF $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXENE INTO THE SENSITIVE H_2O_2 GAS SENSING PLATFORM

Jelena Isailović^{1,2}, Samo B. Hočevar¹, Nikola Tasić¹

¹*Department of Analytical Chemistry, National Institute of Chemistry, Hajdrihova 19, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia*

²*Jožef Stefan International Postgraduate School, Jamova cesta 39, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia*

In recent years, MXenes have attracted massive attention due to their high conductivity, hydrophilicity, low diffusion barrier, high ion transport properties, biocompatibility, large surface area, and ease of functionalization. Thus, they can be a fascinating interface for developing next-generation sensing strategies [1–4]. This novel class of two-dimensional (2D)-layered materials have been successfully synthesized from the precursor MAX phases by etching and exfoliation methods, resulting in surface-functionalized MXenes with numerous terminal groups that account for their hydrophilic nature. As such, MXenes can selectively absorb biomolecules and gas molecules through morphology control and surface modification [5,6]. The drawback is that MXenes are highly prone to oxidative degradation, leading to impaired functionality and inefficacy. Moreover, when MXenes are incorporated on the supporting electrodes and subjected to measurements in a positive potential window, an additional obstacle arises from their innate and irreversible electrooxidation.

In this work, we present the synergistic effect of the advantageous physicochemical properties of exfoliated $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene and the stabilizing character of chitosan, along with the redox activity of ferrocyanide-modified screen-printed carbon electrode for highly sensitive detection of gaseous H_2O_2 .

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I-22

MULTIFUNCTIONAL, REFRACTORY, GEOPOLYMER COMPOSITES

Waltraud M. Kriven

University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, Urbana, IL 61801 USA

Geopolymers are an emerging class of ceramic-like materials which are aluminosilicate inorganic polymers and cured at ambient temperatures from calcined clay and an aqueous, alkaline, metasilicate solution precursor. The strained nature of the 5-coordination aluminum cation polyhedra is identified as the reason why metakaolin-based geopolymer ceramics are made from solution, rather than with high temperature diffusion as for typical ceramics. Geopolymers essentially behave as a refractory glue. The microstructure of alkali based geopolymers is nanoporous and nanoparticulate, having 40 vol.% porosity and ~ 1.5 g/cc density. Intrinsic mechanical properties as well as those of geopolymer composites have been measured for composites containing both ceramics, polymeric as well as biological reinforcements. Such geopolymer composites exhibit significant graceful failure and fracture toughness such as three times those of alumina. Glass frit-containing geopolymer composites, or appropriate intrinsic compositions of geopolymer undergo amorphous self-healing upon heating above the melting point of the glass. Depending on their compositions, geopolymers melt at temperatures up to 1900 °C.

Figure 1. Schematic description of relationship between cements, alkali activated cements, geopolymers and ceramics. Geopolymers are scalable and made under ambient temperatures

like a cement, but can have mechanical properties, like a ceramic

porous insulators and refractories having tailorable porosity; porous aerogels; high temperature resistant, airplane runways (1500 °C); scalable molten salt containment for thermal energy storage and electricity generation from solar heat rather than

Potential applications of geopolymer composites include: fire resistant coatings and fire breaker panels; nuclear radiation shielding against gamma rays and neutron rays with $\sim 98\%$ attenuation to date; low level radioactive waste encapsulation; porous water purification filters for removing heavy metals such as arsenic, cadmium, mercury etc.; corrosion and acid resistant coatings; refractory adhesives between stainless steel,

metals, glass, ceramics and wood to at least 1150 °C; thermal shock resistant coatings having tailorable thermal expansion coefficients; “smart” coatings containing embedded sensors;

from burning coal; fuel cells alternative to PEMS devices; coatings e.g. as roof tiles; fire breaker panels; other patent-pending applications; alternatives to cements for geothermal wells; a potential partial solution to global warming as a potential replacement for Portland cement when made from revalorized mine tailings.

I-23

DEGRADATION OF CVD SiC DURING SYNERGISTIC PROTON IRRADIATION/CORROSION TESTS

Konstantina Lambrinou

*School of Computing & Engineering, University of Huddersfield,
Huddersfield HD1 3DH, United Kingdom (UK)*

The Fukushima Daiichi event in 2011 has demonstrated the need for improved nuclear energy safety, which can be aided by the development of accident-tolerant fuels (ATFs). ATFs are expected to overcome the inherent shortcomings of the standard zircaloy/ UO_2 fuels, thus relieving the nuclear industry from the huge financial penalty associated with severe accidents leading to fuel cladding failure and the ensuing release of radioactive fission products to the power plant containment and the environment. SiC/SiC composites are a revolutionary ATF cladding material concept that combines inherent refractoriness, pseudo-ductility, and a lack of accelerated oxidation during a loss-of-coolant scenario. Its potential in meeting the strict requirements of the ATF cladding application has claimed large global investments, yielding different variants of this material concept. In this work, synergistic proton irradiation/aqueous corrosion tests were performed on monolithic SiC produced by chemical vapor deposition (CVD). CVD SiC coatings are deposited on the outer surface of SiC/SiC composite ATF claddings to minimize material losses in water, i.e., under nominal operation conditions for Gen-II/III light water reactors (LWRs). The proton irradiation/corrosion tests were performed on CVD β -SiC discs ($\text{\O} 3 \text{ mm}$, $50 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ thickness) in 3 different conditions: (a) $320 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, standard PWR (pressurised water reactor) water with 3 ppm H_2 , (b) $320 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, PWR water with 0.1 ppm H_2 , and (c) $288 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, BWR (boiling water reactor) water with 2 ppm O_2 and added H_2SO_4 to control the conductivity at $0.15 \text{ }\mu\text{S/cm}$. All CVD SiC discs were irradiated using a beam of 5.4 MeV protons for 48 h, yielding a total damage dose of 0.1 dpa. The CVD SiC discs underwent post-test analysis by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), atomic force microscopy (AFM), focused ion beam (FIB), high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM), scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM), electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS), and transmission electron backscatter diffraction (t-EBSD), shedding new light into the radiation-assisted degradation of CVD SiC caused by water radiolysis species (esp. H^+), and the dependence of this degradation on the exact water chemistry.

MÖSSBAUER SPECTROSCOPY OF BiFeO₃-BASED COMPOUND

K. Komędera^{1,2}

¹AGH University of Science and Technology, Faculty of Physics and Applied Computer Science, Kraków, Poland

²Mössbauer Spectroscopy Laboratory, Pedagogical University, Kraków, Poland

A crystal structure of BiFeO₃ has been established as rhombohedral with the angle between crystal axes $\alpha = 89.375^\circ$ [1]. A spontaneous electric polarization vector is parallel to the crystallographic $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction. A magnetic structure, due to the ordering of the trivalent high spin magnetic moments of iron is antiferromagnetic of the G-type. Magnetic moments form an incommensurate cycloid propagating in the $\langle 10\bar{1} \rangle$ direction. All magnetic moments are confined within the plane defined by the electric polarization vector $\langle 111 \rangle$ and cycloid propagation vector $\langle 10\bar{1} \rangle$. The lack of the inversion center is likely to be a combined effect of the oxygen octahedron distortion, iron atom displacement and presence of the stereo-active lone pair in the vicinity of the trivalent bismuth ions. Oxygen octahedron rotation and iron atom displacement lead to differentiation of the iron - oxygen distances in the nearest neighbor shell of oxygens surrounding iron. The oxygen octahedron rotation and iron atom displacements occur in nearly opposite directions in adjacent cells along the $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction [2]. Hence, one can expect two different iron sites, neglecting magnetic states. The Mössbauer spectra indeed exhibit two sub-spectra differing by the hyperfine field and electric field gradient (EFG) [3]. Alternatively some hyperfine field distribution could be fitted to the data. Hence, it is interesting to have a closer look on the hyperfine interactions in this complex system with antiferromagnetically coupled long spin cycloids. The aim of this contribution is to attempt to resolve the problem of the Mössbauer spectrum shape by the application of some physically feasible model [4]. BiFeO₃ – parent compound, Pr and Nd-doped sample were studied by ⁵⁷Fe Mössbauer spectroscopy.

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INFLUENCE OF PARTICULAR DOPANTS ON THE CHARACTERISTICS OF A NOVEL ZnO-Cr₂O₃-BASED VARISTOR CERAMIC

Slavko Bernik¹, Tian Tian², Matejka Podlogar¹, Guorong Li²

¹*Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia*

²*Shanghai Institute of Ceramics, Chinese Academy of Science, Shanghai, China*

ZnO-based varistor ceramics with exceptional current-voltage (I - U) nonlinearity and energy-absorption capability are the cornerstone of overvoltage-protection devices for applications over a broad range of voltages, from a few volts up to several-100-kilo volts. Here, ZnO-Bi₂O₃-based varistor ceramics are dominant, while the use of the other two types of varistor ceramics, i.e., ZnO-Pr₆O₁₁-based and ZnO-V₂O₅-based, is mostly limited to special high-energy varistors and multilayer varistors, respectively. Compared to them, the recently discovered ZnO-Cr₂O₃-based varistor ceramics with Cr₂O₃ as the varistor former (i.e., it induces I - U nonlinearity in the ZnO) and oxides of Ca, Co and Sb as a performance enhancer, have such advantages that their production could significantly affect the world market for overvoltage protection. While characterized by comparable or even better current-voltage (I - U) characteristics than the previously known ZnO-based varistor ceramic, the ZnO-Cr₂O₃-based ceramics do not contain the highly volatile Bi₂O₃, expensive rare-earth elements (Pr₆O₁₁) or toxic V₂O₅, their microstructure is practically single-phase, and the cost of the required varistor dopants much lower.

The exceptional electrical characteristics of ZnO-Cr₂O₃-based varistor ceramics, expressed as a coefficient of nonlinearity (α) ranging from 25 to 75, a low leakage current (I_L) below 0.2 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$, and a breakdown voltage (E_b) from 280 to 900 V/mm, result from the specific role of the dopants added to the ZnO. The influence of each particular dopant and its amount on the microstructure development, point defects and electronic states in ZnO grains and at grain boundaries, the height of the electrostatic Schottky barriers at the grain boundaries and consequently the electrical characteristics of the ZnO-Cr₂O₃-based varistor ceramics will be presented and discussed.

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I-27

COLOSSAL MAGNETORESISTANCE AND METASTABILITY IN $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Ca}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($0.5 \leq x \leq 0.75$) THIN FILMS

Emil Tafra¹, Matija Čulo², Mario Basletić¹, Nikolina Novosel²,
Branimir Mihaljević¹, Zvonko Jagličić^{3,4}, David Rivas Góngora²,
Tomislav Ivek², Silvia Tomić², Amir Hamzić², F. Fischgrabe⁵,
V. Moshnyaga⁵, Bojana Korin-Hamzić²

¹*Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb,
Zagreb, Croatia*

²*Institut za fiziku, Zagreb, Croatia*

³*Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering, University of Ljubljana,
Ljubljana, Slovenia*

⁴*Institute of Mathematics, Physics and Mechanics, Ljubljana, Slovenia*

⁵*I. Physikalisches Institut, Georg-August-Universität Göttingen,
Göttingen, Germany*

Manganites are a subject of extensive research due to the famous colossal magnetoresistance, which arises from the competition between the ferromagnetic metallic phase and the paramagnetic insulating as well as the antiferromagnetic charge-ordered insulating phase. Despite the well-understood metallic phase, the insulating behavior in manganites remains an active area of investigation.

In this study, we investigate the dc resistivity and magnetization of thin-film $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Ca}_x\text{MnO}_3$ samples in the antiferromagnetic charge-ordered insulating region of the phase diagram ($0.5 \leq x \leq 0.75$) at low temperatures and magnetic fields up to 16 T. We observe a pronounced influence of the applied magnetic field on the charge-order transition and the variable range hopping mechanism. Remarkably, we report colossal magnetoresistance of $8 \cdot 10^{11}\%$ for $x = 0.58$, which is the largest value ever reported to our knowledge. Furthermore, we observe history-dependent relaxations that occur over extremely long timescales.

We interpret these phenomena in terms of nanoscale phase separation in manganites, in which ferromagnetic metal clusters emerge in the background of the charge-ordered/antiferromagnetic state.

I-28

PLD GROWTH OF FUNCTIONAL OXIDES ON rGO-BUFFERED SILICON SUBSTRATE

Zoran Jovanovic^{1,2}, Urška Trstenjak², Hsin-Chia Ho², Matjaž Spreitzer²

¹Laboratory of Physics, Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences – National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, 11351 Belgrade, Serbia

²Advanced Materials Department, Jožef Stefan Institute, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

Epitaxial integration of oxides with semiconductor substrates is often limited by the lattice mismatch between the two material systems and their dissimilar chemical properties. However, in the case of 2D materials, the strict requirements of traditional epitaxy can be mediated by the weak van der Waals interactions. As a result, a 2D material, such as graphene, can allow remote epitaxial registry with a substrate. In the present work, we have investigated the potential of graphene oxide (GO) as an epitaxy-enabling agent for the pulsed-laser deposition (PLD) growth of strontium titanate (STO) on silicon with native oxide. After SrO-assisted deoxidation of the silicon surface, we have determined that GO can direct the growth of STO to a smooth, compact, and pinhole-free layer, with single (100) out-of-plane orientation, which was further overgrown with functional oxides, such as $\text{PbZr}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{O}_3$.

I-29

RECENT PROGRESS ON OXIDE THERMOELECTRIC MATERIALS AND DEVICES

Nikola Kanas

BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Thermoelectric generators are mostly consistent of materials with n- and p-type conductivity, which are electrically connected in series and thermally in parallel, and as such, they produce the electric power when exposed to a thermal gradient. The work principle is based on the Seebeck effect, and the efficiency of the constitutive materials are described by the figure-of-merit

$$zT = \frac{S^2 \sigma T}{\kappa}$$

where S is the Seebeck coefficient, σ is the electrical conductivity and κ is the thermal conductivity. Therefore, materials with high σ and S combined with a low κ will make a positive effect on TEG performance. For high-temperature applications the state-of-the-art metal-based thermoelectric devices are ruled out due to oxidation and melting. Because of their stability at elevated temperatures, oxides become a favorable choice. The efficiencies of oxides and oxide-based TEGs are still insufficient for commercial purpose and development of oxides with improved thermoelectric properties is demanded.

In this review, some of the state-of-the-art of oxide-based thermoelectric materials and devices will be highlighted, followed by a discussion on the challenges and advantages of oxide-based TEGs. Our recent results related to improved material properties and a promising novel design of all-oxide TEGs for operation at high temperatures in ambient atmosphere will be presented too [1–3].

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I-30

THERMOELECTRIC Cu DOPED SODIUM COBALTITE – STRUCTURAL, MAGNETIC AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Sanja Perać¹, Slavica M. Savić², Zorica Branković¹, Slavko Bernik³,
Aleksandar Radojković¹, Goran Branković¹

¹*Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, University of Belgrade,
Kneza Višeslava 1, 11030 Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Biosense Institute, Center for Sensing Technologies, Dr Zorana Đinđića 1,
21000 Novi Sad, Serbia*

³*Jožef Stefan Institute, Department for Nanostructured Materials,
Jamova cesta 39, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia*

With the increase of the consumption of electrical energy, the need for new energy sources is growing. Conversion of waste heat into electricity, based on the thermoelectric effects is one of the ways to produce the electrical energy. Layered cobalt oxides have been the subject of many investigations in past decade as candidates for application in energy conversion. The ceramic sodium cobaltite became a promising candidate for potential thermoelectric applications, because of

its large thermopower and low resistivity. In this work, polycrystalline samples of $\text{NaCo}_{2-x}\text{Cu}_x\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.01, 0.03, 0.05$) were synthesized from the powder precursors obtained by the citric acid complex method (CAC) and mechanochemically assisted solid state reaction method (MASSR). The obtained powders were uniaxially pressed into disc-shaped pellets and subsequently sintered at 880 °C in inert argon atmosphere. Thermoelectric parameters (the electrical resistivity (ρ), the thermal conductivity (κ) and the Seebeck coefficient (S)) were measured in two temperature regions. In the first one (between 2 and 300 K) κ and S were measured by a Quantum Design physical property measurement system (PPMS 9T) equipped with a 9 T magnet and ρ by a standard four-terminal technique using the direct current. In the second, all parameters were measured simultaneously, in the temperature gradient (ΔT) between hot and cold sides of the samples using Z-meter, based on the “large ΔT method”, and the figure of merit (ZT) was subsequently calculated. Accordingly, ρ , κ and S were determined for a temperature gradient that is established between the hot and cold sides of the samples at the time of each measurement; thus the obtained values represented the actual thermoelectric response of a material under conditions of application. In the low temperature range the highest figure of merit of 0.022 at 300 K was observed for the CAC sample doped with 1 mol% Cu, and it was almost twice higher than in the undoped sample confirming the significant influence of Cu-doping with even small concentrations. As for the results obtained in the temperature gradient, the highest ZT value of 0.061 at $\Delta T = 473$ K was observed for the sample with 5 mol% of Cu prepared by the CAC method. Sample magnetization was measured using a Quantum Design SQUID MPMS-XL-5 magnetometer in zero field cooled (ZFC) and field cooled (FC) regimes, between 2 K and 300 K and in the applied field of 100 Oe. The magnetic susceptibility (χ) of all samples followed the Curie-Weiss law in the temperature range between 50 K and 300 K, while a negative Weiss constant (θ) implied an antiferromagnetic interaction. Indentation experiments were carried out to investigate mechanical properties, therefore, the hardness (H) and the Young's modulus of elasticity (Y) were determined using Agilent Nanoindenter G200. It was found that the highest Y (65.2 GPa) and H (1.41 GPa) were obtained for the CAC sample containing 1 mol% of Cu. These results indicated a significant improvement of mechanical properties even in the case of the sample with the lowest dopant concentration. In general, better thermoelectric and mechanic properties showed the samples synthesized by the CAC method, confirming that fine, homogeneous precursor powders present a good base for obtaining material with improved thermoelectric performances.

O-1

**SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF PURE AND
Sm-, Zr-DOPED TiO₂ NANOFIBERS AND ITS
PHOTOCATALYTIC ACTIVITY**

Sanita Ahmetović¹, Zorka Ž. Vasiljević¹, Vladimir Rajić²,
Dragana Bartolić¹, Mirjana Novaković², Nenad B. Tadić³,
Nikola Cvjetičanin⁴, Maria Vesna Nikolić¹

¹*University of Belgrade, Institute for Multidisciplinary Research,
Belgrade, Serbia,*

²*Department of Atomic Physics, Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences - National
Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia,*

³*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Physics, Belgrade, Serbia,*

⁴*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Physical Chemistry, Belgrade, Serbia*

Pure, samarium (Sm³⁺) and zirconium (Zr⁴⁺) doped titanium dioxide (TiO₂) nanofibers were synthesized using the electrospinning method followed by calcination at 500 °C for 1 h. The structure, morphology and optical properties of the obtained nanofibers were investigated as a function of different Sm³⁺ and Zr⁴⁺ contents (0.5–5 mol%). XRD and FTIR analysis showed that addition of Sm or Zr suppressed the transformation of anatase to rutile. After calcination all fibers were smooth, fragile and randomly oriented. HRTEM analysis revealed that doping with Sm didn't affect the TiO₂ crystal lattice whilst Zr⁴⁺ ions replaced the substitutional sites in the anatase crystalline lattice. The effects of Sm³⁺ and Zr⁴⁺-dopant content and different doses of photocatalyst on the photodegradation of methylene blue (MB) were monitored under UV-light illumination. TiO₂:0.5%Sm³⁺ and TiO₂:1.0%Zr⁴⁺ nanofibers have shown the highest photocatalytic activity of 97% and 98% due to red shifting of the band gap towards visible light in the case of Sm and suppressed electron-hole recombination shown in recorded PL spectra in the case of Zr.

O-2

CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC INVESTIGATION OF THE IRON PHOSPHATE TUNGSTEN BRONZE (Fe-PWB)

Jovana Acković¹, Nenad Nikolić², Zoran Nedić³, Ružica Micić¹,
Jelena Senćanski⁴, Maja Pagnacco⁵, Pavle Tančić⁵

¹University of Priština in Kosovska Mitrovica, Faculty of Sciences and Mathematics, Department of Chemistry, Lole Ribara 29, 38220 Kosovska Mitrovica, Serbia

²University of Belgrade, Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, 11030 Belgrade, Republic of Serbia

³Faculty of Physical Chemistry, University of Belgrade, Studentski trg 12-16, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

⁴University of Belgrade, Institute for General and Physical Chemistry, Studentski trg 12-16, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

⁵University of Belgrade, Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, Department of Catalysis and Chemical Engineering, Njegoševa 12, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

In this paper, 12-tungstenphosphoric acid (PWA) was synthesized in combination with FeCl₃ at room temperature (25 °C). At such manner, Fe³⁺ ion exchange gave new 12-tungstenphosphoric salt of the transition metal iron (FePW₁₂O₄₀×nH₂O; Fe-PWA). Thermal analysis determined the temperature of about 596 °C of the phase transition, i.e., the temperature at which the structure of the Kegin anion is disturbed. Therefore, it was chosen temperature above the breakdown of the Kegin anion of 650 °C, and which is required to obtain phosphate tungsten bronzes (PWB) doped with iron (Fe-PWB). The sample was kept in the oven for 10 min. Such obtained new Fe-PWB doped bronze was further investigated by the X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) and Rietveld methods. The XRPD patterns of Fe-PWA and Fe-PWB were taken in the 3–90° 2θ angle range, and clearly reveal crystallographic and structural differences between these two phases. Determined unit-cell parameters of Fe-PWB obtained by the Rietveld method in the monoclinic crystallographic system are as following: $a_0 = 7.53(2) \text{ \AA}$; $b_0 = 7.51(1) \text{ \AA}$; $c_0 = 7.64(1) \text{ \AA}$; $\beta_0 = 89.7(2)^\circ$ and $V_0 = 431(2) \text{ \AA}^3$. These unit-cell parameters were compared with PWB, as well as other previously characterized doped bronzes (Li-PWB and Ca-PWB). It can be concluded that inserting of the Fe³⁺ ion into the PWB's structure was undoubtedly proven, and have the most influence to the axis a_0 (i.e. it significantly increased), angle β_0 (i.e., it significantly decreased), and volume V_0 (i.e., it significantly increased). On the other hand, influence to the axis c_0 is quite smaller (i.e. it slightly decreased), whereas influence to the axis b_0 is minor. Such behavior is also very different in comparison to the Li-PWB and Ca-PWB.

O-3

EXPLORING THE USE OF ADVANCED CERAMICS FOR SPARK PLUG ELECTRODES OF LARGE GAS ENGINES

Manuel Gruber¹, Walter Harrer¹, Anton Tilz², Michael Engelmayer²,
Wolfgang Fimml³, Andreas Wimmer⁴, Raul Bermejo¹

¹*Department Materials Science, Chair of Structural and Functional Ceramics, Montanuniversitaet Leoben, Peter-Tunner-Strasse 5, 8700 Leoben, Austria*

²*LEC GmbH Graz, Inffeldgasse 19, 8010 Graz, Austria*

³*Innio Jenbacher GmbH & Co OG, Achenseestrasse 1-3, 6200 Jenbach, Austria*

⁴*Institute of Thermodynamics and Sustainable Propulsion Systems, Graz, University of Technology, Inffeldgasse 19, 8010 Graz, Austria*

The drive for high efficiency and low emissions in large gas engines leads to extreme conditions in the combustion chamber in terms of pressure and temperature of the lean air-fuel mixture and thus to high wear of spark plug electrodes. Traditional rare-metal materials used in spark plugs are expensive and are reaching their limits in terms of wear resilience, leading to the search for alternative materials to increase maintenance intervals and - costs, as well as engine reliability.

Advanced ceramics have emerged as a promising alternative due to their high thermal stability, excellent oxidation and corrosion resistance, and lower raw material costs compared to rare metals. However, the required high electrical conductivity poses a significant limitation for the use of ceramic materials. Additionally, the inherent brittleness of ceramics presents a challenge to their applicability, as mechanical stresses during manufacturing, handling, or service may cause fracture. The joining process of ceramic electrodes to metal counterparts is also a critical step for the production of reliable spark plugs.

This work presents a material selection study focusing on potential joining methods, and the thermo-mechanical as well as oxidation behavior of the selected materials. Promising results for different ceramic electrode materials under laboratory conditions, together with corresponding wear mechanisms, are shown. Overall, this research offers insights into the potential of advanced ceramics as spark plug electrode materials, highlighting the need of further investigation to ensure their reliability under various operating conditions.

O-4

DESIGN, SYNTHESIS, AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF DIBORIDE STRUCTURES WITH DIFFERENT MOLAR RATIOS OF TRANSITION METALS (Ti-Zr-Hf-Nb-Ta)

Inga Zhukova¹, Vasanthakumar Kombamuthu², Monika Tatarková¹,
Dejan Zagorac³, Branko Matović³, Alexandra Kovalčíková⁴,
Tamás Csanádi⁴, Ivo Dlouhý⁵, Ján Dusza⁴, Peter Tatarko^{1,2}

¹*Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Slovak Academy of Sciences,
Bratislava, Slovakia*

²*CEMEA – Center of Excellence for Advanced Materials Applications, Slovak
Academy of Sciences, Bratislava, Slovakia*

³*Centre of Excellence "CEXTREME LAB", Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences -
National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Serbia*

⁴*Institute of Materials Research, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Košice, Slovakia*

⁵*Institute of Physics of Materials, Czech Academy of Sciences,
Brno, Czech Republic*

Highly pure High-Entropy Boride ceramics (HEB) were produced by two-step spark plasma sintering, consisting of boro/carbothermal reduction of oxides mixtures and pressure-assisted sintering. This work was focused on the HEB materials with non-equimolar compositions of transition metals (Ti-Zr-Hf-Nb-Ta), which demonstrated a reliable and cost-effective processing way for producing high-entropy diboride ceramics with a single-phase solid-solution. High-entropy borides may have a wide composition range, but $(\text{Ti}_{0.2}\text{Zr}_{0.2}\text{Hf}_{0.2}\text{Nb}_{0.2}\text{Ta}_{0.2})\text{B}_2$ is one of the most investigated compositions. Based on the $(\text{Ti}_{0.2}\text{Zr}_{0.2}\text{Hf}_{0.2}\text{Nb}_{0.2}\text{Ta}_{0.2})\text{B}_2$ structure, a group of high-entropy boride ceramics with non-equimolar transition metal atom ratios was theoretically predicted and experimentally investigated. The theoretical predictions were performed using the Density Function Theory implemented in the VASP program. The Special Quasirandom Structures were used to disorder materials. All structures with non-equimolar ratios contained a single phase according to XRD analysis. Nanoindentation was performed to measure both hardness and Young's modulus of the sintered materials. This study investigated the effect of different concentrations of metal elements on the processing and mechanical properties of high-entropy diboride ceramics.

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O-5

DEFORMATION AND FRACTURE RESPONSE OF SINGLE CRYSTAL MAX PHASES

Miloš Dujović¹, Miladin Radović¹, Ankit Srivastava¹, Thierry Ouisse²

¹*Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Texas A&M University, College Station, TX, USA*

²*Université Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble INP, PHELMMA, France*

A family of atomically layered ternary carbides and nitrides, commonly referred to as MAX phases, exhibits properties that combine some of the best attributes of both metals and ceramics. Notably, these materials display a hysteretic stress-strain response, pseudo-ductility, and high damage tolerance. This is largely due to their layered structure with strong intralayer and weak interlayer bonding, which facilitates several deformation and failure mechanisms, including crystallographic slip, cleavage, buckling of layers, and kinking. Recently, several attempts have been made to characterize the single-crystal level mechanical response of these materials using micromechanical testing of small scale specimens milled from individual grains. These studies have shown that the grain-level deformation and failure mechanisms of MAX phases depend on both the crystallographic orientation and deformation constraint of the grains. Building on these recent works, herein, we first carry out a series of unconventional small-scale tests on single crystal specimens of a Cr₂AlC MAX phase to analyze directly the effects of imposed deformation constraints (Fig. 1a). These tests include free-standing micropillars, and unconstrained and constrained microwalls. Following this, we analyze the fracture response of single crystal MAX phases using notched microcantilever beams (Fig. 1b). We will present the results of these micromechanical tests, focusing on correlating the effects of imposed deformation constraints and the crystallographic orientation of single crystal specimens on their deformation and fracture response.

Figure 1. (a) *Micropillar, unconstrained microwall, and constrained microwall specimens milled from a grain using focused ion.* (b) *Notched microcantilever beam specimen milled from a grain using focused ion.*

O-6

ENHANCED PROPERTIES OF PVDF COMPOSITES BY ACTIVE PHASE SILANIZATION

M. Vijatovic Petrovic¹, F. Craciun², F. Cordero², E. Mercadelli³, N. Ilic⁴,
Z. Despotovic⁵, J. Bobic¹, A. Dzunuzovic¹, C. Galassi³, P. Stagnaro⁶,
G. Canu⁷, M.T. Buscaglia⁷, E. Brunengo⁶

¹*University of Belgrade, Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*CNR-ISM, Istituto di Struttura della Materia, Area della Ricerca di Tor Vergata, Rome, Italy*

³*CNR- ISSMC - Istituto di Scienza, Tecnologia e Sostenibilità per lo Sviluppo dei Materiali Ceramici, Faenza, Italy*

⁴*Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

⁵*Institute Mihajlo Pupin, Belgrade, Serbia*

⁶*CNR-SCITEC, Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie Chimiche "Giulio Natta", Genoa, Italy*

⁷*CNR-ICMATE, Istituto di Chimica della Materia Condensata e di Tecnologie per l'Energia, Genoa, Italy*

0.94[(Bi_{0.5}Na_{0.5})TiO₃]-0.06BaTiO₃/polyvinylidene fluoride flexible composite films were prepared by the hot-pressing method. Surface modification of active phase particles was performed using two coupling agents, namely, (3-aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES) and dodecyl triethoxysilane (DDTES) to enable good adhesion of active phase particles with the polymer matrix. The highest amount of electroactive PVDF β- phase was formed in APTES-modified samples while in DDTES samples mainly γ- phase was formed. Dielectric permittivity values and dielectric losses decreased for silanized samples due to reduced tension at the interface between particles and polymer. Strong intermolecular interaction between the PVDF chains and the APTES-modified particles led to enhanced breakdown strength of these samples. After the polarization of films, energy harvesting potential was evaluated for all samples. The highest voltage output of ~ 15 V and power ~ 225 μW were obtained for a single APTES-modified harvester [1-2].

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2. A.M. Chandran, et al., *Sustainable Energy Fuels*, **6** (2022) 1641

O-7

NOVEL ELECTRONIC MATERIALS ON THE VERGE OF METALLICITY AND IONICITY

P. Reddy¹, D. Tolj², T. Ivšić³, A. Akrap⁴, L. Forró^{3,5}, N. Barišić^{1,5},
H. Ronnow², D.K. Sunko¹

¹*Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb, Croatia*

²*Laboratory for Quantum Magnetism, EPFL, Switzerland*

³*Laboratory of Physics of Complex Matter, EPFL, Switzerland*

⁴*Department of Physics, University of Fribourg, Switzerland*

⁵*Institute for Solid State Physics, TU Wien, Austria*

⁶*Institute Ruđer Bošković, Zagreb, Croatia*

Cuprates and pnictides are two intensively investigated families of functional materials that are on the verge of ionicity and metallicity. Both families exhibit a wealth of surprising behaviors, marked by various ordering tendencies. Among them, high-temperature superconductivity is perhaps the most exciting and mysterious one. A constructive way to improve understanding of this phenomenon is to synthesize and investigate a new system, which displays superior crystallochemical flexibility and tunability of the valence of the transition metal ions.

I will discuss murunskite-based compounds, which interpolate between cuprates and pnictides [1]. A successful growth and characterization of the first-ever high-quality murunskite ($\text{K}_2\text{FeCu}_3\text{S}_4$) single crystals will be presented. This compound shows semiconducting behaviour in resistivity and optical transmittance, while magnetic susceptibility reveals antiferromagnetic ordering around 100 K. Spectroscopy (XPS) and Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations concur that the sulfur $3p$ orbitals are partially open, making them accessible for charge manipulation, which is a prerequisite for superconductivity in analogy with cuprates and pnictides. Furthermore, DFT indicates that the valence band is more cuprate-like, while the conduction band is more pnictide-like. We also managed to synthesize single crystals of several chemically substituted compounds (e.g., Se,Te for S), whose transport and optical conductivity measurements will be discussed in the presentation.

Acknowledgement: This work is supported by Croatian Science Foundation project number IP-2018-01-7828.

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O-8

**OVERCOMING SYNTHESIS AND DENSIFICATION
CHALLENGES TO IMPROVE THE PROPERTIES OF PMN-33PT
PIEZOELECTRIC CERAMICS**

Damjan Vengust, Zouhair Hanani, David Fabijan, Jamal Belhadi,
Urška Trstenjak, Matjaž Spreitzer

*Advanced Materials Department, Jožef Stefan Institute, Jamova cesta 39,
SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia*

Lead magnesium niobate-titanate is an exceptional piezoelectric material with a high potential for various applications. Despite its remarkable properties, issues related to its synthesis and densification have been often overlooked, leading to impurities and suboptimal dielectric, ferroelectric, and piezoelectric responses. In this study, we address the commonly exploited synthesis route and highlight the critical constraints that lead to the formation of secondary phases, which ultimately affect the material's properties. Through a comprehensive characterization approach involving XRD, electron microscopy, and heating microscopy, we demonstrate that the addition of small amounts of MgO and PbO initiates the formation of a liquid phase that improves the densification process of PMN-33PT. Our results reveal that PMN-33PT can be successfully densified at 850 °C, resulting in a material with a dielectric and ferroelectric response comparable to that prepared at standard sintering temperatures of 1150 °C.

O-9

DURABILITY OF HIGH VOLUME FLY ASH BINDERS

Zvezdana Baščarević, Jelena Rakić

Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, Belgrade University, Belgrade, Serbia

Fly ash (FA), a by-product from thermal power plants, has been used for decades as Portland cement replacement material. Recently, additional efforts have been made by scientist and engineers worldwide with an aim to increase, as much as possible, content of FA in a binder, thus reduce negative environmental and economic impacts of the power and cement production. Furthermore, extensive work is being done on evaluating properties of the new binders, with a goal to ensure their wider use.

This work analyzes durability of the high volume FA binders (HVFA, ≥ 50 mass% of FA in a binder). In order to increase FA content and improve properties of

the HVFA binders, FA was mechanically activated and a chemical activator was used for the binder synthesis. Freeze-thaw, carbonation and sulfate attack resistance of the binders were analyzed. It was found that the freeze-thaw resistance of the HVFA binder was in accordance with the standard requirements. Carbonation depth after 56 days of testing of the HVFA binder was 7.3–8.1 mm, and an increase in the compressive strength of the mortar was observed. Studying of the sulfate attack on the HVFA binder showed that the resistance of the FA based binder was good, and even superior to the performance of the Portland composite cement CEM II 42.5N, tested under the same conditions and used for comparison. The obtained results indicated that the HVFA binders can be used for applications where moderate compressive strength and good durability of the binder is needed.

O-10

CHEMICAL ACTIVATION OF HIGH VOLUME FLY ASH BINDERS BY SELECTED SODIUM SALTS

Jelena Rakić, Zvezdana Baščarević

Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, Belgrade University, Belgrade, Serbia

Fly ash (FA), a by-product of coal combustion in thermal power plants, has been widely used in construction industry as partial replacement for Portland cement (PC). Due to environmental protection requirements, it became an imperative to increase the replacement rate of FA. Use of high volume fly ash (HVFA) binders, in which more than 50% of PC is replaced by FA, brings many ecological benefits (reduced pollution and energy consumption related to PC production, reduced waste generation, and preservation of natural resources). However, an increase of FA content in a binder can cause worsening of some of the properties of the binder, and reduction of early compressive strength and prolongation of setting time are of the greatest concern. These properties of HVFA binders can be improved by chemical activation of the binder. In this paper, three selected inorganic activators (Na_2SO_4 , Na_2CO_3 , and Na_2SiO_3) were used for chemical activation of HVFA binder (70 mas.% of FA and 30 mas.% PC). FA was mechanically activated prior to binder synthesis. Effects of the activators on the hydration of the HVFA binders were examined by isothermal calorimetry, X-ray diffraction, and thermogravimetric analyses. Influence of the chemical activation on the properties of the HVFA binders was analyzed by determination of setting time and compressive strength. The results showed that the chemical activators used in this work accelerated reactions of both PC and FA, which lead to shortened setting times and increased early compressive strength of the binders. The HVFA binder synthesized with sodium silicate as chemical activator had the best properties.

O-11

COMPUTATIONAL DISCOVERY OF NEW FEASIBLE CRYSTAL STRUCTURES IN Ce₃O₃N

Jelena Zagorac^{1,2}, Johann Christian Schön³, Dušica Jovanović^{1,4},
Dejan Zagorac^{1,2}, Tamara Škundrić^{1,2}, Milan Pejić^{1,2}, Marija Prekajski^{1,2},
Branko Matović^{1,2}

¹*Materials Science Laboratory, Institute of Nuclear Sciences “Vinča”,
University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Center for synthesis, processing, and characterization of materials for
application in the extreme conditions “CextremeLab”, Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Max Planck Institute for Solid State Research, Stuttgart, Germany*

⁴*Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science and Mathematics,
University of Niš, Niš, Serbia*

Oxynitrides of cerium are expected to have many useful properties but have not been synthesized so far. In this study, we have explored the energy landscape of the not-yet synthesized cerium oxynitride (Ce₃O₃N) based ceramics, and predicted several feasible modifications. The prediction of new modifications with the composition Ce₃O₃N has been performed by combining global optimization on the empirical potential level with a data mining procedure, where the energy landscape has been explored for different pressure values and various numbers of formula units in the simulation cell. In the second step, local structure optimizations of the candidates obtained during the global search and the data mining have been performed on the *ab initio* level, and the newly obtained modifications were analyzed. As a result, we have obtained six low-energy modifications that could be realized as (meta)stable modifications, thus emphasizing the importance of combining different methods in the search for feasible structure candidates, especially in the hypothetical systems.

For the fixed composition Ce₃O₃N, i.e. without considering a possible decomposition into the boundary phases Ce₂O₃ and CeN, the Ce₃O₃N-DM1 modification, with an Ag₃AsS₃ (proustite) structure, is predicted to be the thermodynamically stable modification at standard conditions. This stability of Ce₃O₃N-DM1 also extends to high pressures, while at effective negative pressures, the Ce₃O₃N-GS1 modification should be synthetically accessible. Four predicted orthorhombic modifications Ce₃O₃N-DM2,3,4,5, might be stable at high temperatures. Following on our earlier study of the feasible modifications of composition Ce₂ON₂ [1], this work provides a further glimpse of the potential structural richness of the Ce-O-N system and supports attempts to synthesize the predicted modifications.

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O-12

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY AND DFT CALCULATION OF LaMnO₃ BASED THIN FILMS

Iva Toković¹, Danica Piper¹, Jelena Vukmirović¹, Marija Milanović¹,
Stevan Armaković², Vladimir V. Srdić¹

¹*Department of Materials Engineering, Faculty of Technology, University of
Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia*

²*Department of Physics, Faculty of Natural Sciences, University of Novi Sad,
Novi Sad, Serbia*

Lanthanum manganite (LMO) is a perovskite-type manganate oxide that possesses unique properties including giant magnetoresistance (GMR) and sensitivity to external stimuli such as electric, magnetic fields and electromagnetic radiation. Another important fact is that LMO is very sensitive to the presence of dopant cations such as Sr²⁺, Ca²⁺, Ba²⁺. This material in the form of thin films has great potential for high-tech applications such as spintronics and as a material for memory units.

In this study, we aimed to prepare LMO thin films using the polymer-assisted deposition technique (PAD) [1], determine structure and electronic properties of LMO phase using density functional theory (DFT) calculations with Quantum Espresso and Quantum ATK software packages.

In the experimental part of this work, as source of cations were used nitrates which were dissolved in distilled water. Stability was ensured by addition of ethylenediamine-tetraacetic acid (EDTA) and polyethyleneimine (PEI). The prepared solutions were deposited by spin-coating technique on single crystal strontium titanate (001) substrates and thermally treated at various temperatures up to 900 °C. The characterization of thin films was done with several methods phase. Phase composition was investigated by XRD method. Additionally, structure and thickness of films were observed by AFM, SEM and TEM.

The ground state structure of LMO was obtained after the geometric optimizations at DFT level of theory. Further, a ground state structure was used to calculate band structure, total and partial density of states (TDOS and PDOS, respectively) and electronic density difference (EDD). To obtain more accurate results, the DFT+U approach was used, which included Hubbard potentials as a correction. The obtained results were compared to experimentally obtained data and literature values for evaluation purposes.

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O-13

STRUCTURAL PROPERTIES OF MULTICOMPONENT SOLID SOLUTIONS WITH PYROCHLORE STRUCTURE ON DFT LEVEL

Milan Pejić^{1,2}, Dejan Zagorac^{1,2}, Jelena Zagorac^{1,2}, Tamara Škundrić^{1,2}, Branko Matović^{1,2}

¹*Materials Science Laboratory, Institute of Nuclear Sciences “Vinča”, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Center for Synthesis, Processing and Characterization of Materials for Application in the Extreme Conditions “CextremeLab”, Belgrade, Serbia*

Among all high-entropy oxides, pyrochlores are potentially the most prominent compounds for future practical applications due to their diverse compositions and properties (thermal conductivity, ionic conductivity, geometrically frustrated magnetism, neutron absorption, nuclear waste storage capacity, and excellent high-temperature stability). The high application potential of these materials can also be attributed to their easily-controllable properties achievable through the change of constituent ions.

The structure of multicomponent oxide with pyrochlore structure ($A_2B_2O_7$), containing up to 7 different A-site cations and 3 B-site cations in equiatomic amounts was investigated using a multi-methodological theoretical approach. Investigated structures include 1 A-site cation and 3 B-site cations – $La_2(Sn_{1/3}Hf_{1/3}Zr_{1/3})_2O_7$, 3 A-site cations and 3 B-site cations – $(La_{1/3}Sm_{1/3}Y_{1/3})_2(Sn_{1/3}Hf_{1/3}Zr_{1/3})_2O_7$, 6 A-site cations and 3 B-site cations – $(La_{1/6}Sm_{1/6}Nd_{1/6}Pr_{1/7}Y_{1/6}Yb_{1/6})_2(Sn_{1/3}Hf_{1/3}Zr_{1/3})_2O_7$, and 7 A-site cations and 3 B-site cations – $(La_{1/7}Sm_{1/7}Nd_{1/7}Pr_{1/7}Y_{1/7}Gd_{1/7}Yb_{1/7})_2(Sn_{1/3}Hf_{1/3}Zr_{1/3})_2O_7$.

Structural candidates were generated using the Primitive Cell Approach for Atom Exchange (PCE) method [1] and the supercell approach [2] within the Crystal17 program package. Full structural optimization on the ab initio level was performed using the Quantum Espresso code. Density functional theory (DFT) calculations were utilized, using the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) with the Perdew, Burke and Ernzerhof (PBE) functional in both quantum mechanical codes.

In order to conduct an efficient, accurate, and thorough investigation of systems with such large number of different atomic species, previously described well-established theoretical methods were augmented with machine learning techniques that use artificial neural networks (ANN) trained on the data from the DFT calculations. Such an approach enables us to simulate much larger systems (i.e. larger unit cells) and many more different structural configurations (compared to using only the DFT) while maintaining the precision of the DFT calculations.

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O-14

TiO₂ NANOTUBE ARRAYS DECORATED WITH Ir NANOPARTICLES FOR ENHANCED HYDROGEN EVOLUTION ELECTROCATALYSIS

Uroš Lačnjevac¹, Rastko Vasilic², Ana Dobrota³, Slađana Đurđić⁴, Ondřej Tomanec⁵, Radek Zbořil⁵, Shiva Mohajernia⁶, Nhat Truong Nguyen⁷, Natalia Skorodumova⁸, Dragan Manojlović⁴, Nevenka Elezović¹, Igor Pašti³, Patrik Schmuki^{5,6,9}

¹*University of Belgrade, Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Physics, Belgrade, Serbia*

³*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Physical Chemistry, Belgrade, Serbia*

⁴*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Chemistry, Belgrade, Serbia*

⁵*Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials, Olomouc, Czech Republic*

⁶*University of Erlangen-Nuremberg, Department of Materials Science, WW4-LKO, Erlangen, Germany*

⁷*University of Toronto, Department of Chemistry, Toronto, Canada* ⁸*KTH–Royal Institute of Technology, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, School of Industrial Engineering and Management, Stockholm, Sweden*

⁹*King Abdulaziz University, Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia*

Designing cost-effective hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) electrocatalysts containing highly active, but expensive platinum group metals (PGMs) is key to the commercialization of polymer electrolyte membrane water electrolysis systems for green hydrogen production. Our recent investigations have shown that efficient and durable HER composite cathodes can be prepared by spontaneous deposition of PGM nanoparticles on self-aligned titania nanotube (TNT) arrays formed by anodization [1]. In this synthesis route, anatase TNTs are first cathodically protonated (H-TNT), and then used as the reducing agent for PGM ions at room temperature. Herein, we employ the galvanic displacement strategy to decorate H-TNT arrays

with ultrafine Ir nanoparticles [2]. We demonstrate that transforming the top surface morphology of supporting TNT arrays from ordered open-top tubes to bundled nanowires (“nanograss”) is beneficial for exposing more Ir active centers during the HER operation. Consequently, applying very low concentrations of Ir(III) ions in the galvanic displacement step is sufficient to produce exceptionally active nanograss-modified Ir@TNT composites. An optimum Ir@TNT, possessing a low Ir loading of $5.7 \mu\text{g}_{\text{Ir}} \text{cm}^{-2}$, requires overpotential of only -63 mV to reach a current density of -100 mA cm^{-2} and shows a stable long-term performance in a 1 M HClO_4 solution. Computational simulations suggest that the hydrogen-rich TiO_2 support not only strongly interacts with anchored Ir particles and weakens their H binding strength to a moderate level, but also actively provides hydrogen for rejuvenation of the Ir active sites at the Ir|H- TiO_2 interface, thereby significantly enhancing HER catalysis.

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O-15

SYNTHESIS OF BISMUTH VANADATE PHOTOCATALYST WITH ENHANCED ADSORPTION PROPERTIES

Stefan T. Jelić¹, Jovana Ćirković¹, Jelena Jovanović¹, Aleksandar Radojković¹, Tatjana Novaković², Goran Branković¹, Zorica Branković¹

¹*Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

Efficiency of a semiconductor catalyst is directly correlated to its surface to which a reactant species is adsorbed. There are several ways to optimize the active surface, such as synthesis, processing or any aftertreatment of a photocatalytic material. Our research was focused on modifying the existing sonochemically assisted synthesis of bismuth vanadate.

Two optimization methods were used in order to increase specific surface of the photocatalyst and number of its active sites. The first method was to change concentration of reactants used in the synthesis to reduce agglomeration of bismuth vanadate. Sonochemically assisted synthesis was performed with three different concentrations of reactants to observe agglomeration tendency of the catalyst. The other method included the use of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) as a surfactant in synthesis at highest concentration in order to hinder the particle growth.

Bismuth vanadate was shown to degrade mordant blue 9 dye (MB9) most effectively in alkaline medium (pH = 13) under visible light, discoloring the solution in under 2 hours, while the highest adsorption of MB9 is observed in acidic solution (pH = 1).

O-16

THE DEVELOPMENT OF COST-EFFECTIVE CARBON-BASED TRANSPARENT ELECTRODES IN THE MID-INFRARED REGION

Sara Joksović¹, Jovana Stanojev¹, Branimir Bajac¹, Vladimir V. Srdić²

¹*BioSense Institute, Novi Sad, Serbia*

²*Department of Materials Engineering, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia*

The discovery of indium tin oxide (ITO) in the 19th century had a great impact on the development of transparent conductive electrodes. Transparent conductive electrodes are required to comply with the requirements of high transparency in a certain range and good conductive properties in order to be used as part of optoelectronic devices, such as touch screen panels, OLED, LCD, IR sensors and so on. The transparency above 90 % in the visible range and low sheet resistance made ITO the most widely used material as a transparent electrode. However, the high production cost, brittle nature and relatively low transparency in the IR spectrum of ITO material are serious limitations that needed to be overcome [1,2]. On the other hand, since the discovery in 1991, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been recognized as potential alternatives for ITO films due to their exceptional optical and electrical properties, including in the IR region. To take full advantage of the extraordinary properties of these unique nanostructured materials, they must be uniformly integrated and crosslinked into light-weight matrices, such as those provided by various synthetic polymers [3].

We have developed a thin film material composed of CNT-polymer that exhibits remarkable transparency in both visible and IR ranges. Produced films have achieved a transparency of about 80 % and 70 % in the UV-VIS and mid-IR range (2.5–3.5 μm wavelength), which is significantly higher than the 20 % transparency typically observed in commercial ITO films, in the mid-IR range. The samples showed a decreasing trend of transparency with increasing number of bilayers. The sheet resistance of fabricated thin films was about 15 $\text{k}\Omega/\text{sq}$ with a tendency to decrease with the number of bilayers.

Furthermore, produced CNT-based film offers the added benefit of electrical conductivity suitable for serving as a transparent electrode, and it is manufactured through a cost-effective process. The Layer by Layer (LbL) deposition method is a

simple technique used for the sequential deposition of carboxyl functionalized single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs-COOH) and polyethyleneimine (PEI) in monolayers. PEI served as the positively charged layer, while carboxyl functionalized nanotubes were used as the negatively charged layer to establish an electrostatic bond [4,5]. The resulting samples were composed of 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 bilayers (PEI+SWCNT), and after each bilayer, the samples were dried at 120 °C for 10 min. Finally, produced thin films were thermally treated at 300 °C for 1 h to investigate how temperature influences on their electrical and optical properties. Different samples were investigated in order to find the optimal transparency/conductivity ratio for further application of the films.

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O-17

HIGH-TEMPERATURE HUMIDITY SENSING ABILITY OF INDIUM-DOPED BARIUM CERATE

Aleksandar Malešević¹, Aleksandar Radojković¹, Milan Žunić¹, Slavica M. Savić², Sanja Perać¹, Zorica Branković¹, Goran Branković¹

¹*University of Belgrade, Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, Center of Excellence for Green Technologies, Kneza Višeslava 1, 11030, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Biosense Institute, Center for Sensing Technologies, University of Novi Sad, Dr Zorana Đinđića 1, 21102, Novi Sad, Serbia*

Acceptor-doped perovskites (ABO_3 general formula) with large lattice constants (such as $BaCeO_3$, $SrCeO_3$, and $BaZrO_3$) have been known as fast proton conductors. The ability to conduct protons at high temperatures makes them suitable for humidity sensors in a high-temperature environment. The presence of traces of humidity can play a key role in the functioning of certain industrial processes at higher temperatures. Electrical characteristics of $BaCe_{0.75}In_{0.25}O_{3-\delta}$ (BCI25) sintered sample were analyzed in a dry and a wet argon atmosphere in the 250–700 °C temperature range. The water vapor sensing properties of BCI25 porous film and its response and recovery times were investigated under different conditions of temperature and water vapor concentration. A 30 μm thick film obtained from the powder calcined at 1050 °C exhibited sensitivity comparable to that of the sintered sample with significantly shorter response and recovery times. While the sensitivity of the film gradually decreased with a decrease in partial pressure of water vapor ($p(H_2O)$), a noticeable sensitivity was still observed at $p(H_2O)$ of 200 Pa. Decrease in

conductivity depended logarithmically on the partial pressure of water with the slope of 0.52 that is close to the theoretical value. After several cycles, the reusability test proved an almost unchanged ratio between the impedance value in the dry and the wet Ar atmosphere ($p(\text{H}_2\text{O}) = 2.34 \text{ kPa}$), which implied that BCI25, having good stability and sensitivity, is a promising high-temperature humidity sensor.

O-18

A STRAIGHTFORWARD METHOD FOR SCROLLING PLANAR MATERIALS INTO FREE-STANDING 3D STRUCTURES WITH A SIGNIFICANT REDUCTION IN AREA FOOTPRINT

Achim Diem, Joachim Bill, Zaklina Burghard

*Institute for Materials Science, University of Stuttgart,
70569 Stuttgart, Germany*

One important task of micro-/nanotechnology is to arrange materials into three-dimensional structures and thereby change their mechanical, electrical or optical properties, while at the same time reducing their footprint. A versatile approach to achieve that is rolling origami technology, which yields cylindrical micro-/nanostructures of considerable interest for numerous applications. However, despite recent progress along these lines, a fast, reliable and sustainable rolling method that provides access to high-quality rolling structures of controlled morphology is still needed. We demonstrate a straightforward and sustainable fabrication that uses external mechanical stress to scroll micrometre thick, flexible planar films with centimetre lateral dimensions in one step into tubular or spiral geometry within a few seconds. It furthermore allows controlling the scrolls' diameter, number of windings and nanostructured surface morphology, and it is applicable to a wide range of functional materials as it is performed at ambient condition. A scale-like surface morphology of the scrolls could be exploited in applications such as actuators, in order to speed up, e.g. opening and closing movements. Scales could furthermore improve electrode performance in energy storage systems by enhancing the surface area and reducing the ion diffusion path. As further important advantages, the method has a yield approaching 100%, allows for an easy control of the scrolling direction, and also enables the fabrication of entire arrays wherein each 3D object is located at a predefined position. Finally, it involves only one step, works with a minimal number of components, and does not require additional treatments like etching. This renders it not only cost effective but also eco-friendly and sustainable, thus opening the door for its large-scale application. The obtained 3D structures are highly promising for applications in energy storage, microrobotics, as well as biomedical and optical devices.

I-24

NANOMATERIALS IN APPLICATION IN BIOMEDICINE

Dorota Chudoba¹, Nazarova A.Zh²

¹*International Intergovernmental Organization Joint Institute for Nuclear Research, Frank Laboratory of Neutron Physics, Dubna, Russia*

²*Eurasian National University named after L.N.Gumilyov, Nur-Sultan, Kazakhstan*

One of the promising areas of nanotechnology development is the medical field of application of nanostructures. Nanomedicine is a rapidly developing area in the last decade, including methods for the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of a wide range of diseases using various types of nanostructures. The control of the shape, size, and chemical composition of nanostructures allows to set their physical properties at the synthesis stage and opens up new possibilities for bioprocessing.

A large share of works is those devoted to the use of carbon nanomaterials to biomedicine as nanocontainers. The features of carbon nanomaterials such as large surface volume, porosity and functional surface meant that many types of drugs and antibodies could be chemically conjugated to their surface. Thus, carbon nanomaterial systems can deliver drugs and improve the stability of the drugs and prevent their uncontrolled uptake and removal. Recent studies of carbon nanotubes, carbon fibers and others, as a carrier for anticancer drugs carried out by using experimental and simulation methods have shown the impact of appropriate surface modification to the efficiency of the drug adsorption process. Due to the fact that the effectiveness of drug release from nanocarriers is a major determinant in its biological use the evaluation of drug release kinetics was also perform. It was found that the efficiency of adsorption/desorption process depends on many factors and can be different for various carbon nanomaterials.

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O-19

TUNING OF FERROELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF BiFeO₃ CERAMICS BY CATION SUBSTITUTIONS AT BI-SITE AND Fe-SITE

Aleksandar Radojković¹, Danijela Luković Golić¹, Nataša Jović-Orsini², Jovana Ćirković¹, Nenad Nikolić¹, Zorica Branković¹, Goran Branković¹

¹*Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, University of Belgrade, Kneza Višeslava 1a, 11030 Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences, Belgrade, Serbia*

In this study, we tried various cation substitutions at Bi-site (La³⁺, Eu³⁺) and Fe-site (Nb⁵⁺, Zr⁴⁺) to explore their possible synergism and improvement of the ferroelectric properties of bismuth ferrite. The cations with higher valence ought to suppress the formation of structural defects during syntheses, such as oxygen and bismuth vacancies. These defects are responsible for high leakage currents and low breakdown voltages characteristic of pure BiFeO₃. On the other hand, rare earth cations at the Bi-site usually enable densification of the ceramics at a broader range of temperatures, preventing bismuth loss and formation of defects and secondary phases during sintering. However, dopant concentrations above 10–15 mol% may give rise to a transition from polar, rhombohedral (*R3c*) to non-polar, orthorhombic (*Pnma*) symmetry.

Thus, we synthesized pure and selected compositions doped BiFeO₃ by a hydro-evaporation method and determined the optimal calcination temperature by thermal analyses of the precursor powders. Then we characterized ceramics samples using X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and polarization techniques. Although only 1 mol% Nb⁵⁺ decreased the leakage current, it surprisingly deteriorated the ferroelectric properties of BiFeO₃. Similar effect exhibited the samples containing Zr⁴⁺ that showed no improvement compared with undoped bismuth ferrite. On the contrary, La³⁺ and Eu³⁺ (incorporated at the Bi-site) improved the ferroelectric properties as their concentrations increased, whereby the samples doped with 15 mol% La exhibited higher remnant electric polarizations at observed electric fields. The highest remnant electric polarization of 31.9 μC/cm² at 150 kV/cm, was measured for Bi_{0.85}La_{0.15}Fe_{0.998}Zr_{0.002}O₃, indicating the synergetic effect of La³⁺ and Zr⁴⁺, which is limited to low Zr⁴⁺ concentrations.

P-1

ELECTRON SPIN RESONANCE OF VANADYL IONS IN THE KAOLINITE STRUCTURE: KGa-1 KAOLINITE (GEORGIA, USA)

Bratislav Todorović¹, Pavle Premović²

¹*Faculty of Technology, University of Niš, Leskovac, Serbia*

²*Laboratory for Geochemistry, Cosmochemistry and Astrochemistry,
University of Niš, Serbia*

Kaolinite mineral is mainly used in ceramics, coated paper, as a food additive, in toothpaste, and in cosmetics. Vanadium (V) as a trace metal is not desirable in these industrial products for several reasons. To remove it from kaolinite for industrial use, it is important to establish where in its structure V is incorporated.

V in kaolinite is present in the +3, +4 and +5 oxidation states. One of the dominant V species in kaolinite is vanadyl (VO^{2+}) ions. They have a strong tendency to interact with the surface of Al and other metal hydroxide oxides of this mineral and is thus capable of becoming specifically adsorbed.

As a model kaolinite system, we studied highly ordered (KGa-1) sedimentary kaolinite from the late Cretaceous/early Tertiary deposits in Georgia (USA) [1]. The ESR measurements were performed on finely-ground powder of the KGa-1 sample that was transferred to an ESR quartz tube. Spectrum was recorded on the Bruker ER-200 series ESR spectrometers with the Bruker X-band bridges using standard 100 kHz field modulation. The measurements were made at 9.3 GHz utilizing a rectangular TE cavity.

Figure 1. First derivative, room temperature, X-band spectrum of VO^{2+} ions in the KGa-1 kaolinite.

A representative X-band ESR spectrum from KGa-1 is shown in Fig. 1. This spectrum of KGa-1 is characteristic of VO^{2+} species [1,2]. The spectrum shows an anisotropic spectrum pattern typical of an axially symmetric hyperfine coupling. (A

preliminary Q-band measurement indicates that this spectrum is a superimposition of the spectra of VO²⁺ ions located in two different positions in the KGa-1 structure). A sharp intense peak near $g = 2.002$ is assigned to defects that are always present in the clays [3].

P-2

SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND PHOTOCATALYTIC EXAMINATION OF Co_{0.9}Ho_{0.1}MoO₄ NANOPOWDERS

Milena Rosić¹, Maja Milošević², Maria Čebela¹, Vladimir Dodevski¹,
Vesna Lojpur³, Radomir Ljupković⁴, Aleksandra Zarubica⁴

¹Laboratory for Material Science, Institute of Nuclear Sciences „Vinča“, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, P.O. Box 522, 11001 Belgrade, Serbia

²Department of Mineralogy, Crystallography, Petrology and Geochemistry, Faculty of Mining and Geology, University of Belgrade, Đušina 7, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

³Department of Atomic Physics, Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, P.O. Box 522, 11001 Belgrade, Serbia

⁴Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science and Mathematics, University of Niš, Višegradska 33, 18000 Niš, Serbia

Co_{0.9}Ho_{0.1}MoO₄ nanopowders were obtained by applying glycine nitrate procedure (GNP). The synthesized samples were investigated by DTA, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra, Spectroscopy, Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM), and nitrogen adsorption method. The photocatalytic activity of acquired Co_{0.9}Ho_{0.1}MoO₄ nanopowders was estimated by the photocatalytic degradation of crystal violet in aqueous solution. A simple and effective method for controlling the composition and morphology of Co_{0.9}Ho_{0.1}MoO₄ is presented in this paper, as well as a potentially new approach in the methodology of inorganic synthesis. During photocatalytic testing nanostructured material Co_{0.9}Ho_{0.1}MoO₄ indicated the possibility of a promising solution in photocatalytic processes towards green chemistry and sustainable development.

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P-3

SYNTHESIS AND CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF $\text{Ca}_{0.9}\text{Er}_{0.1}\text{MnO}_3$

Tijana B. Vlašković¹, Bojana Laban¹, Maria Čebela²,
Vladimir Dodevski², Milena Rosić²

¹*Faculty of Sciences and Mathematics, University of Priština in Kosovska Mitrovica, Lole Ribara 29, 38220 Kosovska Mitrovica, Serbia*

²*Laboratory for Material Science, Institute of Nuclear Sciences "Vinča", National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, P.O. Box 522, 11001 Belgrade, Serbia*

$\text{Ca}_{0.9}\text{Er}_{0.1}\text{MnO}_3$ nanopowders with perovskite type crystal structure were synthesized by sucrose-nitrate procedure (SNP). SNP is a combustion method in which sucrose $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_{11}$ was used as fuel, while calcium nitrate tetrahydrate $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \times 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, manganese(II) nitrate hydrate $\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \times \text{H}_2\text{O}$, erbium(III) nitrate pentahydrate $\text{Er}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \times 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were used as oxidants. Obtained powder $\text{Ca}_{0.9}\text{Er}_{0.1}\text{MnO}_3$ were calcinated at a temperature between 800–1000 °C. Powder properties have been studied, such as crystallite and particle size, lattice parameters, structural changes, and specific surface area. X-ray diffraction (XRD), Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM), and Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) method were used to characterize the synthesized samples at room temperature. Also, high temperature treatment (up to 1000 °C) was used to follow the stability of solid solutions and the growth of crystallites.

P-4

Mg SUBSTITUTED HYDROXYAPATITE FOR APPLICATION IN BONE TISSUE ENGINEERING

Božana Petrović¹, Maja Krstić¹, Tihana Mudrinić², Maria Čebela¹,
Maja Dutour Sikirić³

¹*Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences- National Institute of the Republic of Serbia,
Belgrade University, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy - National Institute of the
Republic of Serbia, Belgrade University, Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Rudjer Bošković Institute, Zagreb, Croatia*

Magnesium (Mg) is an essential element in the human body primarily stored in bones. Mg ions have many potential benefits for bone tissue showing excellent osteogenic inductivity [1]. The aim of this study was to synthesize Mg substituted hydroxyapatite (Mg-HAP) for application in bone tissue engineering and to assess its behaviour in conditions mimicking physiological ones. Mg-HAP was synthesized using reflux method and its structural and morphological characterization was performed by XRD, FTIR and SEM. The changes in local structure and composition after irradiation and immersion in physiological solution and simulated fluid were assessed by electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy. The results of EPR analysis pointed out that irradiation did not change the composition and structure of Mg-HAP. After immersion in model media (simulated body fluid and saline solution), the small amount of by-product of synthesis disappeared after 24 h and Mg-HAP remained the only phase. Also, the radical signals in EPR spectra faded away after 28 days in model media, showing that the structure and composition of Mg-HAP both went through a kind of stabilization in simulated physiological conditions. These results make the investigated Mg-HAP promising material for application in bone tissue engineering.

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P-5

CHARACTERIZATION OF HIGH-ENTROPY $A_2B_2O_7$ PYROCHLORE OBTAINED VIA COMBUSTION SYNTHESIS AND POST-CALCINATION

Aleksa Luković¹, Branko Matović^{1,4}, Jelena Maletaškić¹,
Vesna Maksimović¹, Silvana Dimitrijević², Bratislav Todorović³,
Jelena Zagorac¹, Yu-Ping Zeng⁴, Ivana Cvijović-Alagić¹

¹Center of Excellence “CEXTREME LAB”, Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences -
National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade,
Mike Petrovića Alasa 12-14, 11001 Belgrade, Serbia

²Mining and Metallurgy Institute Bor, Zeleni Bulevar 35, 19210 Bor, Serbia

³Faculty of Technology Leskovac, University of Niš, Bulevar Oslobođenja 124,
16000 Leskovac, Serbia

⁴State Key Laboratory of High Performance Ceramics and Superfine
Microstructure, Shanghai Institute of Ceramics, Chinese Academy of Sciences,
1295 Ding-xi Road, Shanghai 200050, China

The goal of this research was to obtain a chemically complex multicomponent oxide with the $A_2B_2O_7$ pyrochlore structure with nominal composition $(La_{1/7}Sm_{1/7}Nd_{1/7}Pr_{1/7}Y_{1/7}Gd_{1/7}Yb_{1/7})_2(Sn_{1/3}Hf_{1/3}Zr_{1/3})_2O_7$ that contains 10 different cations in equiatomic amounts which was obtained by reacting metal nitrates (site A) and metal chlorides (site B) with glycine during the combustion reaction. The powder synthesized initially was found to be amorphous based on XRD analysis. To convert the powder into a crystalline pyrochlore structure, the powder underwent post-calcination at various temperatures ranging from 600–1500 °C. It was discovered that the desired monophasic pyrochlore structure ($A_2B_2O_7$) was obtained after calcination at 900 °C. To create a high-density ceramic pellet, the powder calcined at 900 °C was subjected to pressureless sintering at 1650 °C for four hours in the presence of air. The resulting pellet had a density of 97% of the theoretical density and was free from any additives. This process likely caused the powder particles to fuse together, creating a solid, dense pellet.

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P-6

ENTROPY-STABILIZED OXIDES OWNING FLUORITE STRUCTURE: PREPARATION AND SINTERING

Marija Prekajski Đorđević¹, Jelena Erčić¹, Emilija Nidžović¹,
Aleksa Luković¹, Ravi Kumar^{2,3}, Branko Matović¹, Jelena Maletaškić¹

¹Centre of Excellence-CextremeLab Vinca, Institute of Nuclear Sciences Vinca,
University of Belgrade, Mike Petrovica Alasa 12-14, 11000, Belgrade, Serbia

²Laboratory for High Performance Ceramics, Department of Metallurgical and
Materials Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology-Madras (IIT Madras),
Chennai, 600036, India

³Ceramic Technologies Group-Center of Excellence in Materials and
Manufacturing for Futuristic Mobility, Indian Institute of Technology-Madras
(IIT Madras), Chennai, 600036, India

Entropy-Stabilized Oxides are advanced ceramic materials that possess highly desirable functional properties. Through a five-component oxide formulation, these materials utilize configurational entropy to achieve phase stabilization. In this study we have successfully synthesized a novel type of high-entropy fluorite oxide, specifically $Zr_{0.2}Hf_{0.2}Ce_{0.2}Yb_{0.2}Gd_{0.2}O_{2-\delta}$, through the Self Propagation Room Temperature reaction (SPRT) method. Through heat treatment experiments, it was observed that the phase composition of all samples remained a single phase after high-temperature heating. Furthermore, a thermal treatment at 1500°C resulted in a fully crystallised single-phase fluorite structure. The powders also demonstrated a lack of agglomeration, which allowed for the sintered specimen to exhibit sufficient densification with a small porosity that was uniformly distributed throughout the samples.

Figure 1. XRD patterns of synthesized and thermally treated $Zr_{0.2}Hf_{0.2}Ce_{0.2}Yb_{0.2}Gd_{0.2}O_{2-\delta}$ samples

P-7

THE INFLUENCE OF SPARK PLASMA SINTERING TEMPERATURE ON THE PROPERTIES OF Sb-DOPED BARIUM STANNATE CERAMICS

Jelena Mitrović^{1,2}, Milica Počuča-Nešić^{1,2}, Aleksandar Malešević^{1,2}, Olivera Zemljak^{1,2}, Matejka Podlogar³, Sandra Drev³, Slavko Bernik³, Goran Branković^{1,2}

¹*Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, University of Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Center of Excellence for Green Technologies, Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia*

Barium-stannate (BaSnO₃, BSO) is a member of the perovskite-type alkaline earth stannates ASnO₃ (A = Ca, Sr, Ba) with an ideal cubic crystal structure (space group: *Pm $\bar{3}$ m*). Doping with antimony (Sb⁵⁺) can change this wide band-gap semiconductor ($E_g = 3.1\text{-}3.4$ eV) into an *n*-type semiconductor with high electrical conductivity at room temperature. The major drawbacks in the BSO-based ceramics synthesis are phase composition and low density of final ceramic materials. These problems could be solved using spark plasma sintering (SPS), a current and pressure-assisted technique, which enables the preparation of dense ceramics at significantly lower temperatures and for a shorter time.

To investigate the influence of spark plasma sintering temperature on the structural, microstructural and electrical properties of BaSn_{1-x}Sb_xO₃ (BSSO, $x = 0.00; 0.04; 0.06; 0.08; \text{ and } 0.10$) ceramics samples, BSSO powders were spark plasma sintered at 1100 °C, 1200 °C and 1250 °C for 5 min.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis confirmed that all ceramic samples sintered at 1100 °C crystallized in a single-phased cubic BSO structure. Their relative densities were in the range of 72–82% ρ_t . Sintering at 1200 °C increased the samples' relative densities to 79–96% ρ_t , but also induced the formation of a barium-rich secondary phase, Ba₂SnO₄. Raising the sintering temperature further to 1250 °C induced the melting of all samples except BaSn_{0.92}Sb_{0.08}O₃. Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) revealed that doping with antimony decreased the grain sizes in BSSO samples sintered at 1100 °C and 1200 °C up to the concentration $x = 0.08$.

Electrical measurements revealed the typical semiconductor behavior of the undoped samples, showing nonlinear current-voltage characteristic and the existence of one semicircle in their impedance spectra, characteristic for materials with double Schottky barrier at the grain boundaries. However, samples with higher dopant concentrations ($x = 0.08$ and 0.10) showed significantly lower electrical resistivity and linear current-voltage characteristic. The lowest and almost constant value of electrical resistivity in the temperature range of 25–150 °C, and complete loss of the semicircle in its impedance spectrum revealed the metallic-like behavior of sample BaSn_{0.92}Sb_{0.08}O₃ sintered at 1200 °C.

P-8

ANDESITE BASALT AS A NATURAL RAW MATERIAL FOR OBTAINING GLASS-CERAMICS

Vladimir Pavkov^{1,2}, Gordana Bakić³, Vesna Maksimović^{1,2},
Dušan Bučevac¹, Marija Prekajski Đorđević^{1,2}, Ivana Cvijović-Alagić^{1,2},
Branko Matović^{1,2}

¹*Department of Materials Science, Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences - National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Center for Synthesis, Processing and Characterization of Materials for Application in Extreme Conditions – CEXTREME LAB, Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

The industrial requirements in the 21st century are environmentally friendly and light construction materials with good physical-mechanical properties manufactured from cheap natural raw materials available in large quantities. One of these materials is basalt. Basalt is a natural igneous rock of volcanic origin, with a significant amount in Serbia. Basalt belongs to the group of non-hazardous and eco-friendly materials.

Andesite basalt aggregate from the "Donje Jarinje" site, Serbia, was used as the starting natural raw material for obtaining the glass-ceramic material. The aggregate is from 2 to 5 mm in size. The aggregate was milled in the tungsten-carbide vibrating cup mill for 30 min to obtain a fine powder for synthesis. The homogenization of andesite basalt powder and binder was carried out in the mortar and pestle for 10 min. The paraplast was used as a binder with a content of 0.6 wt.%. After that, uniaxial pressing of the powder at a pressure of 50 MPa was performed. A forming green compact, cold isostatic pressing was performed with a pressure of 230 MPa to increase its density. The sintering was carried out at the temperature of 1060 °C for 60 min in the air. The sintered glass-ceramic sample was a relative density of 99.5%, a macrohardness of 6.7 GPa and a fracture toughness of 2.2 MPa·m^{1/2} [1].

The andesite basalt powder was characterized using the laser light diffraction method, X-ray diffraction method and scanning electron microscopy. Sintered glass-ceramic material was characterized using the X-ray diffraction method, Archimedes principle, scanning electron and optical light microscopy and the Vickers hardness test.

The glass-ceramic material obtained by sintering andesite basalt powder could be used for various industrial applications in the civil engineering, mechanical, chemical, and petrochemical industries, as well as for the making of containers to store nuclear waste.

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P-9

METAL-ORGANIC PEROVSKITES $[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3][\text{M}^{\text{II}}(\text{HCOO})_3]$ (M = Cu, Mn and Co)

J. Mužević¹, N. Penić¹, E. Topić², D. Barišić¹, M. Rubčić², D. Pajić¹

¹Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb, Croatia

²Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb, Croatia

Perovskites (ABX_3) are currently highly popular in the science of materials, especially metal-organic perovskites containing both organic and inorganic characteristics. Because of their structural features that are prone to substitution, hybrid organic-inorganic perovskites (HOIP) have many potentials. The most promising is the vast majority of magnetic properties they hold. However, the magnetic properties of most perovskites have only been tested on powdered samples due to the lack of synthetic strategies for growing monocrystals with quality morphology large enough for measuring magnetic properties [1].

With this in mind, we have prepared a series of ABX_3 hybrid organic-inorganic copper(II), cobalt(II), manganese(II) perovskites containing formate bridge on the X site and a guanidinium molecule on the A site; $[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3][\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_3]$ (1), $[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3][\text{Mn}(\text{HCOO})_3]$ (2) and $[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3][\text{Co}(\text{HCOO})_3]$ (3). For all compounds, the quality monocrystals large enough are obtained. Also, for all obtained compounds, temperature dependence of magnetization $M(T)$ was measured using SQUID magnetometer in the temperature range 2–350 K. According to the crystal structure the magnetic susceptibility was determined for chain compounds using Fischers approach for local spins larger than $\frac{1}{2}$, and Bonner-Fischer approach for local spins $\frac{1}{2}$.

$[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3][\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_3]$ (1)

$[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3][\text{Mn}(\text{HCOO})_3]$ (2)

$[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3][\text{Co}(\text{HCOO})_3]$ (3)

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P-10

THERMAL SPRAYING OF Ti₂AlC COATINGS

Aleksandar Maslarevic^{1*}, Gordana M. Bakic¹, Bratislav Rajcic²,
Nenad Milosevic¹, Vesna Maksimovic³, Vladimir Pavkov³

¹Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

²Innovation Center, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Belgrade,
Belgrade, Serbia

³Vinca Institute of Nuclear Science, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia,
University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

Compound Ti₂AlC is a MAX phase discovered in the early 1960s. It is well known that Ti₂AlC has excellent physical and mechanical properties and chemical stability [1]. On the surface of Ti₂AlC, at high temperatures, a stable, protective oxide layer, Al₂O₃, is usually formed [2], whose coefficient of thermal expansion is approximately equal to the coefficient of thermal expansion of Ti₂AlC [3]. If this Al₂O₃ layer is compact, it stops further oxygen penetration and protects Ti₂AlC from further oxidation. Due to its excellent oxidation resistance, MAX phase Ti₂AlC has great potential in producing protective coatings for components in the industry that are exposed to high temperatures [4,5]. Coating Ti₂AlC can be applied to the substrate by different thermal spraying processes. Cold spraying (CS), high velocity air fuel (HVOF), and high velocity oxygen fuel (HVOF) processes can be singled out as particularly interesting due to the possibility of applying thicker coatings to the substrate [6].

This paper describes the technology of applying the Ti₂AlC phase on heat-resistant steel using the HVOF system of the third generation, which uses a mixture of oxygen and kerosene as fuel. Also, the filler material, which was in the form of powder, and the microstructure of the obtained coating were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The Ti₂AlC coating was successfully applied and a relatively good mechanical bond was achieved with the substrate. The goal of surfacing the Ti₂AlC coating was a potential application for protecting steel from oxidation at elevated temperatures.

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P-11

STRUCTURAL MODIFICATION OF GRAPHENE OXIDE/12 TUNGSTOPHOSPHORIC ACID COMPOSITES VIA ION BEAM IRRADIATION FOR IMPROVED ELECTROCHEMICAL CHARGE STORAGE

Željko Mravik¹, Milica Pejčić¹, Jelena Rmuš¹, Blaž Belec²,
Nemanja Gavrilov³, Vladimir Skuratov⁴, Zoran Jovanović¹

¹*Center of Excellence for Hydrogen and Renewable Energy (CONVINCE),
Laboratory of Physics, Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences,
University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Materials Research Laboratory, University of Nova Gorica,
Ajdovščina, Slovenia*

³*Faculty of Physical Chemistry, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

⁴*Flerov Laboratory of Nuclear Reactions, Joint Institute for Nuclear Research,
Dubna, Moscow Region, Russia*

Graphene oxide (GO) is a well-known and highly appreciated material for energy-related applications, particularly in electrochemical supercapacitors due to its large surface area and surface chemistry that enhances capacitance through redox reactions. It has been found that modifying the properties of GO can improve its capacitance [1]. Also, incorporating heteropolyacids (HPA) onto GO and modifying the HPA structure via thermal treatment has been shown to enhance the material's charge storage properties [2]. Ion beam irradiation is an advanced method to simultaneously modify various properties of materials, including structure, surface chemistry, and morphology.

In this study, composites of GO and 12-tungstophosphoric acid (WPA) with 6 and 13 wt.% of WPA were synthesized and modified using ion beam irradiation (xenon ions, 150 MeV). The degree of modification of irradiated GO and composites was analyzed using Raman spectroscopy, XPS, XRD, and SEM methods to assess structure, surface chemistry, and morphology. Reduction of oxygen functional groups on GO surface, higher number of defects and formation of ion tracks was noticed for irradiated GO samples. Results showed that higher fluences are required to achieve the same degree of modification of surface chemistry in composites as in GO.

Galvanostatic charge/discharge was used to investigate the applicability of the materials in supercapacitors, and it was found that irradiated composites exhibited improved capacitance and cycling stability compared to GO. This was attributed to the previously noted structural modification of WPA due to ion beam irradiation [3,4].

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P-12

AB INITIO INVESTIGATION OF THE NOVEL Cr₂SiN₄ COMPOUND UNDER EXTREME PRESSURE CONDITIONS

Tamara Škundrić^{1,2,3}, Dejan Zagorac^{1,2}, Milan Pejić^{1,2},
Dušica Jovanović^{1,2,3}, Jelena Zagorac^{1,2}, Branko Matović^{1,2}

¹*Institute of Nuclear Sciences “Vinča”, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Centre of Excellence “Cextreme Lab”, Centre for synthesis, processing and characterization of materials for application in extreme conditions, Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science and Mathematics, University of Niš, Niš, Serbia*

Exploration of the energy landscape of the Cr₂SiN₄ system led to several promising structural candidates, generated using the combination of global optimization, data mining, and the PCAE method. However, in order to further investigate these phases and especially to examine their behavior under extreme conditions, quantum mechanical calculations have been performed. For several different modifications, thermodynamic functions have been calculated for the pressure range from 0 to 10 GPa, using the GGA-PBE functional. Evidently, a gradual decrease in the unit cell parameters and corresponding volumes has been spotted in all of the phases under study, when pressure is applied. Correspondingly, with pressure elevation minute change in total energy and a gradual increase in Gibbs free energy has been observed, and finally, in all of the investigated phases, a rising trend in bulk modulus has been evidenced when employing pressure. The largest value of bulk modulus is found in the equilibrium spinel type modification, from the initial value of 368.23 GPa to the 407.83 GPa, which it reaches at the pressure of 10 GPa. Thus, it is considered that this phase has the highest capacity of resistance to the volume change under pressure. However, the smallest value of bulk modulus is found in Mg₂SiO₄-type modification, a phase that appears in the most extreme conditions. The bulk modulus of this phase reaches only 161.51 GPa at the pressure of 10 GPa, from the initial value of 128.46 GPa. Ab initio calculations of the mechanical properties in the high-pressure regime were performed using the CRYSTAL solid-state-quantum-chemical program. These findings could be of great value, as they give us an insight into the behavior of this novel material under extreme conditions. As this material could potentially have a very wide industrial

and technological applicability, these results could provide us with more valuable information for further synthesis and development of new Cr-Si-N materials with improved performances in extreme conditions.

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P-13

THEORETICAL STUDY OF ALN/BN MIXED CHEMICAL SYSTEMS AND THEIR MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Dejan Zagorac^{1,2}, Jelena Zagorac^{1,2}, Matej Fonovic³, Tamara Škundrić^{1,2}, Milan Pejić^{1,2}, Dušica Jovanović^{1,2}, Milos B. Djukic⁴, Branko Matović^{1,2}

¹*Institute of Nuclear Sciences “Vinča”, Materials Science Laboratory,
University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Center of excellence “CextremeLab”, Center for synthesis, processing, and
characterization of materials for application in the extreme conditions,
Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Faculty of Engineering, University of Rijeka-RiTeh, Rijeka, Croatia*

⁴*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Belgrade, Serbia*

In the last few decades, aluminum nitride (AlN) and boron nitride (BN) had become a point of interest to many researchers and scholars from different disciplines around the world. Due to its broad attractive properties, AlN has been successfully used in various applications, starting from advanced ceramics materials, additive for grain size control in micro-alloyed steels, through optoelectronics and microelectronics, and finally to semiconductors. On the other hand, BN has broad applications in various fields, such as 2D material, lubricant material, superhard and semiconductor material as well as many others. This study focuses on the mixed AlN/BN compounds, in particular, boron-rich AlN [1] and aluminum-rich BN [2] systems, thus having the entire range of AlN/BN compositions. The special focus was on structural, elastic, and mechanical properties investigated using DFT methods. Important mechanical properties were investigated; bulk modulus B , shear modulus K , Young's modulus E , Vickers hardness H_v , anisotropy, stiffness, Poisson's ratio, and brittleness/ductility relationship, in order to offer novel technological and industrial applications of mixed AlN/BN materials.

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P-14

ENERGY LANDSCAPE EXPLORATION AND CRYSTAL STRUCTURE PREDICTION OF TWO NOVEL COMPOUNDS IN THE Cr-Si-N SYSTEM

Tamara Škundrić^{1,2,3}, Dejan Zagorac^{1,2}, Milan Pejić^{1,2},
Dušica Jovanović^{1,2,3}, Jelena Zagorac^{1,2}, Branko Matović^{1,2}

¹Institute of Nuclear Sciences “Vinča”, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

²Centre of Excellence “Cextreme Lab”, Centre for synthesis, processing and characterization of materials for application in extreme conditions, Belgrade, Serbia

³Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science and Mathematics, University of Niš, Niš, Serbia

Due to the great potential for a very wide technological and industrial application, the Cr-Si-N system is a very appealing material for research. Although previous experimental studies have shown the material only in thin films, there are several theoretically predicted promising structural candidates in bulk Cr-Si-N, with the composition of Cr₂SiN₄ [1]. Using the global exploration of the energy landscape, two more compositions within this system, CrSi₂N₄ and Cr₃SiN, have been investigated. Every structure candidate that was found in these searches was subjected to the crystallographic analysis and all the promising ones were subjected to a local optimization on the *ab initio* level. Since there exist no experimental data that one could compare with, local optimizations have been performed on the DFT level employing both, LDA-PZ and the GGA-PBE functional, for comparison.

Global optimization generated several relevant phases in the CrSi₂N₄ system. The most favorable structure became TiMn₂O₄-type modification with the lowest calculated energy on the whole energy landscape. However, the spinel structure which was referred to as a global minimum in the Cr₂SiN₄ system, became much higher in energy when optimized in CrSi₂N₄. Also, some non-favorable phases from the previous composition became favorable phases in the CrSi₂N₄ system. Thus, this optimization yielded several promising structural candidates. Moreover, we have investigated another Cr-Si-N composition in Cr₃SiN system which resulted in two cubic perovskite structure variations, both crystallizing in space group *Pm-3m* (no. 221). Finally, this is an interesting material with possible very wide application and all these findings could help us find the best way for future synthesis. However, since there is still so much that has not yet been discovered about this material, further research is of crucial importance.

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P-15

ZnO/ZnS CORE/SHELL NANOSTRUCTURES: EXPERIMENTS COMBINED WITH *AB INITIO* CALCULATIONS

Jelena Zagorac^{1,2}, Dejan Zagorac^{1,2}, Vesna Šrot³, Marjan Randelović⁴,
Milan Pejić^{1,2}, Peter A. van Aken³, Branko Matović^{1,2}, J. Christian Schön⁵

¹*Institute of Nuclear Sciences "Vinča", Materials Science Laboratory,
University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Center of excellence "CextremeLab", Center for synthesis, processing, and
characterization of materials for application in the extreme conditions,
Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Max Planck Institute for Solid State Research, Center for Electron Microscopy,
Stuttgart, Germany*

⁴*University of Niš, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Niš, Serbia*

⁵*Max Planck Institute for Solid State Research, Nanoscale Science Department,
Stuttgart, Germany*

ZnO/ZnS core/shell nanostructures were synthesized by gas-phase sulfidation of ZnO powder at elevated temperatures. The structural, morphological, and element compositional analysis of ZnO/ZnS core/shell nanostructures were characterized by XRD, imaging, and analytical (S)TEM, and concur with literature data. The XRD results showed a three-phase composition, where the ZnO phase is dominant and appears as a wurtzite structure, and the ZnS phase appears as both cubic sphalerite and hexagonal wurtzite structure. The (S)TEM imaging combined with EDX and EELS further shows that these are core/shell structures, with a relatively thick interface, where the shell consists of ZnS and the core of ZnO, respectively. The experimental results were combined with theoretical modeling of ZnO/ZnS (hetero) structures and band gap calculations for ZnO/ZnS systems, yielding more insights into the properties of the nanoparticles [1]. In particular, we have studied the electronic properties of the investigated ZnO/ZnS chemical systems, where a band gap measurement of the ZnO/ZnS core/shell sample has been performed. Theoretical supercell models were created to investigate the structure and electronic properties of ZnO/ZnS. DFT hybrid calculations were executed using PBE0 and HSE06 functionals. Computed band structures concur with DRS measurements where a direct band gap has been observed. Additional band structures and band gap tuning depending on the structural features have been suggested. Our multidisciplinary study investigates in great detail the structural and electronic properties of ZnO/ZnS core/shell nanostructures with diverse possible applications, from nanostructures, semiconductors photovoltaics, light-emitting diodes (LED), to heterostructures, solar cells, infrared detectors, and thermoelectrics.

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P-16

ENERGY LANDSCAPE AND CRYSTAL STRUCTURE INVESTIGATIONS OF LANTHANUM FLUORO SULFIDE LaFS

Milan Pejić^{1,2}, Dejan Zagorac^{1,2}, J. Christian Schön³, Jelena Zagorac^{1,2},
Tamara Škundrić^{1,2}, Branko Matović^{1,2}

¹*Materials Science Laboratory, Institute of Nuclear Sciences “Vinča”,
University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Center for Synthesis, Processing and Characterization of Materials for
Application in the Extreme Conditions “CextremeLab”, Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Max Planck Institute for Solid State Research, Stuttgart, Germany*

Rare earth metals and their compounds and alloys have important applications in various mature markets as well as in high-technology markets, so identifying new rare earth compounds and modifications is an important enterprise. Traditionally, this is done experimentally, by synthesizing many new materials in an exploratory fashion and studying their properties. However, this approach is increasingly complemented by theoretical calculations that predict new compounds or modifications without recourse to experimental input [1].

In order to theoretically predict new stable and/or metastable modifications of LaFS, the following methods were used. First, global explorations were performed on the energy landscape of periodic approximants of LaFS using simulated annealing with empirical potentials, implemented in the software package G42+ [2]. The variable periodically repeated simulation cell contained 4 (4La + 4F + 4S; 12 atoms total), 6 (6La + 6F + 6S; 18 atoms total), and 8 (8La + 8F + 8S; 24 atoms total) formula units of LaFS, and more than a million structure candidates were obtained this way. These candidates were analyzed regarding their symmetry, grouped according to which space group they belong to, and then compared with each other using the CMPZ algorithm [3] implemented in the software package KPLOT [4]. The structures were then sorted by relevance criteria, such as (empirical potential) energy, how often the structure was found, and symmetry. In this fashion, about one hundred relevant structure candidates were identified. For these, local structural optimizations were performed on the ab-initio level with different functionals using the CRYSTAL software package [5].

Finally, E(V) (energy vs. volume) and H(p) (enthalpy vs. pressure) curves were calculated for the most promising structure candidates in order to determine the stable phase at a given pressure and the transition pressures among the phases.

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P-17

ELECTRONIC PROPERTIES OF PREDICTED Y₂O₂S USING *AB INITIO* CALCULATIONS

Dragana Jordanov¹, Dejan Zagorac¹, Klaus Doll²

¹“Vinča” Institute of Nuclear Science, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

²Institute for Theoretical Chemistry, University of Stuttgart, Stuttgart, Germany

Crystal structure prediction has been accomplished to investigate the energy landscape of Yttrium Oxysulfide (Y₂O₂S). Global optimizations on the energy landscape of Y₂O₂S have been carried out using empirical potentials followed by, a local optimization using *ab initio* calculations [1]. Our calculations showed the *Alpha* phase in good agreement with the experimentally observed trigonal structure. Furthermore, novel *Beta* and *Gamma* modifications of pure Yttrium Oxysulfide are suggested. Y₂O₂S is a material known as a wide-gap semiconductor. From the calculation of the bulk, it is found that the material has an indirect band gaps and that the top of the valence bands shows an anisotropic character which means an anisotropic mass of the hole [2]. We included the calculation of the Density of States (DOS) for the most stable structures (*Alpha*, *Beta* and *Gamma*) and discuss the band gaps, also [3]. The results presented here have all been obtained using the B3LYP functional and local density approximation (LDA). Our calculations were in good agreement with the literature data [4].

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P-18

DFT STUDY OF GLUTAMINE (L) MOLECULE INTERACTION WITH THE 001 AND 101 ANATASE SLAB SURFACES IN A VACUUM

Dušica Jovanović^{1,2}, J. Christian Schön³, Dejan Zagorac^{1,4},
Aleksandra Zarubica², Branko Matović^{1,4}, Milan Pejić^{1,4},
Tamara Škundrić^{1,4}, Jelena Zagorac^{1,4}

¹*Institute of Nuclear Sciences Vinča, Materials Science Laboratory,
University of Belgrade, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science and Mathematics, University of
Nis, 18000 Nis, Serbia*

³*Max Planck Institute for Solid State Research, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany*

⁴*Center for Synthesis, Processing and Characterization of Materials for
Application in the Extreme Conditions-CextremeLab, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia*

A better understanding of the molecular inorganic-organic interactions in biological environments is of key importance for understanding physiological processes, and the safe application of medical implants, medicaments, drug delivery systems, etc. [1]. Glutamine (L) amino acid as the building block of the cell wall, peptides, proteins, etc, plays a major role in biological systems in biosynthesis and energy production [2]. Tumor cells show an increased demand for amino acids due to their rapid proliferation, thus, targeting their metabolism is becoming a potential oncological therapeutic strategy. One of the inorganic materials that show antitumor properties is titanium dioxide, while its doping was found to enhance interactions with biological systems [3]. In addition, Au / Ag / Cu doped TiO₂ particles showed toxic effects on several cancer cell lines. Studies have shown that glutamine can interact with TiO₂ slabs through a variety of mechanisms that depend on factors such as the orientation of the glutamine molecule on the TiO₂ surfaces, surface type (101 shows more stability, while 001 proved to be more reactive), and the presence of other molecules or ions in the surrounding environment [4]. In this study, we locally optimized 2D-slab structures of pristine and Au / Ag / Cu doped anatase 001 and 101 surfaces, then similarly optimized a single glutamine molecule in a vacuum. We placed the pre-optimized glutamine molecule in various orientations and on a variety of locations onto the relaxed substrate surfaces and then performed *ab initio* relaxations of the molecule on the substrate slabs. We employed the DFT method with a GGA-PBE functional, implemented in the Quantum Espresso code. Some of the most interesting physical interactions between molecule and surface (Fig. 1) obtained in this study could show promising applications in biomedicine.

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Figure 1. Interaction of optimized Glutamine (L) molecule with a) pristine anatase slab (101) surface; b) Au doped anatase slab (101) surface; c) Ag doped anatase slab (001) surface; d) Cu doped anatase slab (101) surface; in a vacuum, visualized by VESTA program.

P-19

**DFT STUDY OF NEW HYBRID ORGANIC-INORGANIC
PEROVSKITES: GUANIDINIUM-BX₃ SUBSTITUTED BY
B = (Sn²⁺, Ge²⁺, Ba²⁺, Zn²⁺) AND X = (I⁻, Br⁻)**

Dušica Jovanović^{1,2}, Dejan Zagorac^{1,3}, J. Christian Schön⁴,
Aleksandra Zarubica², Branko Matović^{1,3}, Milan Pejić^{1,3},
Tamara Škundrić^{1,3}, Jelena Zagorac^{1,3}

¹*Institute of Nuclear Sciences Vinča, Materials Science Laboratory, University of Belgrade, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Department of Chemistry, Faculty of science and mathematics, University of Nis, 18000 Nis, Serbia*

³*Center for Synthesis, Processing and Characterization of Materials for Application in the Extreme Conditions-CextremeLab, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia*

⁴*Max Planck Institute for Solid State Research, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany*

In recent years, perovskite solar cells (PSC) development has attracted great attention as a “green” energy source that might even replace fossil fuels soon [1]. Conventional perovskite solar cells mostly contain toxic lead, which contributes to environmental pollution, so the solution was found to substitute lead with some non-toxic metal [2]. Our investigation of hybrid organic-inorganic perovskites aims to increase the chemical stability as well as to decrease the band gap value of crystal perovskites which enables better conductivity and shifts the absorbance range, in order to produce the most efficient perovskite solar cells. The *ab initio* calculations of GA-BX₃, where GA is the guanidinium cation C(NH₂)₃⁺, with several different inorganic cations and anions - specifically: B = (Sn²⁺, Ge²⁺, Ba²⁺, Zn²⁺) and X = (I⁻, Br⁻) have been performed using Density Functional Theory (DFT), with several functionals, Local Density Approximation (LDA) and Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE), as well as HSE06 (Heyd-Scuseria-Ernzerhof) hybrid functional. Further investigations of structural and electronic properties will provide insights into the potential applications of these new hybrid organic-inorganic perovskite structures (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Unit cell of the crystalline hybrid organic-inorganic perovskite hexagonal structure – GASnI_3 (GA – guanidinium cation, $\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3^+$) (space group P63/m), visualized by the VESTA program.

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P-20

EXAMINATION OF IQOS RESIDUE, ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT AND POTENTIAL APPLICATION

Vladimir Dodevski¹, Milena Rosić¹, Maria Čebela¹, Sanja Krstić¹, Hadi Waisi², Jasmina Popović³

¹Laboratory for Material Science, Institute of Nuclear Sciences „Vinča“, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, P.O. Box 522, 11001 Belgrade, Serbia

²University of Belgrade, Institute for General and Physical Chemistry, Studentski trg 12-16, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

³Department of Wood Science and Technology, Faculty of Forestry, University of Belgrade, Serbia

IQOS (I-Quit-Ordinary-Smoking) is a brand of heated tobacco. It is an alternative to traditional cigarettes, which involves heating tobacco rather than burning it. IQOS devices heat tobacco sticks, called HEETS or HeatSticks, to a temperature that is high enough to release nicotine and flavor, but not high enough to produce smoke.

After consuming IQOS, we treated the remains of HEETS with pyrolysis at 800 degrees. In this way, we have protected the environment from pollution, and in addition, we have obtained carbon material, which further has various applications. The obtained final product was tested using different methods and based on the tested properties, it can be said that the material can potentially be used as an energy fuel, a supercapacitor, for the removal of organic compounds, a drug carrier, etc.

Keywords: IQOS, carbon material, environment

P-21

EXAMINATION OF DIFFERENT RAW MATERIALS, AS PRECURSORS FOR OBTAINING CARBON MATERIALS

Vladimir Dodevski¹, Milena Rosić¹, Maria Čebela¹, Sanja Krstić¹,
Hadi Waisi², Jasmina Popović³

¹*Laboratory for Material Science, Institute of Nuclear Sciences „Vinča“,
National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade,
P.O. Box 522, 11001 Belgrade, Serbia*

²*University of Belgrade, Institute for General and Physical Chemistry,
Studentski trg 12-16, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Department of Wood Science and Technology, Faculty of Forestry,
University of Belgrade, Serbia*

The examination of different raw materials as precursors for obtaining carbon materials is an important area of research due to the wide range of applications for carbon materials in various fields, including energy storage, catalysis, and electronic devices. Some of the commonly studied precursors for carbon materials include biomass, petroleum-based precursors, waste materials, natural materials. The selection of a precursor material depends on various factors, such as the intended application of the carbon material, the availability and cost of the precursor, and the properties of the resulting carbon material. Different precursors can result in carbon materials with varying structures, porosities, and surface chemistries, which can affect their properties and performance in different applications. In our work, we used cherry pits, sour cherry, vineyard peach pits, bean and pea husks. The properties of the initial precursors were tested and then they were treated physically and chemically at different temperatures and times. Correlation of the properties between the initial and final samples was made, as well as their potential application in relation to the obtained properties.

Keywords: carbon materials, precursor, properties

P-22

**SUPERCAPACITIVE PROPERTIES OF CARBON MATERIALS
ACTIVATED BY ALKALI METAL HYDROXIDES OBTAINED
FROM SUCROSE**

Sanja Krstić, Vladimir Dodevski, Maria Čebela, Milena Rosić,
Marija Egerić, Radojka Vujasin, Darko Jaćimovski

*Laboratory for Material Science, Institute of Nuclear Sciences "Vinča",
National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade,
P.O. Box522, 11001 Belgrade, Serbia*

The main aim of this research is to show influence of different hydroxides, applied in carbon materials activation process on the electrochemical properties of activated carbon samples. The carbon material samples were prepared by hydrothermal treatment of sucrose and thermally activated using KOH, NaOH and LiOH by chemical activation method. The electrochemical properties of the obtained carbon material samples were examined by cyclic voltammetry and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and correlated to their physicochemical properties. Investigated samples showed characteristic capacitor-like behavior. The best result of specific capacitance was obtained for the sample synthesized treated by KOH, while the increase in capacitance follows the arrangement of the growth of ionic radius of a metal from an alkali which is used for activation. Dependence on the type of hydroxide is due to differences in the radii of a metal. The alkalis with larger radii of metal produce wider pores and consequently the structure of a porous layer become more accessible and available to the charge transfer of capacitive response.

Keywords: active carbon; sucrose, alkali-treated carbon materials; hydrothermal obtained carbons; electrochemical capacitance distribution.

P-23

ZnMn₂O₄ AS A CATHODE MATERIAL IN AN AQUEOUS SOLUTION OF ZnCl₂ AND Mn(NO₃)₂ FOR Zn-ION BATTERIES

Nenad Nikolić¹, Jelena Senćanski², Stevan Blagojević², Maja Pagnacco³,
Ivana Stojković Simatović⁴

¹University of Belgrade, Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, Kneza Višeslava 1, 11030 Belgrade, Belgrade, Republic of Serbia

²University of Belgrade, Institute of General and Physical Chemistry, Studentski trg 12-16, 11000 Belgrade, Republic of Serbia

³University of Belgrade, Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, Njegoševa 12, 11000 Belgrade, Republic of Serbia

⁴University of Belgrade, Faculty of Physical Chemistry, Belgrade, Studentski trg 12-16, 11000 Belgrade, Republic of Serbia

Due to Li-ion batteries having become the main power source of most portable electronic devices, their waste has also become a significant environmental problem. To find batteries that would be environmentally friendly, this work examines Zn-ion batteries in an aqueous solution of ZnCl₂. The ZnMnO₄ was synthesized by glycine nitrate combustion of Zn(NO₃)₂, Mn(NO₃)₂ and glycine as a chelating agent [1]. The structure of the material obtained was characterized by X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) showing a spinel structure; the morphology was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) showing that nano-particles were obtained. The electrochemical characterization was done by cyclic voltammetry in an aqueous solution of ZnCl₂. The mixture pasted on the glossy carbon electrode was prepared by mixing the cathode material, graphite and polyvinyl diene difluoride (PVDF) in a ratio 85:10:5 [2]. Due to the low discharge capacity obtained of ~14 mAh g⁻¹ for 5 mV s⁻¹, further examination was done by adding 1 ml of 1M Mn(NO₃)₂ into 10ml of a saturated aqueous solution of ZnCl₂. After adding the Mn(NO₃)₂, the discharge capacity increased from ~14 mAh g⁻¹ to ~65 mAh g⁻¹ at the same polarization rate, making this additive a promising one for aqueous Zn-ion batteries. Further investigation needs to be directed to adding the same additive in larger amounts compared to 1ml to the same volume of the electrolyte. The results obtained suggest the aqueous Zn-ion battery described in this work to be a potentially promising “green” battery that may replace harmful commercial organic Li-ion batteries.

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P-24

ELECTROCHEMICAL FABRICATION OF TiO₂ NANOTUBE ARRAYS IN FLUORIDE-FREE SYSTEM

Miroslav Hnatko^{1,2}, Anna Kityk^{1,2}, Peter Švec^{2,3}

¹*Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Dúbravská cesta, 9, Bratislava, 84536, Slovak Republic*

²*Centre of Excellence for Advanced Materials Application, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Dúbravská cesta, 5807/9, Bratislava, 84511, Slovak Republic*

³*Institute of Physics, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Dúbravská cesta, 9, Bratislava 84511, Slovak Republic*

TiO₂ is a material with a number of almost unique properties used for many years in various functional applications such as catalysis, photocatalysis, self-cleaning, wetting, solar cell, gas sensing, biomedical, ceramics, interference coatings, etc. [1]. The most-common method for TiO₂ growing is anodization in aqueous electrolytes: HF electrolytes or HF mixtures. The second-generation electrolytes are buffered neutral electrolytes containing NaF or NH₄F instead of HF. The third-generation systems for TiO₂ fabrication are fluoride containing water free electrolytes (glycerol, CH₃COOH, ethylene glycol electrolytes) [1].

In this work was proposed novel eco-friendly fluoride-free method of TiO₂ nanotube fabrication. It was demonstrated that TiO₂ micro- and nano-array can be created on Ti-6Al-4V alloy by anodic galvanostatic and potentiostatic treatment in ethylene glycol containing deep eutectic solvent (DES) without fluoride-containing additives. It was shown that electrochemical dissolution process of Ti-6Al-4V in DES creates organized arrays of amorphous non-uniformly growing tubular units based on Ti and O, Fig. 1. The main outer diameter of tubes was evaluated to be ~75 nm and the inner diameter corresponds to ~20 nm. The micro-sized pattern looks like micropits ~25 μm in diameter and ~5 μm in depth, uniformly distributed over the entire surface of the treated samples. Such surface design [2] can be successfully used to significantly increase the surface area of Ti-samples and improve its catalytic properties. Fluoride-free electrolyte can be proposed as environmentally friendly alternative to the toxic and aggressive common electrolytes.

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P-25

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF SEPIOLITE/ZrO₂ COMPOSITES FOR PHOSPHATE REMOVAL FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS

Željka Milovanović¹, Slavica Lazarević², Ivona Janković-Častvan²,
Željko Radovanović³, Slobodan Cvetković¹, Đorđe Janačković²,
Rada Petrović²

¹*University of Belgrade - Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy,
Department of Ecology and TechnoEconomics, Njegoševa 12, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy,
Karnegijeva 4, Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Innovation Center of the Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy,
Karnegijeva 4, Belgrade, Serbia*

The sepiolite/ZrO₂ composites were prepared in toluene using sepiolite and zirconium propoxide by two different procedures. The efficiency of the obtained adsorbents for the removal of phosphate from water solutions was investigated. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive analysis (EDS), Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, DTA/TG thermal analyses, specific surface area determination and determination of the point of zero charge were used to characterize the obtained composites, Sep-ZrI and Sep-ZrII. The results indicate that ZrO₂ in the form of fine nanoparticles was successfully loaded onto the surface of sepiolite fibers. Adsorption kinetics and equilibrium isotherms were investigated to establish the adsorption rates, maximum capacities and possible mechanisms of the adsorption of phosphate from water onto Sep-ZrI and Sep-ZrII composites at a pH of 4. The adsorption kinetics and isotherm follow the pseudo second-order equation and Freundlich adsorption model, respectively.

P-26

Ag/ZnO NANOCOMPOSITES FOR PHOTOCATALYTIC APPLICATION

**Bojana Simović¹, Željko Radovanović², Goran Branković¹,
Aleksandra Dapčević³**

¹*Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, University of Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Innovation centre of Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade, Serbia*

In this work, the decoration of noble metal nanoparticles on a semiconductor surface was used as a strategy to reach strong visible light absorption and efficient electron-hole separation to enhance the photocatalytic activity of ZnO.

The Ag-modified ZnO nanopowders were obtained by the green synthesis. Zinc acetate dihydrate with different silver nitrate content (0, 0.75, 1.5 and 3 mol%) was dissolved in ethylene glycol in the presence of chitosan. The obtained mixtures in the form of gel were heated at 150 °C for 2 h and subsequently calcined at 400 °C for 1 h. The obtained samples were characterized by XRPD, FESEM, HRTEM, and UV-vis techniques while the photocatalytic efficiency was tested by monitoring the degradation of textile dyes Reactive Orange 16 (RO16), Acid Green 25 (AG25), Mordant Blue 9 (MB9), and Ethyl Violet (EV) then compared with the commercial ZnO nanopowder.

The results showed that the Ag/ZnO samples consisted of ZnO nanoparticles with an average crystallite size of about 25 nm and Ag (20–30 nm) distributed on the surface of ZnO. The uniformity in size and nearly spherical shape of ZnO nanoparticles, forming various forms of agglomerates, were observed. Compared to both, the unmodified and commercial ZnO, all the prepared Ag/ZnO composites showed a broad band in the visible region at 500 nm, resulting in a narrowing of the band gap. This band confirms the surface plasmon resonance of the metallic Ag nanoparticles, since they can absorb visible light and activate the photocatalyst in the visible spectrum.

All the obtained nanopowders showed higher adsorption power and photocatalytic activity in the degradation of RO16 dye than the commercial ZnO. The powder with 1.5 mol% of Ag had the highest photocatalytic efficiency as a consequence of smaller Ag particles and their good distribution, as well as the narrowest band gap. This means that the photocatalytic activity does not depend on the Ag content only and that the size and distribution of the metal particles play an important role. Since the ZnO with 1.5 mol% of Ag demonstrated the best photocatalytic activity, the same sample was tested for diverse dyes and the high photocatalytic efficiency was also confirmed by testing on AG25, MB9 and EV dyes.

P-27

CHARACTERIZATION AND PHOTOCATALYTIC ACTIVITY OF NEWLY SYNTHESIZED Er AND Yb DOPED SrGd₂O₄ NANOPHOSPHORUS

Tijana Stamenković¹, Marjan Ranđelović², Maria Čebela¹,
Marina Vuković³, Ivana Dinić⁴, Lidija Mančić⁴, Vesna Lojpur¹

¹*“Vinča” Institute of Nuclear Sciences, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Faculty of Science and Mathematics, University of Niš, Niš, Serbia*

³*Innovative Centre, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Belgrade, Serbia*

⁴*Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, Belgrade, Serbia*

The aim of this research was to investigate for the first-time photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue over SrGd₂O₄ powders co-doped with constant Er³⁺ (0.5 at.%) and different Yb³⁺ (1, 2.5 and 5 at.%) concentrations. Samples were successfully prepared *via* sol-gel assisted combustion method. They exhibit photoluminescence properties which are manifested as red emission at 661 nm (⁴F_{9/2} → ⁴I_{15/2}) and two green emissions at 551 and 523 nm (⁴S_{3/2} → ⁴I_{15/2} and ²H_{11/2} → ⁴I_{15/2}). X-ray Powder Diffraction pattern proved that all samples crystallize as a pure orthorhombic phase. Scanning electron microscopy was used for morphology characterization and it revealed the existence of porous agglomerated round-shaped particles. Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy showed the presence of dopant ions and even distribution of all constituting elements. To calculate the energy band gap, UV-VIS diffuse reflectance spectroscopy was performed and a value of 4.3 eV was obtained, as well as the four additional values from the bands at lower energies. Photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue was monitored using UV-VIS absorption spectroscopy. Obtained results were promising since after 4 h of exposure to the simulating Sun irradiation, more than 50% of the starting dye concentration was mineralized.

P-28

METAL ORGANIC FRAMEWORK/POLYAMIDE ELECTROSPUN NANOFIBERAS MEAN FOR CONGO RED DYE PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION

Marija Egerić¹, Aleksandra Nešić², Branka Pilić², Yi-Nan Wu^{3,4},
Aleksandar Devečerski¹, Radojka Vujasin¹, Ljiljana Matović^{1,3,4}

¹*“Vinča” Institute of Nuclear Sciences - National Institute of the Republic of
Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Faculty of Technology, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia*

³*College of Environmental Science and Engineering, State Key Laboratory of
Pollution Control and Resource Reuse, Tongji University, Shanghai, China*

⁴*Shanghai Institute of Pollution Control and Ecological Security,
Shanghai 200092, China*

Development of new methods and materials for wastewater treatment and safe discharge into the environment is an extremely important topic nowadays. Various industries produce large amounts of wastewater, while demand for clean water increases over time due to the rapid growth of human population. Different techniques are applied in order to produce hybrid materials which can be used in wastewater treatment, such as ones made of polymeric nanofibers and materials with photocatalytic properties. In this research, the electrospinning technique was used to synthesize nanofibers polyamide/UiO-66 Metal Organic Framework (MOF) composite. The content of MOF in those ultra-thin nanofiber membranes varied from 0.5 wt.%, 1 wt.%, 2 wt.% to 10 wt.%. Membranes were cut in the rectangular shape 1cm × 2 cm (making it this way easy applied and removed from the solution) and used for degradation of 10 ppm Congo Red Dye from aqueous solution in batch conditions. Removal efficiency of Congo Red was evaluated as a function of UV irradiation time. For determination of the dye concentration in solutions prior and after UV irradiation, samples were analyzed by UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The best performance was shown by membranes which contained 1 wt.% of MOF, then 2 wt.%, 0.5 wt.% and subsequently 10 wt.%, due to more homogenous distribution of MOF particles on the surface on the polyamide nanofibers. In order to test renewability of composite membranes, experiments were performed in two cycles in the same conditions. The results indicated that electrospun UiO-66/polyamide membranes can be reused for two cycles with same efficiency for removal of Congo Red dye from aqueous solution. Microstructural and morphological characterization of the synthesized nanofibers was performed using XRD, FTIR and BET.

P-29

INFLUENCE OF SWIFT HEAVY ION IRRADIATION ON PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BISMUTH-VANADATE

Marko Jelić¹, Ekaterina Korneeva², Nikita Kirilkin², Tatiana Vershinina²,
Oleg Orelovich², Vladimir Skuratov², Zoran Jovanović¹,
Sonja Jovanović¹

¹*Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences - National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Joint Institute of Nuclear Research, Dubna, Russia*

Photoelectrochemical (PEC) water splitting is a promising method for storing solar energy in the form of chemical fuels. Recently, bismuth vanadate (BiVO₄) has gained a lot of attention as photoanode due to its visible light harvesting properties, band edge positions and low-cost of synthesis. However, pronounced electron-hole recombination is a huge limiting factor and understanding the effects contributing to it is important for further advancements. In this study, the effects of swift heavy ions (SHI) irradiation on physicochemical properties of hydrothermally synthesized BiVO₄ thin films were examined. For this purpose, 150 MeV Xe ion irradiation was used at two fluences, 5×10^{10} and 5×10^{11} ions/cm². X-ray diffraction study shows that irradiated material retained initial monoclinic scheelite crystal phase together with preferential growth along [010] direction. For the highest fluence a shift of the diffraction maxima towards lower 2θ values was observed indicating increased interplanar distances. Also, higher degree of amorphization was noticed compared to sample irradiated at 5×10^{10} ions/cm². Raman spectroscopy analysis confirmed presence of bands that correspond to the monoclinic scheelite phase along with the appearance of new bands for 5×10^{11} BiVO₄ at 250, 420 and 915 cm⁻¹. Scanning electron microscopy revealed prismatic morphology of all samples with an average grain size of 600 nm. In irradiated sample formation of ion tracks, ~10 nm in diameter, was observed. Their density corresponded to applied fluence. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy analysis of Bi 4*f*, V 2*p* and O 1*s* states showed that, after irradiation, amount of V⁴⁺ increased and large extent of oxygen was present in the form of hydroxide for the 5×10^{11} irradiated sample. By using UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectroscopy it was noticed that only one optical transition was present for all three samples. Also, it was observed that band gap decreases with the increase of fluence.

P-30

PHOTOCATALYTIC EFFICIENCY ASSESSED IN SOLID STATE PHASE APPLICATION

Bojan Miljević¹, Vesna Miljić¹, John Milan van der Bergh²,
Snežana Vučetić¹

¹*University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Novi Sad, Serbia*

²*Liverpool John Moores University, Built Environment and Sustainable Technologies (BEST) Research Institute, L3 2ET, Liverpool, United Kingdom*

Self-cleaning of both exterior and interior wall surfaces possesses a strong technological demand. With this goal, ceramic based photocatalytic nanocomposite suspensions were synthesised at the optimal pH value according to the modified low supersaturation co-precipitation method [1,2]. Obtained photocatalytic material was applied on various substrates.

There are several methods for determination of photocatalytic activity using the different pollutants, but used in liquid state. For the purpose of application onto the wall surfaces these methods can't be used. Therefore, in order to assess the photocatalytic efficiency in solid state phase application, a new method was developed. Methyl orange (MO) of optimised concentration was used as a pollutant. Samples of different substrates were then kept in a climate chamber with defined parameters: temperature, relative humidity and UV/visible light. Fourier-transform infrared spectra (FTIR) were measured on these samples as well as on the blank samples kept in dark during 24 h. FTIR spectra were compared and evaluated in a sense that MO signals went through the reduction that can be monitored and quantitatively determined.

Additionally, detailed material characterisation study was performed employing various analytic methods such as scanning and transmission electron microscopy, thermogravimetric and dynamic scanning calorimetry measurements as well as microstructure analysis by X-ray powder diffraction.

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P-31

DEVELOPMENT OF $Ti_3C_2T_x$ FOR PHOTOCATALYTIC WATER PURIFICATION

Milinko Perić¹, Andrea Lazić², Elvira Tot³, Jovana Paskaš²,
Vladimir V. Srdić², Sanja J. Armaković⁴, Nikola Kanas¹

¹University of Novi Sad, BioSense Institute, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Serbia

³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Physics, Serbia

⁴University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry,
Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Serbia

Water purification has become increasingly problematic, with a wide range of challenges. Thus, more attention must be paid to removing accumulates from water such as pharmaceutical products. Hydrochlorothiazide (HCTZ) is the diuretic detected in surface water (rivers and lakes).

MXenes are two-dimensional materials of transition metals and C or/and N elements, whereas $Ti_3C_2T_x$ is the most intensively studied material. In our study, a single phase $Ti_3C_2T_x$ was obtained by chemical etching of Ti_3AlC_2 by HF, formed *in situ* using a mixture of HCl and LiF. The synthesized material was characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), UV-VIS spectrophotometry, Raman spectroscopy, and BET analysis. Due to its hydrophilicity and large surface area, followed by an appropriate band structure, $Ti_3C_2T_x$ could be used for photocatalytic water purification.

This work investigated the photolysis and photocatalysis of HCTZ under the influence of UV radiation in aqueous suspensions of Ti_3AlC_2 and $Ti_3C_2T_x$. The kinetics of photolysis and photocatalysis was monitored using HPLC. It was found that HCTZ is stable during photolysis and that $Ti_3C_2T_x$ does not show photocatalytic activity for the degradation of HCTZ. However, this paper presents the current status and potential for the practical application of $Ti_3C_2T_x$.

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P-32

THE INFLUENCE OF THERMAL ANNEALING OF Pt-BASED THIN FILMS ON ELECTRO-OXIDATION OF FORMIC ACID

Dragana Milošević, Sanja Stevanović, Nebojša Nikolić, Dušan Tripković

*University of Belgrade - Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy,
Njegoševa 12, 11000 Belgrade, Republic of Serbia*

Due to their high electrocatalytic activity, Pt-based materials are widely investigated as electrocatalysts for the electro-oxidation of small organic molecules for fuel cells technology applications, contributing to the potential reduction of fossil fuel use in the near future. In addition to methanol, formic acid has also gained increasing attention as a potential fuel for direct fuel cells due to lower toxicity, non-flammability and a lower storage cost. The electro-oxidation of formic acid on Pt-based thin films is taking place predominantly via indirect pathway, through the dehydrogenation reaction of formic acid, with the formation of CO as a poisoning species. The activity of electrocatalysts is dependent both on surface structure and surface orientation in terms of the arrangement of the atoms at the surface. Controlled heat treatment led to the rearrangement of surface atoms thus enhancing the catalytic properties. In order to investigate changes in morphology before and after thermal annealing, Pt/CrNi catalysts were characterized using an atomic force microscope (AFM). The performance of all catalysts was tested in formic acid electro-oxidation reaction. The synergistic effect of individual metallic components, in the designed catalyst, resulted in high activity and exceptional stability. The approach demonstrated in this work may promote the development of new generation of high-performance catalysts for use in direct formic acid fuel cells (DFAFCs).

Keywords: Pt thin films; NiCr supports; thermal treatment; electro-oxidation; formic acid

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SYNTHESIS OF Eu AND Yb BASED DIRAC SEMIMETALS

Mihael Brezak, Nikola Miše, Mario Novak

Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, Zagreb University, Croatia

Dirac semimetals are a new class of materials with a broad scope of promising future applications. [1] Synthesis of monocrystals of these materials is often difficult and requires special attention and dedication. [2] Europium and Ytterbium are highly susceptible to oxidation, and the synthesis requires procedures being done inside an inert atmosphere or vacuum. The crystal grower must take many effects into account in order to acquire high-quality monocrystals, which can then be used to investigate novel properties intrinsic to the material.

We will present crystal growth techniques used in our laboratory to obtain high-quality Dirac semimetals. We shall discuss the use of different equipment used in the crystal growth process, including the Bridgman furnace, and how they are used in the synthesis of materials such as EuCd_2As_2 , EuMnBi_2 and YbMnBi_2 .

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P-34

ENHANCEMENT OF UP-CONVERSION LUMINESCENT CHARACTERISTICS OF $\text{Yb}^{3+}/\text{Ho}^{3+}$ CO-DOPED Bi^{3+} BASED SrGd_2O_4 NANOPARTICLES

Tijana Stamenković¹, Nadežda Radmilović¹, Ivana Dinić²,
Marina Vuković³, Tanja Barudžija¹, Maria Čebela¹, Vesna Lojpur¹

¹*Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Institute of Technical Science of SASA, Knez-Mihailova 35/4, Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Innovative Centre, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Belgrade, P.O. Box 51 Belgrade, Serbia*

In this investigation, samples of SrGd_2O_4 doped with different Yb^{3+} (2, 4, 6 at.%) ions and constant Ho^{3+} (1 at.%) and Bi^{3+} (2 at.%) concentrations were prepared. The sol-gel method with glycine as a fuel and citric acid as a chelator was chosen for sample preparation. All samples were heated in the furnace for 1.5 h at

500 °C and then thermally treated for 2.5 h at 1000 °C. The pure orthorhombic lattice of SrGd₂O₄, space group *Pnma*, was revealed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) (JCPDS Card No.:01-072-6387). Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) discovered agglomerated clusters of spherical particles measuring around 150 nm in size. Including Bi³⁺ ions into the structure influenced the morphology of the sample showing fine packing of pyramidal-shaped nanoparticles. The uniform distribution of constitutive elements in the samples was confirmed by energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). Up-conversion emission properties were evaluated from photoluminescent emission spectra and intensity dependence on excitation power after excitation at 976 nm. Dominant green (550 nm), red (671 nm), and infrared (758 nm) ⁵F₄, ⁵S₂ → ⁵I₈, ⁵F₅ → ⁵I₈, ⁵F₄, ⁵S₂ → ⁵I₇ transition emissions, respectively, are detected in all samples. The sample co-doped with Bi³⁺ showed the most intense photoluminescent emission.

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BACTERIAL CELLULOSE (BC)-CeO₂ NANOCOMPOSITE FILM FOR CHRONIC WOUND TREATMENT

Svetlana Butulija¹, Jelena Filipović Tričković¹, Ana Valenta¹,
Bratislav Todorović², Sanja Petrović², Bojana Četenović¹,
Željko Radovanović³, Danica Zmejkoski¹, Branko Matović¹

¹*“Vinča” Institute of Nuclear Sciences - National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Faculty of Technology, University of Niš, Leskovac, Serbia*

³*Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade, Serbia*

Bacterial cellulose (BC) is a promising natural polymer with a range of characteristics such as biocompatibility, microporosity, transparency, conformability, elasticity, the ability to preserve a moist environment, as well as absorb exudates in wounds. That is why BC is an attractive material in biomedical applications, especially in skin tissue repairing, but its lack of antimicrobial activity limits its performance. To overcome this shortage, BC was combined with cerium (IV)-oxide (CeO₂) nanoparticles. For BCCeO₂ /1, NPs were randomly distributed among BC nanofibers, and for this sample the reduction of MN frequency was most pronounced. BCCeO₂ /1 also showed the highest protection from the effect of H₂O₂ on cell proliferation. Redox parameters in blood plasma samples were also examined. All of the composites have antimicrobial activity in comparison with the control sample. This material has possible application as a wound-healing material, especially in chronic wound treatment.

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SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF REINFORCED ALUMINA COMPOSITES

J. Maletaškić, A. Luković, J. Erčić, E. Nidžović, M. Prekajski-Djordjević,
B. Matović¹

“Vinča” Institute of Nuclear Sciences - National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

Alumina composite was prepared via simple route. Alumina ceramics that resembles seashells are made of aligned micron-sized monocrystalline platelets joined together by silica secondary phase. SiO₂ was added to improve mechanical properties of composite. The evolution of the phase composition during thermal treatment was investigated by X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) and thermal analyses. Effect of sintering temperature on mechanical properties, due to the increase of sintering temperature that can produce a higher strength and higher density, was also investigated. SEM observation of composite was also included. Ceramics composites such as this are good candidates for high temperature oxidation atmosphere applications, as they have excellent mechanical and other performance requirements.

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ALUMINUM-BASED COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH CERAMIC FIBERS

Danica Maksimović^{1,2}, Vladimir Pavkov², Vesna Maksimović²,
Barbara Putz³, Ivana Cvijović-Alagić²

¹*Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences - National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Department of Materials Science, Montanuniversität Leoben, Leoben, Austria*

The modern transportation industry is in high demand for lightweight structural components with exceptional mechanical properties that can be obtained by a cost-effective production process. These specific industrial requirements can be achieved through the attainment of innovative aluminum matrix composites (AMCs) with improved characteristics in accordance with the circular economy. Solid-state recycling is considered a good solution to attain the above-mentioned industrial

demands since it enables the obtainment of usable and inexpensive raw materials with known chemical composition from industrial waste and therefore supports the cost-effective production of structural components. The present research was, therefore, directed toward the repurposing of waste materials derived from the metal industry and the civil engineering sector through a simple and economical solid-state recycling procedure to obtain raw materials for the production of innovative AMCs with required characteristics. The aluminum 2xxx series alloy, *i.e.* 2024 alloy, in the form of metallic chips generated during the industrial machining was selected for the obtainment of composite base, while basalt fibers derived from stone mineral wool, as waste material in civil engineering, were used to produce the composite reinforcing phase. Basalt, characterized by high strength and low density, provides improved resistance to chemical and mechanical damage, while the 2024 alloy contributes to good fatigue properties of the final fiber-reinforced AMCs. To obtain usable raw materials for the AMCs preparation from the solid industrial waste the basalt fibers were thermally treated, while aluminum-based metallic chips were ball-milled. Treated aluminum alloy powder and basalt fibers were mixed in a 3D tumbler mixer in a 9:1 ratio, isostatically pressed, and sintered in a protective argon atmosphere at 550 °C. Isostatic pressure and sintering duration were varied during the AMCs preparation to determine the optimal processing parameters for the obtainment of AMCs with the required characteristics for a predetermined purpose. The scanning electron microscopic (SEM), energy dispersive spectroscopic (EDS), and X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses complemented with hardness and density measurements were conducted to characterize starting and final materials. Obtained composites showed improved mechanical properties compared to the starting aluminum alloy, regardless of the processing conditions. The AMCs processed at a higher pressure and for longer sintering times showed higher density and hardness. The results of the presented research undoubtedly indicated that solid-state recycling, as a simple, energy- and cost-efficient process, can be successfully used for the attainment of innovative composites for lightweight structural components in the transportation industry.

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P-38

SPS DENSIFICATION OF B₄C-SiC COMPOSITES

Branko Matović

Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences – National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

Boron carbide (B₄C) - silicon carbide (SiC) ceramic composites were obtained through the densification of B₄C and β-SiC powders with different ratios using the spark plasma sintering (SPS) technique. The thermal treatment was carried out for 5 min in Ar atmosphere in a temperature range from 1850 to 2000 °C under a pressure of 70 MPa. The effect of starting powders ratio on the sintering behavior, relative density, microstructural development, and mechanical properties of the obtained composites was investigated. The obtained results showed that only starting compounds, *i.e.* B₄C and SiC phase, are observed in the sintered ceramic materials. SEM micrographs revealed that the sintered composites are composed of densely compacted B₄C and SiC grains with a uniform distribution of both phases. The maximal relative density value (100 %) was achieved for the sample densified at 2000 °C with 25% of B₄C and 75% of SiC. The microhardness of obtained composites ranges from 33 to 43 GPa, depending on the constituents' content and the densification temperature. The maximal microhardness value was achieved for the composite densified at 2000 °C which contains a maximal amount of B₄C (75%). In order to examine the behavior of composites in extreme conditions, the surface changes induced through the interaction of obtained composite materials and CO₂ pulse laser were also studied. During the irradiation, the laser pulse duration was ~2 μs with average pulse energy of 120 mJ. The results of this study show that the SPS technique can be a very effective densification method for the obtainment of additive-free B₄C - β-SiC ceramic composites with promising properties for application in radiation at extremes.

Keywords: B₄C-SiC ceramics, SPS, microstructure, mechanical properties, laser

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INVESTIGATING NTC THERMISTOR, FERROELECTRIC AND ELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF Fe_2TiO_5

Zorka Ž. Vasiljević¹, Milena P. Dojčinović¹, Nikola Ilić²,
Jelena Vujančević³, Maria Vesna Nikolić¹

¹*University of Belgrade, Institute for Multidisciplinary Research,
Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences - National Institute of the Republic of
Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

³*Institute of Technical Science of SASA, Belgrade, Serbia*

Pure phase orthorhombic pseudobrookite (Fe_2TiO_5) was synthesized using a modified sol-gel method. Bulk samples were obtained by uniaxial pressing of the obtained powder into compacts sintered at 900 °C for 2 h. A noticeable NTC thermistor effect was noted with a $B_{20/55}$ value of 5747 K and high resistivity of 45 $\text{M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ at 25 °C. A non-linear current-voltage characteristic was observed in the voltage range (0.2–1100 V) at room temperature (25 °C). Non-saturated (lossy) P - E loops were obtained at both measured frequencies (100 Hz and 1 kHz) more expressed for the higher measured frequency, with the maximal polarization of 0.291 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and remanent polarization of 0.123 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ for 20 kV/cm^2 and 1 kHz. Complex impedance measured in the temperature range 20–330 °C enabled analysis of the contribution of grain boundary and grains to the conduction mechanism. Bulk conductivity data determined in this temperature range was analyzed using Jonscher's universal dielectric response model and showed that the conduction process followed the nearest neighbor hopping conduction mechanism.

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INFLUENCE OF GD-DOPING ON ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES IN $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Gd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x=0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2$) PEROVSKITES

Milena Rosić¹, Maria Čebela¹, Nebojša Labus², Marko Radović³,
Sonja Aškračić⁴, Zorana Dohčević Mitrović⁴, Marija Stojmenović¹

¹Laboratory for Material Science, Institute of Nuclear Sciences “Vinča”,
National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, P.O. Box
522, 11001 Belgrade, Serbia

²Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, Knez Mihailova 35/IV, 11000
Beograd, Serbia

³University of Novi Sad, Center for Sensor Technologies, Biosense Institute,
Novi Sad, Serbia

⁴Center for Solid State Physics and New Materials, Institute of Physics
Belgrade, University of Belgrade, Pregrevica 118, 11080 Belgrade, Serbia

$\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Gd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x = 0.05\text{--}0.20$) nanostructured perovskites were successfully synthesized by modified glycine nitrate procedure (MGNP). Temperature intervals of sintering and phase transition during heating were revealed during dilatometric measurements. In order to determine the band gap values of the tested samples, ellipsometric measurements were performed in the UV-VIS spectral range. Decrease of band gap values with increase of Gd dopant content was attributed to n-type doping and upward shifting of the Fermi level in the conduction band. The investigation of the crystal structure and phase content of nanocrystalline $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Gd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ powders was continued using micro-Raman spectroscopy. The electrical conductivity of Gd^{3+} doped sintered samples CaMnO_3 as a function of temperature was measured by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), in the temperature range of 400–700 °C. The corresponding activation energies of conductivity, measured in the investigated temperature range, were also discussed. The obtained research results showed that the highest hardness values of 7.58 GPa respectively, were achieved and that these nanostructured materials can be used as a high-density ceramic material for various industrial applications.

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P-41

EFFECT OF CoMoO₄ NANOPOWDERS SYNTHESIZED BY GLYCINE NITRATE PROCEDURE AND CALCINATED AT 450 °C ON BRIGGS-RAUSCHER OSCILLATORY DYNAMICS

Milena Rosić¹, Jelena Maksimović², Jelena Senčanski³, Vladimir Dodevski¹, Maria Čebela¹, Marina Simović-Pavlović⁴, Maja Pagnacco⁵

¹Laboratory for Material Science, Institute of Nuclear Sciences „Vinča“, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Serbia

²Faculty of Physical Chemistry, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

³University of Belgrade, Institute for General and Physical Chemistry, Serbia

⁴University of Belgrade, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Belgrade, Serbia

⁵University of Belgrade, Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, Department of Catalysis and Chemical Engineering, Belgrade, Serbia

Cobalt molybdate is of importance for the development of mobile telecommunication systems, such as mobile phones and high-quality microwave dielectric ceramics for high resonant frequency selectivity in microwave devices. Due to their special catalytic properties, cobalt molybdates have been used as catalysts in many chemical and petrochemical processes. The CoMoO₄ nanoparticles were synthesized in a simple, quick, and inexpensive way, by using a glycine nitrate procedure (GNP), with and without calcination at 450 °C [1], and investigated by applying the Briggs-Rauscher oscillatory reaction method [2]. The complex oscillatory BR reaction is sensitive to different insoluble analyte addition [3]. This feature of BR oscillatory reaction is used to investigate effect of different masses of GNP synthesized (with and without calcination at 450 °C) CoMoO₄ samples on oscillatory dynamics. These two samples give the complete different effects in BR reaction. Obtained results strongly suggest that BR oscillatory reaction could be used for distinguishing these two samples, opening new direction in the investigation of ceramics materials.

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P-42

WHAT HAPPENS WHEN BiFeO₃ UNDERGOES POTENTIODYNAMIC POLARIZATION?

Milica Vujković¹, Zoran Jovanović², Danica Bajuk-Bogdanović¹,
Nataša Tomić³, Maria Čebela^{2,4}

¹University of Belgrade, Faculty of Physical Chemistry, Belgrade, Studentski trg
12-16, Belgrade, Serbia

²Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences University of Belgrade, National Institute of
the Republic of Serbia, Mike Petrovića Alasa 12-14, Belgrade, Serbia

³Institute of Physics Belgrade, University of Belgrade, Pregrevica 118, 11080,
Belgrade, Serbia

⁴Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb, Bijenička c.
32, HR-10000 Zagreb, Croatia

Unlike its ferroelectric and magnetic properties [1], the electrochemical behavior of bismuth ferrite, BiFeO₃ (BFO) has received less attention [2]. In this contribution, BFO was hydrothermally synthesized [3] to be examined as an electrode for metal-ion aqueous rechargeable batteries. BFO powder was first investigated in terms of structural and surface properties using X-ray diffraction and Thermally-Programmed Desorption methods and then characterized in Li and Na- containing aqueous electrolytes using Cyclic Voltammetry and Chronopotentiometry. BFO was found to be inactive within the electrochemical potential window of the aqueous electrolyte. However, its ability to be electrochemically transformed, under deep cathodic polarization, results in an active phase composed of Bi- and Fe-based oxides, as confirmed by Fourier-transform infrared and Raman spectroscopy. The redox behavior of BFO-derived oxide electrode is compared in both Li and Na -based aqueous electrolytes and discussed in the context of tailoring electrochemical properties for safe and sustainable metal-ion batteries.

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P-43

INFLUENCE OF Ag DOPING ON THE MORPHOLOGICAL AND MAGNETIC PROPERTIES IN CuO NANOPOWDERS

Maria Čebela^{1,2}, Uroš Čakar³, Vesna Lojpur¹, Maja Milošević⁴,
Sanja Krstić¹, Vladimir Dodevski¹, Milena Rosić¹

¹*Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia,
University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb, Bijenička c.
32, HR-10000 Zagreb, Croatia*

³*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Pharmacy, Department of Bromatology,
Belgrade, Serbia*

⁴*Department of Mineralogy, Crystallography, Petrology and Geochemistry,
Faculty of Mining and Geology, University of Belgrade, Đušina 7, 11000
Belgrade, Serbia*

We studied the influence of Ag doping on the crystal structure and magnetic properties of CuO nanopowders. For the synthesis of nanoparticles of copper-silver oxides solid solutions with the composition $\text{Cu}_{1-x}\text{Ag}_x\text{O}$ ($x=0.01-0.05$), a self-propagating synthesis was applied at room temperature, during which a successful reaction between metal nitrate and sodium hydroxide occurred. Prepared powders were calcinated at 700 °C for 2 h. The diffraction pattern was recorded at room temperature and atmospheric pressure without of any re-heating of the sample. The Rietveld method for fitting refinement procedure was performed which showed the incorporation of Ag^{3+} ions in the CuO crystal lattice, where they substitute Cu^{2+} ions. SQUID magnetometer was used for investigation of magnetic behavior of synthesized materials in temperature interval 2–400 K. It is known that copper(II) oxide exhibits ferroelectricity driven by magnetic order at temperature as high as 230 K [1]. Multiferroic phase is present above the first order phase transition at $T_{N1} = 213$ K and exists up to the subsequent first order phase transition $T_{N2} = 230$ K [1,2]. It was shown that disorder in the form of impurities can stabilize the ferroelectric phase [2] this was our motivation to dope CuO with Ag in order to improve further its multiferroic properties. Compared with CuO, we observed small changes in magnetic properties in $\text{Cu}_{1-x}\text{Ag}_x\text{O}$. The size and morphology of the particles were successfully determined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

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P-44

HYPERFINE INTERACTIONS IN THE HEXAGONAL STRUCTURE OF CuFeO₂ DELAFOSSITE

Karolina Siedliska¹, Kamila Komędera², Tomasz Pikula¹

¹Lublin University of Technology, Lublin, Poland

²AGH University, Cracow, Poland

Delafossites are binary oxides of the type ABO, where A is a monovalent cation such as Cu, Ag, and Pd, and B represents trivalent metal ions such as Al, Co, Cr and Fe, with the parent compound the CuFeO₂ [1]. Two polymorphs of delafossite compounds exist, a rhombohedral (3R) and hexagonal (2H) form with *R3m* and *P6₃/mmc* space group, respectively [2], which differ in the stacking orientation of the double layers consisting of edge-sharing B^{III}O octahedra and of triangularly arranged A^I layers.

In general, delafossite materials exhibit an interesting combination of properties which drives research into diverse application areas ranging from thermoelectrics and Li-ion batteries to pollutant degradation and solar energy conversion [3]. Besides, delafossites in general and CuFeO₂ in particular exhibit very interesting magnetic properties with complex ordering phenomena and geometric frustration at low temperatures. As the synthesis of the 2H delafossite polymorph is quite challenging, the magnetic properties of the 2H polymorphs are much less investigated. This is particularly visible for CuFeO₂, for which, the synthesis of the 2H polymorph without 3R contribution has been barely reported and, thus, the 2H magnetic structure is still under open discussion.

We report on an investigation of the hexagonal polymorph of delafossite CuFeO₂ using a sample obtained by hydrothermal synthesis and methodically based on X-ray diffraction and Mössbauer spectroscopy. Low-temperature measurements of the Mössbauer effect allowed for shining some light on the magnetism in 2H-CuFeO₂ which contrasts with the well-established one in 3R-CuFeO₂. They revealed complicated spectral shapes at low temperatures indicating complex magnetic structures like spin density waves and magnetic relaxations below 20 K.

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SYNTHESIS, STRUCTURE AND MAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF Fe₂TiO₅

Maria Čebela^{1,2}, Priyanka Reddy², Uroš Čakar³, Nebojša Labus⁴,
Vesna Lojpur¹, Vladimir Dodevski¹, Milena Rosić¹

¹*Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia,
University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

²*Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb, Bijenička c.
32, HR-10000 Zagreb, Croatia*

³*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Pharmacy, Department of Bromatology,
Belgrade, Serbia*

⁴*Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, Knez Mihailova 35/IV, 11000 Beograd,
Serbia*

Iron(III) titanates are attracting rapidly growing interest as very promising candidates for applications in solar energy and optoelectronics because they contain earth-rich elements. Potentially, Fe₂TiO₅ is a thermoelectric material. We used a Vibrating Sample Magnetometer and Superconducting Quantum Interferometer Device Magnetometer to study the magnetic properties of the pseudobrookite material Fe₂TiO₅. The material was synthesized by the sol-gel method. The structural parameters of the synthesized samples were investigated by X-ray analysis. The diffractogram was refined with the help of Rietveld refinement on FullProf Suite. Temperature-dependent ZFC and FC magnetization was measured on SQUID for lower temperature down to 2 K and on VSM for higher temperatures up to 1000 K. A transition was observed at 815 K with a separation between the ZFC and FC curves. Parallely the bifurcation in the isothermal hysteresis measurements indicates that the system exhibits dominant canted AFM (or weak FM) with a small amount of spin glass. The small value of the moment was also pointing towards the canted AFM ordering. The size and morphology of the particles was determined using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

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